

Agro2Circular

D7.7 – Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Final)

May 2025

Authors: Essi Paronen (VTT); Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Vafa Järnefelt (VTT), lines Toivanen (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT) and Silvia Forin (VTT)

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – March 2025 (42 months)

Deliverable No.	D7.7D54
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 7 - A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability
Task	T7.3 - Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring
Lead beneficiary	VTT
Contributing beneficiary/ies	TECH PARTNERS
Due date of deliverable	9 May 2025
Actual submission date	6 May 2025

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1	5.3.2025	First draft of document
v0.2	31.3.2025	Revised version based on the comments of Fuensanta Monzo – CETEC and Maite Ferrando (KVELOCE)
v1.0	31.3.2025	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1	30.4.2025	First draft based upon first final version
v2.0	06.5.2025	Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	5.3.2025	Reviewers, LCA data providers and WP7 leader
v1.0	28.3.2025	Coordinator, reviewers and WP7 leader
v.1.1	30.4.2025	Coordinator and WP7 leader

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Alba Matamoros	6.5.2025
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó	6.5.2025

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the views of the author(s) the European Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the A2C consortium shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	11
2	Introduction	14
3	Methodology	16
3.1	Life cycle assessment (LCA)	16
3.1.1	Environmental impact assessment	16
3.1.2	Data collection methods	18
3.1.3	Data quality analysis	19
3.2	Carbon handprint	20
4	Agrifood and plastic waste system LCA	21
4.1	Goal and scope	21
4.1.1	Goal	21
4.1.2	Scope	21
4.1.3	Studied systems	23
4.1.4	Functional unit	25
4.1.5	Benchmark linear system	26
4.1.6	Assumptions	28
4.1.7	Allocation	29
4.1.8	Impact assessment method	29
4.1.9	Limitations	30
4.2	Sensitivity analysis	31
4.2.1	Renewable electricity	31
4.2.2	Water scarcity	31
4.2.3	Waste treatment function	32
5	Agrifood system	34
5.1	System description	34
5.1.1	Demo 4	36
5.1.2	Demo 3	38

5.1.3	Demo 2c.....	42
5.1.4	Demo 5.....	43
5.1.5	Demo 6.....	46
5.1.6	Demo 8.....	47
5.2	Results	47
5.2.1	Sensitivity analysis	54
5.2.2	Carbon handprint.....	63
5.3	Discussion	64
6	Plastic waste system	67
6.1	System description	67
6.1.1	Demo 1.....	68
6.1.2	Demo 2a EG to GA and 2b TPA to PCA	70
6.1.3	Demo 7.....	73
6.1.4	Demo 9.....	73
6.2	Results	74
6.2.1	Whole system.....	74
6.2.2	Without demo 2 a and b	77
6.2.3	Sensitivity analysis	82
6.2.4	Only demo 2a and 2b – carbon footprint	89
6.2.5	Carbon handprint.....	91
6.3	Discussion	92
7	LCA conclusions	96
8	Circularity monitoring	99
8.1	Framework	99
8.1.1	Objective	99
8.1.2	Methodology.....	99
8.1.3	CE Monitoring Framework.....	101
8.2	Application of the framework to demos	122
8.2.1	Scope of the application	123
8.2.2	Criteria applied in the choice of indicators	123
8.2.3	Analysis of the A2C demo cases.....	125

8.3 Discussion and conclusions	138
9 Bibliography	143
10 Annex.....	148

List of Tables

<i>Table 3-1. EF impact categories with respective impact category indicators, units, characterisation models and robustness (European Commission, 2021).</i>	16
<i>Table 3-2. Scale and type of the data used in the LCA.</i>	19
<i>Table 4-1. Reference flows, functional units and linear benchmarks used in the agrifood waste system LCA.</i>	25
<i>Table 4-2. Reference flows, functional units and linear benchmarks of the used in the plastic waste system LCA</i>	26
<i>Table 4-3. Factors for water use impact category on different level.</i>	31
<i>Table 4-4. Waste treatment processes used in the waste treatment function sensitivity analysis.</i>	32
<i>Table 5-1. Life cycle inventory of demo 4.</i>	38
<i>Table 5-2. Life cycle inventory of demo 3.</i>	41
<i>Table 5-3. Life cycle inventory of demo 2c.</i>	43
<i>Table 5-4. Life cycle inventory of demo 5.</i>	45
<i>Table 5-5. Life cycle inventory of demo 6.</i>	46
<i>Table 5-6. Life cycle inventory of demo 8.</i>	47
<i>Table 6-1. Demo 1 aggregated life cycle inventory. The table includes all the life cycle stages of demo 1.</i>	70
<i>Table 6-2. Life cycle inventory of demo 2a. The data is aggregated from all the processing steps.</i>	72
<i>Table 6-3. LCI data of the demo 2b. The data is aggregated from all the demo 2 b processing steps.</i>	72
<i>Table 6-4. Life cycle inventory of demo 7.</i>	73
<i>Table 6-5. Life cycle inventory of demo 9.</i>	74
<i>Table 8-1. Circular economy practice list with definitions.</i>	102
<i>Table 8-3. Environmental impact assessment metrics.</i>	110
<i>Table 8-4. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in Demo 3. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.</i>	127
<i>Table 8-5. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in Demo 4. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.</i>	129
<i>Table 8-6. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in Demo 5. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.</i>	131

<i>Table 8-7. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in Demo 6. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.</i>	133
<i>Table 8-8. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in Demo 8. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.</i>	135
<i>Table 8-9. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in Demo 2c. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.</i>	137

List of Figures

<i>Figure 4.1. System boundary of A2C LCA marked as the red line.</i>	22
<i>Figure 4.2. The studied A2C solution systems in the LCA. The demos belonging to the agrifood waste sub-system are highlighted in green, while the demos belonging to the plastic waste sub-system are highlighted in blue.</i>	24
<i>Figure 5.1. A2C agrifood waste system and the principal material flows. The green boxes illustrate the demo processes, and the underlined and bolded items are the A2C demo outputs.</i>	34
<i>Figure 5.2. Contribution analysis by different A2C agrifood system life cycle stages (processing steps) with market electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	48
<i>Figure 5.3. Contribution analysis by different A2C agrifood system process types with market electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories. The results are characterised.</i>	50
<i>Figure 5.4. Comparison of the A2C agrifood system with market electricity to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.</i>	52
<i>Figure 5.5. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C agrifood system with market electricity, and of linear benchmark system.</i>	53
<i>Figure 5.6. Contribution of different A2C agrifood system life cycle stages (processing steps) with wind electricity to the environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	55
<i>Figure 5.7. Contribution of different A2C agrifood system process types with wind electricity to the environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	56
<i>Figure 5.8. Comparison of the A2C agrifood system with wind electricity to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.</i>	57
<i>Figure 5.9. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C agrifood system with wind electricity, and of linear benchmark system.</i>	58
<i>Figure 5.10. Normalised and weighted results of agrifood system with market electricity, reported with life cycle stages, and lemon production shown as separate code.</i>	60
<i>Figure 5.11. Agrifood system results compared to benchmark system, and to benchmark system combined with composting treatment for the biowaste.</i>	61
<i>Figure 5.12. Agrifood system results with market electricity and two water scarcity factors, global and Murcia area.</i>	63

<i>Figure 6.1. A2C plastic waste system and the principal material flows. The green boxes are part of the demo 1. The underlined and bolded items are the A2C demo outputs.</i>	67
<i>Figure 6.2. Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages (processing steps) to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	75
<i>Figure 6.3. Comparison of the A2C plastic system with all demos to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the A2C plastic waste system is divided with the value of the linear system. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.</i>	76
<i>Figure 6.4. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system and of the linear benchmark system.</i>	77
<i>Figure 6.5. Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages (processing steps) without the demos 2 a and b to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	78
<i>Figure 6.6. Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system process types without the demos 2 a and b with market electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	79
<i>Figure 6.7. Comparison of the A2C plastic system without the demos 2 a and b to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the A2C plastic waste system is divided by the value of the linear system. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.</i>	80
<i>Figure 6.8. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2 a and b and of the linear benchmark system.</i>	81
<i>Figure 6.9. Sensitivity analysis: Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages without the demos 2 a and b with wind electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	82
<i>Figure 6.10. Sensitivity analysis: Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system process types without the demos 2 and b with wind electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.</i>	83
<i>Figure 6.11. Sensitivity analysis: Comparison of A2C plastic system with renewable electricity to the system with market electricity. The value of the A2C plastic waste system with wind electricity is divided with the value of the same system with market electricity. The value of the system with market electricity is manually set to be 1.</i>	84
<i>Figure 6.12. Sensitivity analysis: Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2a and b with market and wind electricity.</i>	85
<i>Figure 6.13. Sensitivity analysis: Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2a and b with Murcia watershed and global water use impact factors.</i>	87
<i>Figure 6.14. Sensitivity analysis: Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system with market electricity and benchmark system added with incineration and landfill waste treatment function.</i>	88
<i>Figure 6.15. Carbon footprint of the A2C laboratory-scale glycolic acid and linear benchmark product lactic acid. The results are modelled using Spanish market electricity.</i>	89
<i>Figure 6.16. Carbon footprint of the A2C laboratory-scale PCA and linear benchmark product benzoic acid. The results are modelled using Spanish market electricity.</i>	90

Figure 6.17. Carbon handprint of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2 a and b and using Spanish market electricity. In this calculation the substitution ratio of the A2C demo output compared to the linear benchmark is not taken into account. This aspect should be considered in a wider LCA calculation where the final product where the A2C demo output is applied is studied. _____ 92

List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
CE	circular economy
CFF	circular footprint formula
EF	environmental footprint
EG	ethylene glycol
GA	glycolic acid
LCA	life cycle assessment
LDPE	low density polyethylene
MHET	monomeric mono-2-hydroxyethyl terephthalate
PA	polyamide
PBAT	polybutylene adipate terephthalate
PCA	protocatechuic acid
PE	polyethylene
PEF	product environmental footprint
PET	polyethylene terephthalate
PHBV	poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
PTA	purified terephthalic acid
RER	region of Europe
RoW	rest of the world
TPA	terephthalic acid
TPS	thermoplastic starch
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

1 Executive summary

In this LCA (life cycle assessment) study, the environmental impacts of the Agro2Circular (A2C) agrifood, plastic package waste and agriculture film upcycling solution are calculated together with creating a circularity monitoring framework for selected agrifood and plastic cases. The LCA has two primary goals: identifying the most relevant process improvements for future technology development through hotspot analysis, and to benchmark the environmental performance of the A2C circular solution to a functionally equivalent linear solution. The purpose of combining benchmarking and hotspot analysis is to identify what are the aspects of the novel A2C system which need to be possibly improved to reach the levels of sustainability as the more developed benchmark products.

The main contributors to the environmental impact of the A2C solution are electricity consumption and production of the used chemicals. In the agrifood chain, the hotspots are the electricity consumptions of demo 5 process fermentation and demo 2c processes yeast fermentation and solvent evaporation. The impact of manufacturing the used chemicals is significant in demos 5, 6 and 8. In the plastic waste system, the electricity consumption of the demo 2b dominates the results. These hotspots are explained by the less developed technology of the A2C solution compared to the industrially optimized processes found in the linear benchmark system.

A sensitivity analysis is conducted to test how selected modelling assumptions impact the environmental performance of the A2C solution. The tested assumptions are application of renewable electricity and local watershed scarcity factors for water use impact category in the A2C solution. Additionally, the impact of the avoided waste treatment emissions caused by directing the waste to A2C upcycling processes instead of waste treatment is studied. This impact is evaluated by benchmarking the A2C solution's environmental impact against the linear benchmark system because the avoided waste treatment emissions are added to the benchmark system.

The results of the renewable electricity sensitivity assessment show that the environmental impact of the agrifood waste system with renewable electricity is decreases 41 % and plastic waste system 73 % (excluding the demos 2 a and b from the assessment) when wind

electricity is applied instead of market electricity. Contrarily, applying local watershed factor in the impact category water use showed negligible impact to the overall environmental footprint of both agrifood and plastic waste system. The impact of the avoided waste treatment emission has a negligible impact to the difference of the environmental performance of the agrifood system and plastic system including all demos. The sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the results of presented in this deliverable can be considered as robust.

The LCA results indicate that currently, when all the demonstrators with different TRL levels are included in the assessment and the benchmark system is modelled using industrial-level data, the A2C agrifood and plastic waste system are not yet more environmentally sustainable than the linear benchmark systems. The agrifood waste system's environmental impact is 3 times higher than the linear benchmark system's and the plastic waste system's impact is 23 times higher. It should be noted that in the plastic waste system, the life cycle stages which contribute the most to the result (production of PCA from TPA and GA from EG) are modelled using laboratory scale data. Also, the agrifood system contains partly laboratory-scale data. Simultaneously, the benchmark systems represent more industrial-level processes which are typically more efficient in energy and chemical use and yields. If these two life cycle stages are subtracted from the results in order to be able to investigate the plastic waste system better, the environmental impact of the plastic waste system is 49 % smaller than the linear benchmark systems.

Even if the A2C agrifood results were higher than of the compared benchmarks, they are in quite the same scale, and with improvements the same level can be reached. The whole plastic waste system's environmental impact compared to the benchmark can only be evaluated when more upscaled data is available.

The novel circularity monitoring framework outlined in this deliverable provides a step-by-step guide, distinguishing between intrinsic and impact-related metrics. Applying this framework to the A2C case study shows that following these steps can efficiently identify crucial elements in case-specific circular economy monitoring and improve the alignment of circularity assessment with impact-based methods like LCA. This study resulted in a list of recommended circularity monitoring metrics, offering a practical approach for A2C demo

practitioners to evaluate the development and impact of their activities related to the circular economy.

2 Introduction

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project develops new technologies for the upcycling of fruits & vegetable agri-food wastes (F&VW) and non-renewable multilayer plastics into new high added value products with application in the food, nutraceuticals, cosmetic and agriculture sectors.

To verify the environmental sustainability of new technologies such as the ones developed in the A2C project, sustainability assessments, such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), are needed. LCA as a method examines that no relevant life cycle stage is excluded and that environmental burdens do not shift along the value chain or environmental impact categories.

Circularity is at the core of the A2C project as the A2C concept promotes circularity by upcycling agrifood wastes into valuable bioactives and recyclable compounds, enhancing resource efficiency. Hence, it is crucial to monitor the circularity to ensure that the objectives of the A2C concept are met. This addresses this requirement by presenting a framework to monitor the circularity of the A2C concept.

These deliverable updates the D7.6 which was a screening LCA study. In the screening LCA, the carbon footprint was estimated for producing fiber and phenolic extract in the demonstrator 3 and plastic pellet in the demonstrator 9. This D7.7 includes a more comprehensive assessment of the environmental sustainability of the whole A2C systemic solution covering the agrifood and plastic waste system. Also, a circularity monitoring framework is set and applied to selected A2C system parts to evaluate the circularity of the A2C system. In this deliverable, the LCA and circularity monitoring aspects are presented in separate chapters. By presenting the chapters individually, the deliverable aims to ensure that the reader can easily understand and navigate through the specific methodologies, results, and implications of each aspect. However, in the conclusions chapter of circularity monitoring (chapter 8.3), the deliverable combines the two aspects to provide a holistic understanding of the potential to reduce environmental burden and to promote resource efficiency and circularity.

The purpose of this deliverable is to identify already in the technology development stage the main contributors (e.g. process or life cycle stage) to the environmental impacts of the A2C waste systems chains and provide valuable feedback for the technology developers.

3 Methodology

3.1 Life cycle assessment (LCA)

The study follows the LCA methodology described more in detail in the Agro2Circular D7.5 Evaluation framework and Methodology. LCA is a standardised method for assessing the potential environmental impacts of a product or a service taking into account the whole life cycle. The relevant standards are ISO 14040:2006 “Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework” (International Organization for Standardization, 2006a) and ISO 14044:2006 “Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines” (International Organization for Standardization, 2006b). Also, the European Commission has provided a general guide describing the LCA method for Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) calculations (European Commission, 2021). This LCA applies the impact assessment method suggested in the PEF methodology (European Commission, 2021).

3.1.1 Environmental impact assessment

The EF3.1 impact assessment methodology by the European Commission (2021) was used for the characterization, normalization and weighting of the LCA results. The method includes 16 impact categories which are listed in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1. EF impact categories with respective impact category indicators, units, characterisation models and robustness (European Commission, 2021).

EF impact category	Impact category indicator	Unit	Characterisation model	Robustness
Climate change, total	Global warming potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	Bern model - Global warming potentials (GWP) over a 100-year time horizon (based on IPCC 2013)	I
Ozone depletion	Ozone depletion potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	EDIP model based on the ODPs of the World Meteorological	I

			Organisation (WMO) over an infinite time horizon (WMO 2014 + integrations)	
Human toxicity, cancer	Comparative toxic unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h	Based on USEtox2.1 model (Fantke et al. 2017), adapted as in Saouter et al., 2018	III
Human toxicity, non-cancer	Comparative toxic unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h	Based on USEtox2.1 model (Fantke et al. 2017), adapted as in Saouter et al., 2018	III
Particulate matter	Impact on human health	Disease incidence	PM model (Fantke et al., 2016 in UNEP 2016)	I
Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to U ₂₃₅	kBq U ₂₃₅ eq	Human health effect model as developed by Dreicer et al. 1995 (Frischknecht et al, 2000)	II
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC eq	LOTOS-EUROS model (Van Zelm et al, 2008) as applied in ReCiPe 2008	II
Acidification	Accumulated exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ eq	Accumulated exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)	II
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated exceedance (AE)	mol N eq	Accumulated exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)	II
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009) as applied in ReCiPe	II
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009) as applied in ReCiPe	II
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTU _e)	CTU _e	Based on USEtox2.1 model (Fantke et al. 2017), adapted as in Saouter et al., 2018	III
Land use	Soil quality index	Dimensionless (pt)	Soil quality index based on LANCA model (De Laurentiis et al. 2019) and on the LANCA CF version 2.5 (Horn and Maier, 2018)	III
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	m ³ water eq of deprived water	Available WATER REMaining (AWARE) model (Boulay et al., 2018; UNEP 2016)	III
Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP)	kg Sb eq	van Oers et al., 2002 as in CML 2002 method, v.4.8	III

	ultimate reserves)			
Resource use, fossils	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ	van Oers et al., 2002 as in CML 2002 method, v.4.8	III

The results of this deliverable in chapters 5.2 and 6.2 are reported as environmental footprint following the impact assessment methodology of PEF (European Commission, 2021). Next, the steps of transforming the LCA results to environmental footprint is explained. First, the characterised results are shown which mean that characterisation factors are applied to convert an assigned life cycle inventory result to the common unit of the EF impact category indicator. The characterised results are *normalised* by dividing them with normalisation factors that represent the overall inventory of a reference unit (e.g. a whole country or an average citizen). According to the PEF method (European Commission, 2021): “Normalised life cycle impact assessment results express the relative shares of the impacts of the analysed system, in terms of the total contributions to each impact category per reference unit.”. The normalised results are dimensionless. After normalisation, the results are *weighted*. In the weighting, results are multiplied by a set of weighting factors, which reflect the perceived relative importance of the impact categories. The study applies the weighting proposed by PEF where more weight is given for the most robust impact categories. Finally, the single score environmental footprint is calculated based on the normalised and weighted results.

In the interpretation step of the LCA, the life cycle stages which are examined in more detail are selected based on the normalized and weighted single score results. In this LCA, the term life cycle stage corresponds to a processing step within the A2C concept.

3.1.2 Data collection methods

An Excel template was developed for LCA data collection. This template was utilized to gather data from project partners for each of the demonstrators (hereinafter referred to as demo). The required information includes the amounts and types of raw materials, energy consumption, and other necessary input resources, as well as the output products, emissions, and waste generated in the manufacturing process.

3.1.3 Data quality analysis

In this LCA, the primary data was directly collected from the demo leaders and other technical project partners. However, since the development of the A2C system is still ongoing, there are some uncertainties regarding the representativeness of the data for industrial use. Therefore, all results presented in this report should be considered preliminary and not final. It is recommended to update the calculations once the solutions are fully adopted on an industrial scale.

Each demonstrator description features a chapter detailing the assumptions used in the calculations. Together with the primary data, secondary information for the life cycle inventories was gathered from public data sources. For certain input materials and conventional linear benchmarks, specific datasets were unavailable, and proxies were used. The used proxies are listed in the assumptions section of each of the demos.

Secondary data used in the assessment is from the ecoinvent 3.10 database, using the system model “cut-off by classification”. This represents the best technological, geographical, and most up-to-date data available for LCA with high precision and completeness as requested by ISO 14040 (2006).

The demos are on different technological scales which impact the data quality. Also, part of the data was estimated instead of real measured data. Table 3-2 below lists the data scale and type used in the LCA.

Table 3-2. Scale and type of the data used in the LCA.

Demo	Life cycle stage	Scale (laboratory/demonstrator/industrial)	Data type (estimated/real)
1	pre-treatment	pilot	estimated
	optical sorting	demonstrator	estimated
	delamination and sorting	demonstrator	real and estimated
	pre-treatment to enzymatic attack	pilot	estimated

	PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET	demonstrator	estimated
	MHET conversion	demonstrator	estimated
2a	EG to GA	laboratory	real and estimated
2c	TPA to PCA	laboratory	real and estimated
2c	lemon extract to lemon oil	laboratory	real and estimated
3	Lemon enzymatic extraction	pilot	real
4	Artichoke Microwave-assisted extraction	pilot	real
5	PHBV and carotenoids production	pilot	real and estimated
	PHBV extraction	pilot and industrial scaled	estimated
6	-	industrial	estimated
7	-	industrial	estimated
8	-	industrial	estimated
9	-	industrial	real

3.2 Carbon handprint

All products have a footprint, i.e. there are inevitable negative impacts in the life cycle of products. Some products, however, can also show positive impacts by enabling others to reduce their footprints e.g. by being more energy efficient in the use stage, creating less material loss in the production stage, or by being longer-lasting in use than the competitive products with the same function. The term handprint is used to refer to these positive impacts that products enable in other actors' value chains.

In this project, the handprint methodology suggested by Pajula et al. (2021) was used to model the potential carbon handprint of the A2C solutions. The method compares the carbon footprints of a baseline (reference situation most likely to occur in the absence of the offered solution, being the linear benchmark products in this project) and the new solution that has a lower footprint. Other environmental handprints (i.e. resource, water, air quality or nutrient handprints) suggested by Pajula et al. (2021) are not considered in this project.

4 Agrifood and plastic waste system LCA

The LCA model for the A2C solution was split into two parts to simplify the analysis: one sub-system for agrifood waste and one for plastic waste. These subsystems are referred to as agrifood waste and plastic waste systems hereafter. This chapter outlines the shared components of both systems' LCAs. More detailed descriptions of the systems are presented in dedicated chapters 5.1 and 6.2.

4.1 Goal and scope

4.1.1 Goal

The first goal of this LCA is to detect which processes or life cycle stages have the highest contribution to the A2C systems' environmental impacts. This will be performed via hotspot analysis. The second goal is to benchmark the environmental performance of the A2C circular solution to a functionally equivalent linear solution. The purpose of combining the benchmarking and hotspot analysis is to identify what are the aspects of the novel A2C system which need to be possibly improved to reach the level of sustainability as the more developed benchmark products.

4.1.2 Scope

The processes included in the LCA are shown in Figure 4.1. The red line defines the cradle-to-gate system boundary, which includes the part of the product's life cycle reaching from the production of raw materials to the finalization of the product at company gate.

Figure 4.1. System boundary of A2C LCA marked as the red line.

The A2C system begins with receiving the agrifood, packaging, and agriculture film waste. The selected agrifood waste are artichoke and lemon. These waste types were selected based on data availability. These materials are processed and upcycled in the demonstration units. The system ends after the production of the demo outputs which can be considered as products. It should be noted that the manufacturing of the necessary inputs, such as chemicals, is included in the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), but these inputs are not reflected in Figure 4.1. Also, the use stage and end-of-life of final products are not included in the LCA. These stages are excluded because the goal of the LCA is to evaluate the A2C demos, and the A2C ingredients produced in them.

Additionally, the transport, used packaging materials, and infrastructure are excluded. Transport is not included because the distances between the demos are assumed to be short and the system is not yet at a commercial scale with optimised logistics routes. Packaging materials are excluded because they can be recycled again. Infrastructure, such

as emissions related to building the machines, is not included because its impact is typically negligible in an LCA study.

4.1.3 Studied systems

In the following, the two systems assessed via LCA (agrifood waste and plastic waste, highlighted in green and blue respectively in Figure 4.2) are illustrated in detail. Green boxes represent the demos 3, 4, 5, 6 and 8 and the green text in the white demo 2 box stands for demo 2c. The plastic waste system, which includes demos 1, 7, 9, 2a and 2b, is marked by blue boxes and blue text in the white demo 2 box. Detailed information on each of the demos is available in the project's technical deliverables.

Figure 4.2. The studied A2C solution systems in the LCA. The demos belonging to the agrifood waste sub-system are highlighted in green, while the demos belonging to the plastic waste sub-system are highlighted in blue.

In theory, the agrifood and plastic systems are connected to each other. The link takes place between the demos 1 and 5 where the water rejections from demo 1 are directed to demo 5. However, in this LCA the link is excluded due to lack of data and the two systems are considered as separate.

4.1.4 Functional unit

This LCA consists of a complex system with several input waste flows and outputs with different functionalities. The main reference flows in the agrifood waste system are lemon and artichoke. For the plastic waste system, the main reference flows are plastic packages and agricultural film waste. The functional units of this LCA's agrifood system are listed in the Table 4-1 and the plastic waste systems in the Table 4-2. The functional units are amounts of the A2C demo outputs in the column "Amount – functional unit".

The functional units of the linear benchmark systems are similarly listed in Table 4-1 and Table 4-2 in the columns "Amount – functional unit" and "Linear system benchmark".

Table 4-1. Reference flows, functional units and linear benchmarks used in the agrifood waste system LCA.

Reference flow and amount	Demo	A2C demo output	Amount – functional unit	Linear system benchmark	LCI data source
artichoke 100 kg	4	dietary fibre	1,2 kg	inulin from chicory root	Hingsamer et al. 2022
		antioxidant extract	0,3 kg	ascorbic acid	ecoinvent 3.10: ascorbic acid production, RER
lemon 2314 kg	3	dietary fibre	166,6 kg	inulin from chicory root	Hingsamer et al. 2022
		phenolic extract	43,97 kg	hydroquinone	ecoinvent 3.10: hydroquinone production, RER
	2c	microbial oil	15,11 kg	crude coconut oil	ecoinvent 3.10: market for coconut oil, crude, GLO
	6	pellet: TPS-PBAT (90%) and A2C PHBV (10%)	537,4 kg	TPS-PBAT pellet	Nessi et al. 2022
	8	pellet: PBAT (90%) and A2C PHBV (10%)	537,4 kg	PBAT pellet	Nessi et al. 2022

The reference flow amount of artichoke is selected based on the demonstrator trials.

The amount of 2314 kg of treated lemon waste was chosen as the reference flow because it represents the quantity processed by CTNC to obtain the extracts needed for demos 6 and 8.

Table 4-2. Reference flows, functional units and linear benchmarks of the used in the plastic waste system LCA

Reference flow and amount	Demo	A2C demo output	Amount – functional unit	Linear system benchmark	LCI data source
plastic package waste 1200 kg	1 and 2a	glycolic acid	15,69 kg	lactic acid	ecoinvent 3.10: lactic acid production, RER
	1 and 2b	protocatechuic acid	22,94 kg	benzoic acid	ecoinvent 3.10: benzoic acid production, toluene oxidation, RER
	1 and 7	non-biodegradable plastic pellet for food packages + compatibilizer (maleic anhydride)	802,9	virgin LDPE pellet + stabiliser additive (PVC)	ecoinvent 3.10: polyethylene production, low density, granulate, RER and polyvinylchloride production, bulk polymerization, RER
	1	-	115 kg	virgin ethylene	ecoinvent 3.10: market for ethylene, RER
agriculture film waste 1735 kg	1 and 9	non-biodegradable plastic pellet for agriculture film	1000 kg	virgin LDPE pellet	ecoinvent 3.10: polyethylene production, low density, granulate, RER

The amount of plastic bag waste and agriculture film waste reference flows is selected based on the demonstrator trials.

4.1.5 Benchmark linear system

To benchmark the environmental sustainability of the A2C solution, it is necessary to select conventional linear benchmark products which correspond to the A2C demo outputs.

4.1.5.1 Agrifood system

Table 4-1 shown in the chapter 4.1.4 lists the agrifood waste A2C demo outputs and their respective linear benchmarks used in the LCA model.

The demo 3 and 4 benchmark for dietary fibre is chosen to be inulin from chicory root, based on the same use purpose as a dietary fibre. The production of inulin is based on a LCA study by Hingsamer et al. (2022) and modelled using the Netherlands as location similarly as in the LCI data source.

Following the recommendation of the demo leaders, tertiary butylhydroquinone was selected as demo 3 benchmark for phenolic extract. Due to a lack of suitable data, hydroquinone was used as a proxy for tert-butylhydroquinone, based on the hydroquinone production dataset from ecoinvent 3.10. Tert-butylhydroquinone, a member of class hydroquinone, is assumed to be an adequate comparison. Hydroquinone production is modelled with Spanish electricity mix.

The benchmark for the artichoke antioxidant extract produced in demo 4 is ascorbic acid, as recommended by the demo leaders because it has been used in other nutraceutical formulations in their portfolio. Both ascorbic acid and tert-butylhydroquinone are polyphenols with antioxidant properties suitable to be used as benchmark, but ascorbic acid was chosen to differentiate between the two similar demos. Also in this case, the use of Spanish market mix electricity is assumed.

The benchmark for demo 2c is based on expert opinion. The crude grade of coconut oil is assumed to match the microbial oil as it also requires further processing before it could be applied in the cosmetic industry. For the coconut oil, the dataset is applied directly from the ecoinvent database.

In demo 6, the A2C output is a blended pellet which consists of TPS-PBAT and PHBV derived from the A2C demo 5. In this demo, the PHBV is the circular component and the TPS-PBAT the linear. Therefore, the linear benchmark is a pellet made only from TPS and PBAT using Spanish electricity. Similarly in demo 8, a pellet made only from PBAT (produced using Spanish electricity) is selected to be the benchmark.

4.1.5.2 Plastic waste system

The benchmarks of the plastic waste system LCA and the benchmark data sources are shown in Table 4-2 in chapter 4.1.4.

For demo 2a the selected reference is lactic acid, since LCI data on glycolic acid production was not available. The lactic acid is considered a valid proxy because it is also a hydroxy acid. Similarly, for protocatechuic acid the benchmark benzoic acid is used as a proxy since it is also a hydroxybenzoic acid. For the demo 7, the benchmark is pellet made from virgin LDPE with a PVC stabiliser additive. The linear benchmark requires a stabiliser additive (PVC) whereas the A2C demo 7 output needs a compatibiliser (maleic anhydride). In demo 9, the benchmark is virgin LDPE pellet without additives and compatibilisers because they are not used in the A2C demo 9 output. The benchmark related to demo 1 is added to the benchmark system because from demo 1 recyclable plastic can be collected. Thus, the amount of ethylene is added to the benchmark model. Ethylene was selected because it is the main raw material of a LDPE.

4.1.6 Assumptions

This subsection lists the common assumptions used for the agrifood waste and plastic waste system. Both systems include system-specific assumptions which are listed in chapters 5 and 6.

- The locations of all the A2C processes are in Spain although the demo 2a, b and c experiments took place in Italy. Spain was the chosen location because the Agro2Circular demonstrator is situated there.
- The input waste, agrifood and plastic, are considered burden-free. Therefore, no emissions are assigned to them. The impact of avoided waste management for the agrifood and plastic waste are considered in the sensitivity analysis, as explained further in chapter 4.2.3.
- The impact of allocating no emissions to the input raw material (though being a waste from the previous life cycle) is a methodological decision that needs to be tested with sensitivity analysis according to the ISO standards 14040-44. To see what the maximum burden for the waste used as a raw material could be, lemon production is considered with mass-based allocation, i.e. using the lemon production dataset from

ecoinvent directly as the burden for the lemon waste. The burdens are shown in the results transparently with code “lemon production”. Inclusion of burden for lemon waste is reviewed with sensitivity analysis in chapter 5.2.1.2. Overall, in LCA and circular ecosystems, the question of when a waste turns into a valuable raw material is difficult to define, but if there is demand/market for waste material, it becomes a by-product at some point and should carry an environmental burden as well.

- The technical characteristics of the A2C outputs are similar as the benchmarks and they can substitute the benchmarks in a ratio of 1:1. Similarly, the use of the A2C outputs does not change the production of the final products where they are used. These assumptions are used due to the scope of the study shown in Figure 4.1 which starts from the raw material acquisition and ends with the production of the A2C demo output. The required technical properties and product formulations take place in the final products marked in Figure 4.1.

4.1.7 Allocation

In this LCA the input waste to the agrifood and plastic systems is assumed not to have any burden for the A2C system, i.e. allocation from the previous life cycles is avoided as a cut-off approach. The impact of this approach is tested in demo 3 with the lemon value chain as explained earlier.

To avoid allocation in the A2C agrifood systems, processes were considered as an entity, i.e. a full system with several outputs instead of allocating the burdens to different products.

In the plastic waste system, allocation was not necessary as the plastic waste system is examined as a singular unit which produces all the A2C outputs.

4.1.8 Impact assessment method

As stated in chapter 3, the EF 3.1 impact assessment method is used in this LCA study.

4.1.9 Limitations

The LCA contains limitations which impact the robustness of the results. Given the limitations outlined below, the LCA results should be regarded as indicative and suitable for screening purposes only.

1. No emissions are assigned to the plastic system input waste streams. In this LCA the burden for the plastic waste is discussed in chapter 7.3.
2. When circular products replace linear products, the LCA should take into account the ratio to which extent the circular product can replace a linear product, and if the final product, where the circular product is applied, requires additional processing or has changes of product composition due to using the circular product. The substitution ratio or possible changes in the processing of composition of the final product are not taken into account in this LCA due to the scope of the study as explained in chapter 5.1.3.
3. In the plastic waste system, laboratory-scale data is combined with demonstrator and pilot-scale data in three demos due to the limited availability of demonstrator-scale data of all the processes. However, this limitation is resolved by analysing the results with and without the laboratory-scale processes.
4. The scale of the data used in the LCA is not fully industrial which limits the interpretation of the results especially when the A2C demo outputs are compared to the linear benchmarks.
5. The EF3.1 version that was applied in the calculations was based on the version provided by the ecoinvent database. This means that global characterisation factors were used instead of country specific factors. This mainly affects the impact categories of land use and water use. For the land use, the difference between the factors is not major, since the global factor is ca 50 and Spanish ca 58, meaning that the importance of land use is slightly underrated in the results but considered reasonably realistic. For water use, the difference in the water scarcity factors is bigger (globally ca 43 and in Spain ca 78) and thus the impact of this difference is tested with a sensitivity analysis.

4.2 Sensitivity analysis

To analyse the results better, selected sensitivity analyses are performed for the agrifood and plastic chain LCA results. The executed sensitivity analyses are described in this section.

4.2.1 Renewable electricity

The aim of renewable electricity sensitivity analysis is to detect the impact of applying less carbon intensive electricity in the A2C system. In the main results, the LCA is calculated for Spanish market electricity and in the sensitivity analysis for wind electricity. The wind electricity is modelled using ecoinvent 3.10 process electricity production, wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore, ES. The wind electricity was selected because in Spain it covers the highest share out of all renewable electricity production types, accounting for 25% of the produced electricity in the ecoinvent process market for electricity, high voltage, ES

4.2.2 Water scarcity

The impacts of water usage are highly dependent on location where the water is consumed. In LCA it is possible to model water consumption on global, country or watershed level. For each of the levels, specific characterization factors for impact category water use can be applied. The Table 4-3 shows different characterization factors which represent the water use in m³.

Table 4-3. Factors for water use impact categories on different levels.

Level	Characterization factor (m ³)	Source
Global	43,0	EF 3.1
Country (Spain)	77,7	AWARE
Watershed (Murcia)	80,6	AWARE

In the results for which water scarcity sensitivity assessment is not performed, the global values are applied. In the sensitivity assessment for agrifood and plastic waste system, the watershed level factor for Murcia region has been applied for primary water production and for A2C processes which release water to air. The aim of the sensitivity analysis is to perceive how the local factor influences the results of the water use impact category.

4.2.3 Waste treatment function

The functional unit of this LCA takes into account manufacturing new materials for different industries. However, the A2C solution can also be considered to have another function which is the treatment of waste. Namely, waste treatment emissions can be avoided when using the waste as raw materials in A2C solution instead of directing the waste to waste treatment facilities. The objective of this sensitivity analysis is to detect the impact of the avoided waste treatment which takes place at a waste treatment plant. In the waste treatment function sensitivity analysis, the avoided waste treatment emissions are assigned to the benchmark system. This approach is selected instead of subtracting the waste treatment emissions from the A2C solution results because the waste treatment is not the primary function of the A2C solution in this LCA.

Table 4-4 shows the selected waste treatment processes for the agrifood and plastic waste system which are added to the benchmark system.

Table 4-4. Waste treatment processes used in the waste treatment function sensitivity analysis.

A2C waste system	Treated waste	Waste treatment	ecoinvent 3.10 process
agrifood	2414 kg (lemon + artichoke)	industrial composting	treatment of biowaste, industrial composting, RoW
plastic	2189 kg PE	incineration	treatment of waste polyethylene, municipal incineration, GLO
	75 kg PET		treatment of waste polyethylene terephthalate, municipal incineration
	2264 kg	landfill	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, sanitary landfill, RoW

For the agrifood waste system, the treated waste is the sum of the lemon and artichoke waste. This waste is treated in an industrial composting treatment. Food waste is not treated as landfill, since there was no available dataset describing landfilling of biowaste, but mostly a mixture of biological and thermal disposal.

The plastic waste system's waste treatment function is modelled for two options: incineration and landfill. The amount of treated waste is the plastic package waste and agriculture film waste from which the soil is subtracted because it is not plastic. The treatment of the soil is not taken into account in this sensitivity analysis.

5 Agrifood system

5.1 System description

In this chapter the agrifood system is described in more detail. The agrifood system on a higher level is shown in Figure 4.2 with green boxes and text to demonstrate the life cycle stages and demos to which they are connected. Figure 5.1 below shows the agrifood system more in detail.

Figure 5.1. A2C agrifood waste system and the principal material flows. The green boxes illustrate the demo processes, and the underlined and bolded items are the A2C demo outputs.

The agri-food system consists of processing of two separate agri-food waste streams, artichoke and lemon. Artichoke is processed separately from others in demo 4. Lemon is processed first in demo 3, from which the output fractions are sent to demo 2c and demo 5. From demo 5 the bio-based material is sent further to demos 6 and 8.

The demo 4 uses artichoke waste to produce dietary fibre and antioxidant extract. The first processes are washing and cutting of artichoke waste, enzymatic extraction, and filtration into solid and liquid phases. The liquid phase then undergoes centrifugation and ultrafiltration, and finally dehydration where solid enriched in dietary fibers is achieved. The solid phase processing contains microwave-assisted extraction and purification, to gain antioxidant extract.

The lemon waste enters the demo 3 at the pre-treatment stage, where the lemon peel and pulp are cut to smaller pieces. Water and chemicals are added, and the lemon waste is enzymatically extracted and separated with filtration into solid and liquid phases. The solid phase is purified and dehydrated into dietary fibre. The liquid phase is concentrated and purified with resins. From the purification stage the stream is separated into permeate liquid extract rich in sugars (to be used further) and to purified liquid phase to go through freeze-drying/lyophilisation into phenolic extract. The sugary fraction from lemon waste in demo 3, is then sent further to demo 2c and demo 5.

In the demo 2c the sugary fraction is used for producing microbial oil using biotechnology processes. The demo 2c consists of processing steps; yeast fermentation, deepwell plate centrifugation, deepwell extraction and solvent evaporation.

In the demo 5 the sugary fraction undergoes fermentation, filtration and drying and then the dried solids would go through two processes; PHBV extraction and purification, and carotenoids production. Due to lack of data, the total mass of dried solids goes through PHBV extraction, and thus carotenoids production is excluded. The demo 5 does not have any final output product, but the PHBV material sourced from lemon waste is processed further in demos 6 and 8.

In demos 6 and 8, the PHBV obtained from demo 5 is used to manufacture biodegradable pellets for food packaging (demo 6) and for agriculture film (demo 8). In demo 6 the PHBV is blended with starch-TPS and PBAT and in demo 8 with PBAT.

5.1.1 Demo 4

This part focuses on the microwave-assisted extraction of artichoke waste. This process is operated separately from all other demos, starting with 100 kg artichoke waste. The products, dietary fibre and antioxidant extract, can be derived from the separated liquid and solid phases, respectively.

Demo 4 could also process other agricultural wastes, for example lemon or grape, which would have higher sugary fraction / liquid waste stream to be utilized further in demo 5.

5.1.1.1 Assumptions

The following assumptions were used when modeling the demo 4:

Pre-treatment

- Cutting artichoke waste is done by an electrically operated cutter.
- Artichoke is washed with tap water.

Extraction

- The washed and cut artichoke waste is mixed with tap water.
- Artichoke/water mixture undergoes extraction with an electrical microwave extractor.
- The unit of used enzymes is converted from ml to grams with an assumed density of 1 g/ml.

Filtration

- Separation of liquid and solid phases is done with manual filters and not considered to use any electrical power.
- The liquid phase contains soluble fibers, as dietary fibers.
- The solid phase obtained contains antioxidant compounds.

Centrifugation of liquid phase

- Electrically operated centrifugation is included, but in the future this stage could be omitted by using filtration with metallic sieves.

Ultrafiltration of liquid phase

- Excess water is disposed of into general drain and general wastewater treatment.
- Electricity for ultrafiltration is sourced from solar panels located on the facility.

Dehydration of liquid phase

- Excess water from electrical drying is disposed of into general drain and general wastewater treatment.

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) of solid phase

- The MAE process is repeated 10 times to process the total mass of solid treated with enzymes, inputs are multiplied to treat all the mass.
- The ethanol used in the MAE is partly circulating and assumed that 80 % of the ethanol can be reused in the process. This 80% of ethanol is therefore excluded from the calculations, and only 20% of ethanol needed is considered as input to MAE.
- The ethanol used is evaporated to air.
- Excess solid waste biomass is separated from the solution of the antioxidant. This biomass could in theory be used as nitrogen/carbon source for fermentation in demo 5, but due to its low sugary content it cannot be utilized efficiently and is discarded. This biomass could be used as piglet feed, substituting other feed production, but no substitution benefits or downstream treatment processes (e.g. drying) are considered in this calculation.

Purification and Concentration of solid phase

- The purification-concentration process is repeated 10 times to process the total mass of solid treated with enzymes, inputs are multiplied to treat all the mass.
- As in MAE, the ethanol used in the process is assumed to be 80% reusable, which can be excluded from the study. 20% of the ethanol is included in the calculations.
- The ethanol used is evaporated to air.
- The final product, antioxidant extract, could be encapsulated, but this process is excluded here.

5.1.1.2 Life cycle inventory

Table 5-1 shows the inventory data used in modelling the demo 4.

Table 5-1. Life cycle inventory of demo 4.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
artichoke waste	100		kg	-
electricity, non-solar	590,48		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
solar electricity	15		kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted, ES
water	905		kg	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland
enzymes	0,01		kg	market for enzymes, GLO
citric acid	0,1		kg	market for citric acid, GLO
ethanol	130		kg	market for ethanol, without water, in 99.7% solution state, from ethylene, RER
solid enriched in dietary fibres		1,2	kg	-
antioxidant extract		0,3	kg	-
waste treated as wastewater		0,6697	m ³	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment, Europe without Switzerland
solid waste		100	kg	
ethanol to air		130	kg	-
water vapour		0,02880	m ³	-

5.1.2 Demo 3

This part focuses on the lemon waste enzymatic extraction process. The high-added value substances, as dietary fibre and phenolic extracts can be derived from extraction after which the solid and liquid phases are separated. The processing is carried out by CTNC.

Lemon is mostly used for its juice, and the waste is generated from fruit juice processing and vegetable canning companies. The lemon peel and pulp are discarded as waste, peel from juice extraction (squeezing) and pulp from pulp decrease stage. This white and yellow solid material has a high moisture content of circa 85%.

5.1.2.1 Assumptions

The LCA model consists of 2314 kg of lemon waste which is turned into products as described earlier in Table 4-1. The created extracts are dehydrated but are not 100 % dry matter, the dietary fibre has moisture content of 5,1 % and phenolic extracts of 4,1 %.

The following assumptions were used when modelling the demo 3:

Pre-treatment

- The lemon production is included in the model based on the mass allocation for lemon production. The burden of lemon waste could also be allocated as zero, since the material used is a waste stream from lemon juice production and would otherwise be discarded if not used in the A2C processes. The exclusion of the lemon production is covered with sensitivity analysis in chapter 5.2.1.2. This is the only demo where a burden for the waste material used as input is considered but it is done here as an example of the maximum impact that the agrifood waste streams could have.
- Lemon peel and pulp cutting is done by an electrically operated cutter.

Enzymatic Extraction

- The boiler feed water is included as normal tap water, instead of decalcified water as described by demo leaders, since there is no specific dataset for decalcified water in ecoinvent database.
- Ultrapure water is used for the lemon waste extraction.
- Natural gas used in the heating of the mixture in a tank is included with a dataset “market group for heat, central or small-scale sourced from natural gas”, to include all possible environmental impacts in addition to CO₂ emissions. The amount of natural gas used in m³ is converted to MJ with a factor of 38, meaning that 1 m³ natural gas has a heating value of 38 MJ.
- The enzymes used in the process are included with a global proxy, ecoinvent dataset called “market for enzymes”, which describes the average production of three commonly used enzymes.

Filtration

- Liquid and solid extracts are separated with decanter.
- No losses are considered at this stage.

Purification of solid phase

- The filtrated solid phase undergoes oxidizing washing with ultrapure water.

- Circa 16 % of the original solid matter is lost when washing of the fibre and discarded with wastewater.

Dehydration of solid phase

- The excess water from drying is disposed of into general drain and general wastewater treatment.
- Approximately 46% of the original solid matter ends up with the produced dehydrated fibre.

Concentration of liquid phase

- The excess water is separated in electrical membrane filtration equipment, and the condensed water is disposed of into general drain and general wastewater treatment.
- Circa 2 % of the original solid matter is lost in the pipelines, and in the following step of resin purification.

Purification of liquid phase with resins

- Production of adsorption and desorption resins is excluded from the calculations, since they are circulating and used multiple times.
- The electricity use of resin adsorption and desorption is included.
- The resins absorb the phenolic compounds, and the sugary fraction can be separated from phenolic compounds.
- The relation of the sugary fraction separated is 79:1, meaning 79 kg sugary fraction out of 80 kg liquid phase is treated with resins.
- Approximately 24,4% of the original solid matter ends up with the separated sugary fraction.

Lyophilisation

- The excess water from drying is disposed of into general drain and general wastewater treatment.

- Approximately 12% of the original solid matter ends up with the produced freeze-dried polyphenols (=phenolic extract).

5.1.2.2 Life cycle inventory

Table 5-2 shows the inventory data used in modelling the demo 3.

Table 5-2. Life cycle inventory of demo 3.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
lemon waste	2314		kg	-
electricity	3923,36		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
heat	1,06E+04		MJ	market group for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, RER
water, ultrapure	17752		kg	market for water, ultrapure, RER
water	8794		kg	market group for tap water, RER
enzymes	0,23		kg	market for enzymes
oxidising agent	2,222		kg	hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state, RER
dehydrated solid extract/ fibre extract		166,6	kg	-
dehydrated liquid extract / phenolic extract		43,97	kg	-
liquid extract rich in sugars to demos 5 and 2c		3656	kg	-
waste treated as wastewater		16,243	m ³	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment, Europe without Switzerland
water to air		8,794	m ³	-

Benchmark product inulin is modelled based on the inventory data in the publication of Hingsamer et al. (2022), where the carbon footprint was about 1,5 kg CO_{2e}/kg inulin. The production was assumed to take place in the Netherlands, and thus it was modeled with Netherlands specific data for electricity and fertilisers' production. For other inputs, European or global average data from ecoinvent was used. Water used for the inulin washing is not considered, even though harvested roots are washer, chipped and cleaned, then roots are extracted. Also, the average transport of 100 km from field to factory are excluded. The values are calculated from the annual inulin production amount of 10 300 tons. The nitrogen fertilizer used in the cultivation phase emits dinitrogen monoxide, and this is included in the calculations. Also, the waste biomass from inulin processing is included and handled as ecoinvent average data "market for biowaste", when in Hingsamer et al. (2022) it was excluded as a zero reasoned by IPCC for being the biomass burned.

Hingsamer et al. (2022) used ecoinvent 3.7.1., when this study used ecoinvent 3.10. and EF v3.0.

5.1.3 Demo 2c

Demo 2c uses the sugary fraction from lemon waste processed in demo 3 as an input for the fermentation process. Since the same fraction is used also by demo 5, it is calculated with the assumption that 30 % of the sugary fraction is used as input material in demo 2c.

5.1.3.1 Assumptions

Yeast fermentation

- The KOH and HCl were presented as 100 % pure chemicals in the LCI data Table 5-3 even though they were used in 1M concentration. The water in the chemical solutions was excluded from the modeling.
- The impacts of compressed air covered only the electricity consumption of the air compressor.
- The input cooling water did not have emissions because it was recycled again after this process.
- There was volume loss due to sampling and evaporations. These losses were caused by releases of water vapor.

Centrifugation

- The electricity consumption of the centrifuge was considered negligible at the laboratory scale due to short operation time (0.3 h) of the centrifuge. Thus, it was excluded.
- The spent medium is modelled as 100 % water although it contains also minor amounts of other materials. The spent medium was discarded for wastewater treatment because the data was based on laboratory scale evaluation. However, in a more upscaled solution the spent medium could be used in other applications, such as a fertilizer.

Extraction

- 90 % of the solvents (BA and K1) can be recycled. In the LCI data, only the refurbished amount is listed.
- The aqueous waste is discarded as average wastewater treatment.

Solvent evaporation

- 33.33 % of the output solvent is butyl acetate. This was calculated based on the share of the butyl acetate of the total solvents used in the experiment. The K1 solvent is assumed not to have use stage emissions according to the manufacturer's product sheet.

5.1.3.2 Life cycle inventory

Table 5-3 shows the inventory data used in modelling the demo 2 c.

Table 5-3. Life cycle inventory of demo 2c.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process
lemon extract	1097		kg	-
electricity	3,02E+04		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
polypropylene glycol	1,03		kg	market for propylene glycol, liquid, RoW
demineralized water	256,3		kg	market for water, deionised, Europe without Switzerland
KOH	0,6407		kg	market for potassium hydroxide, GLO
HCl	0,001002		kg	market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state, RER
solvent BA	56,51		kg	market for butyl acetate, RER
solvent K1	113		kg	market for solvent, organic, GLO
microbial oil		15,11	kg	-
butyl acetate to air		33,91	kg	-
waste treated as wastewater		1941,3	l	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment, Europe without Switzerland
carbon dioxide, non-fossil to air		26,91	kg	-
water vapour to air		0,1106	m ³	-

5.1.4 Demo 5

Demo 5 uses the sugary fraction from lemon waste processed in demo 3 as an input for the fermentation process. Since the same fraction is used also by demo 2c, it is calculated with an assumption that 70 % of sugary fraction is used as input material in demo 5.

The process is carried out with three separate operators. First the operator handles the process from fermentation to drying, second is in charge of the PHBV extraction and purification, and third manages the carotenoids from lemon waste.

Demo 5 does not have final output products, but the material processed is moved further to demos 6 and 8 for bioplastic production. Thus, there are no benchmark products for demo 5 directly. The impacts of demo 5 could be allocated to demos 6 and 8, but in this study demo 5 impacts are reported on this separate name to show its impact transparently.

5.1.4.1 Assumptions

The following assumptions are used in the modelling of Demo 5:

Fermentation

- The used nitrogen source is calculated as a combination of organic + inorganic sources, inorganic as ammonium chloride and organic as fodder yeast in 1:2 ratio
- Data for phosphorous source, KH_2PO_4 (Monopotassium phosphate) is included stoichiometrically from the ingredients, phosphoric acid and potassium carbonate, based on the chemical reaction. The impact from the chemical production is excluded, and only production of ingredients is included.
- The KOH and HCl were presented as 100 % pure chemicals in the LCI data Table 5-4 even though they were used in 1M concentration. The water in the chemical solutions was excluded from the modeling.
- Tap water is used as the additional water source

Filtration

- Concentrated biomass is separated with electrically powered filter
- The water used for washing the biomass is considered and removed from the process into general drain and general wastewater treatment
- Salt water brine separated in the filtration could be circulated into a new fermentation process, which would keep the chemicals and nutrients circulating. Circulation of salt

water brine into a new fermentation process has been proved as suitable, but the recirculation was excluded from the calculations due to lack of data.

- Decreasing the need for new input nutrients and chemicals by reusing the salt water brine could decrease the impacts of demo 5 of the total agrifood system.

Drying

- Concentrated biomass is dried with an electrical evaporator.
- The excess water is evaporated into the air.

PHBV extraction and purification

- The data for PHBV extraction and purification is based on WETSUS experience and estimations on annual input of A2C biomass delivered for PHBV processing.
- PHBV extraction is assumed to happen near the fermentation stage and located in Spain using Spanish market electricity.
- PHBV extraction produces organic residues that could be used for heat production, but this compensation is excluded from the calculations.

Carotenoids production

- Production of carotenoids is excluded from the model for lack of data.

The impacts of demo 5 could be divided into demos 6 and 8 which use A2C PHBV material as input material, but due to transparency reasons, Demo 5 is reported in the results as its own entity.

5.1.4.2 Life cycle inventory

Table 5-4 shows the inventory data used in modelling of the demo 5.

Table 5-4. Life cycle inventory of demo 5.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
sugary fraction from demo 3	2559		kg	-
electricity	2,77E+04		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
heat	1163		MJ	market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry, RER
steam	5597		kg	steam production, in chemical industry, RER

hydrochloric acid	0,7746		kg	hydrochloric acid production, from the reaction of hydrogen with chlorine, RER
potassium hydroxide	2,957		kg	market for potassium hydroxide, GLO
sodium chloride	4180		kg	market for sodium chloride, powder, GLO
butanol	17,12		kg	market for 2-butanol, RER
water	1,129e+04		kg	market for tap water
nitrogen source	140,2		kg	phosphoric acid production, dihydrate process, RER and market for potassium hydroxide, GLO
PHBV		110,8	kg	-
wastewater		3,657	m ³	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment
water to air		1,645	m ³	-

5.1.5 Demo 6

5.1.5.1 Assumptions

The following assumptions are used in modelling of the Demo 6:

- The starch-PBAT is modelled using unit process data of starch (TPS)/PBAT blend from European Commission et al. (2022). This data modified by taking into account the differences between the total masses of EG and TPA in the usedecoinvent process to model the PBAT production and between the listed PBAT precursors (1,4-butanediol, adipic acid, and PTA) in the chapter 4.5.2.3.1 of the Nessi et al. (2022). The difference of the masses 0,09 kg/kg PBAT was divided into three and added in equal shares to the total mass of the PBAT precursors.
- The starch in the TPS is from maize
- The waste treatments of the waste from PBAT production are: hazardous waste - hazardous waste incineration, spent solvent mixture - hazardous waste incineration and waste plastic mixture - municipal incineration

5.1.5.2 Life cycle inventory

Table 5-5 shows the inventory data used in modelling the demo 6.

Table 5-5. Life cycle inventory of demo 6.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
PHBV from demo 5	55,40		kg	-
TPS-PBAT	498,6		kg	-

electricity, non-solar	591,4		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
electricity, solar	29,16		kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted, ES
biodegradable compounds		537,4	kg	-
products retained in the filters		16,62	kg	-

5.1.6 Demo 8

5.1.6.1 Assumptions

The following assumptions are used in modelling of the Demo 6:

- The PBAT is modelled using unit process data PBAT from European Commission et al. (2022). This data modified by taking into account the differences between the total masses of EG and TPA in the used ecoinvent process to model the PBAT production and between the listed PBAT precursors (1,4-butanediol, adipic acid, and PTA) in the chapter 4.5.2.3.1 of the Nessi et al. (2022). The difference of the masses 0,09 kg/kg PBAT was divided into three and added in equal shares to the total mass of the PBAT precursors.

5.1.6.2 Life cycle inventory

Table 5-6. Life cycle inventory of demo 8. shows the inventory data used in modelling the demo 8.

Table 5-6. Life cycle inventory of demo 8.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
PHBV from demo 5	55,40		kg	-
PBAT	498,6		kg	-
electricity, non-solar	591,4		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
electricity, solar	29,16		kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted, ES
biodegradable compounds		537,4	kg	-
products retained in the filters		16,62	kg	-

5.2 Results

The results for the whole A2C agrifood system are shown in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2. Contribution analysis by different A2C agrifood system life cycle stages (processing steps) with market electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.

The contribution analysis for the whole agrifood system with Spanish market electricity shows that all demos are quite visible in the results. The biggest impact in 12 out of 16 categories is from demo 5 (ca 30 - 58%) where the sugary fraction from lemon waste is treated with fermentation. In most categories the high impact of demo 5 is caused by the high electricity use for fermentation, impact varying between 18-90 % of total demo 5 impact in different categories. The second highest contributor in demo 5 is the production of sodium chloride used for fermentation. The fermentation uses a lot of chemicals, which could be decreased with the circulating system e.g. the remaining nitrogen and phosphorous sources in the salt water brine could be re-used. In the land use category, where demo 5 impact is largest (58 %), it is mostly (73 %) created by the land occupation and transformation in the yeast production value chain.

The demo 2c, also processing sugary fraction, has the second highest impacts in many of these 12 categories, which is mostly caused by electricity consumption. For example, in the climate change category demo 2c's electricity contributes to 93 % of demo impacts.

In categories material resources: metals/minerals, the largest shares are caused by demo 8 (42 %), and demo 6 (26 %) both impacts mostly (89-92 %) created by the use of antimony. In ozone depletion, demo 8 is responsible for 58 %, and demo 6 responsible for 35 %, in both demos caused mostly (ca 98%) by the bromomethane (Halon 1001) emissions from the production of purified terephthalic acid used as a raw material in the PBAT production process.

Demo 4, where artichoke waste is treated, has the lowest impact in 15 out of 16 categories, but the largest share in photochemical oxidant formation (49 %). This is caused mostly (91 %) from the emissions of ethanol used in the microwave-assisted extraction. The generally low impacts on demo 4 is foreseeable, since the artichoke waste treated (100 kg) is much lower than lemon waste (2 314 kg) in other demos.

Demo 3 with lemon enzymatic extraction has also a very low share compared to other demos, but the highest impact in water use (44 %), which is caused mostly (95 %) by the water use for lemon production that was included in the calculations. Demo 3 is the only demo with burden for the waste material, and here the burden is as large as possible in the LCA context, since the treated waste stream is included as traditional lemons which have high irrigation demand. This could be also excluded, which would decrease the impact of water use a great deal. Exclusion of lemon production is covered in the sensitivity analysis chapter 5.2.1.2. In addition, it must be noted that the water balance in the processes and in the ecoinvent data may not be perfectly balanced, so there are some uncertainties related to this impact category.

The agrifood system's results by process types are presented in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3. Contribution analysis by different A2C agrifood system process types with market electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories. The results are characterised.

Contribution analysis for all the demos analysed by process types show that overall, the production of the used chemicals and electricity have the largest impact when market electricity is used. Chemicals have the biggest contribution in seven categories: ecotoxicity: freshwater (49 %), eutrophication: freshwater (41 %), human toxicity: carcinogenic (52 %) and non-carcinogenic (46 %), land use (58 %), material resources (94 %), and ozone depletion (94 %). High impact from the production of chemicals is explained by the high resource use and emissions that occur in their production stage. Chemicals with the most impact are caused from traditional PBAT production in demos 6 and 8, e.g. antimony, butanediols, and adipic acid. Also, sodium chloride used in demo 5 has notable impact, and its impact could be decreased with recirculation.

Electricity production is the biggest contributor of seven categories: acidification (53 %), climate change (53 %), energy resources (72 %), eutrophication:marine (53 %), eutrophication:terrestrial (52 %), ionizing radiation (96 %), and particulate matter formation (42 %). This is explained by the emissions caused by the energy sector, for example sulfur dioxide emissions in acidification, carbon dioxide emissions in climate change, uranium and natural gas consumption in energy resources, and Radon-222 emissions in ionizing radiation.

In photochemical oxidant formation, the biggest share is caused by direct emissions (57 %), which are caused mainly by ethanol emissions to air (78 %) from MAE in demo 4 and solvent evaporation (15 %) in demo 2c. In water use, lemon production has a large impact (42 %), which is caused entirely by the use of water for the irrigation of lemon trees in Demo 3. Lemon production was included to the demo as a test, as explained in Demo 3 assumptions in chapter 5.1.2.1.

The other codes used for the result analysis are barely visible: fuels, waste treatment and water. Water has some impact in eutrophication:freshwater (18 %), caused by (99 %) the use of ultrapure water in demo 3, resulting from the ultrapure water process releasing phosphates to surface waters. Demo 3 uses ultrapure water for lemon extraction, while demo 4 uses tap water in the artichoke extraction. If water impact savings are wanted, the need for ultrapure water could be challenged.

The A2C agrifood system compared to benchmarks is shown in Figure 5.4. Comparing the agrifood system to benchmarks shows that the A2C system has higher impacts than benchmarks in all categories. In most categories the impact is maximum five-fold, but in ionizing radiation the impact of A2C is about 30-fold.

Figure 5.4. Comparison of the A2C agrifood system with market electricity to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.

Normalized and weighted results of agrifood system and linear benchmark system are presented Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C agrifood system with market electricity, and of linear benchmark system.

The normalized and weighted results for A2C agrifood system in total are ca. three times higher compared to the benchmarks. The benchmarks are linear products with industrialized and optimized processes. The A2C processes are mainly on pilot scale, and there is room for improvements for e.g. circulating the chemicals to decrease their consumption notably. When looking at climate change impact, all benchmarks have lower impacts compared to the relevant A2C demo production. Further development is thus needed to minimize the impacts of the A2C processes.

The normalized and weighted results show that the biggest impact from A2C solution are caused from energy resources (25 %), climate change (21 %), and material resources (17 %). The impact on energy resources (25 %) is mostly caused by demo 5 (39 %) and demo 2c (36 %). Demo 5 impact on energy resources is caused mostly by electricity use in

fermentation (74 %), and demo 2c impact from the sum of electricity used in yeast fermentation and solvent evaporation (93%).

The normalized and weighted impact on climate change (21 %) is also caused mostly by demo 5 (38 %) and demo 2c (27 %). Demo 5 impact is mostly caused by electricity used in fermentation (56 %) Demo 2c impact is mostly from the electricity needed for yeast fermentation and solvent evaporation (sum 91 %).

The impact of material resources (17 %) is caused by demo 8 (42 %), demo 5 (27 %), and demo 6 (26 %). Demo 8 and demo 6 impacts are mostly caused by antimony (92 % and 89 % respectively) used in PBAT production, demo 5 by sodium chloride (89 %) used in fermentation.

When the normalized and weighted results are analysed on a demo level, the impact is caused as follows: 34 % from demo 5, 24 % from demo 2c, 16 % from demo 8, 12 % from demo 6, 9 % from demo 3, and 5 % from demo 4.

5.2.1 Sensitivity analysis

5.2.1.1 Renewable electricity in full agrifood system

The results for the whole A2C agrifood system with wind electricity are shown in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6. Contribution of different A2C agrifood system life cycle stages (processing steps) with wind electricity to the environmental impact in EF impact categories.

Contribution analysis of all the agrifood demos processed with wind electricity shows that the impacts are quite evenly distributed, although demo 5 shows slightly larger impact (28-60 %) than others in 12 out of 16 categories. Similarly to market electricity, Demo 8 has the highest impact in material resources (42 %) caused by use of antimony, and in ozone depletion (60 %) caused by bromomethane emissions of purified terephthalic acid production. Also, similarly to market electricity, demo 4 has the biggest impact in photochemical oxidant formation (63 %) caused by ethanol (91 %) used in the MAE. Demo 3 has the biggest impact in water use (61 %), caused by the lemon production.

The contribution of different agrifood system's process types is presented in Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.7. Contribution of different A2C agrifood system process types with wind electricity to the environmental impact in EF impact categories.

Contribution analysis for the whole agrifood system with wind electricity shows that the production of chemicals becomes even more relevant, and it has clearly the largest impact in 14 out of 16 impact categories (48-98 %) when the impacts are broken down by the process types. For example, in the climate change category, there are a few chemicals (adipic acid, sodium chloride, 1,4 butanediol and purified terephthalic acid) used in demos 8, 6 and 5 that together contribute nearly 50% of the climate impact in total. In ozone depletion with 98 % impact from the production of chemicals, the most impact (97 %) is caused from the use of purified terephthalic acid in demos 8 and 6.

In the photochemical oxidant formation category direct emissions are the biggest contributor (73 %), which is mostly (78 %) caused by direct air emissions from ethanol use in demo 4 Microwave-assisted extraction. The highest impact of water use is caused by lemon production (60 %), entirely from the water consumption for lemon cultivation.

The other codes used for the result separation are barely visible: fuels, waste treatment and water. Water has some impact in eutrophication: freshwater (23 %), caused 99 % by the use of ultrapure water in demo 3, resulting from the ultrapure water process releasing phosphates to surface waters.

The A2C agrifood system with wind electricity compared to benchmarks is shown in Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.8. Comparison of the A2C agrifood system with wind electricity to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.

Comparing the agrifood system to benchmarks shows that the A2C system has higher impacts than benchmarks in all categories. In most categories the impact of A2C is two to three-fold, but in land use about five-fold, and in photochemical oxidant formation about seven-fold.

Normalized and weighted results of agrifood system and linear benchmark system are presented in Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C agrifood system with wind electricity, and of linear benchmark system.

The normalized and weighted results for A2C agrifood solution with wind electricity is almost double compared to the benchmarks. In this scenario, the electricity used in the benchmarks production is market electricity, and A2C solution with wind electricity. The benchmarks are linear products with industrialized and optimized processes. The A2C processes are pilot scale and there is room for improvements, e.g. by circulating the chemicals to decrease their consumption notably.

The normalized and weighted results show that the biggest impact from A2C agrifood system with wind electricity are caused by the use of material resources (28 %), climate change (18 %), and use of energy resources (13 %). The impact of material resources (28 %) is caused by demo 8 (42 %), demo 5 (27 %), and demo 6 (26 %). Demo 8 and demo 6

impacts are mostly caused by antimony (92 % and 89 % respectively) used in PBAT production, and the impact of demo 5 by sodium chloride (86 %) used in fermentation.

The normalized and weighted impact on climate change (18 %) is caused by demo 5 (32 %), demo 8 (and 27 %) and demo 6 (22 %). Demo 5 impact results from steam needed for PHBV processing (44 %) and sodium chloride (29 %) used in fermentation. Demo 8 and demo 6 impacts are mainly created during the production of the three main chemicals (adipic acid, 1,4-butanediol, and purified terephthalic acid) used for PBAT production (96% and 71 % respectively).

The impact on energy resources (13 %) is also mostly caused by demo 5 (28 %), demo 8 (28 %), and demo 6 (21 %). Demo 5 impact is mainly caused by steam needed for PHBV (48 %) and sodium chloride used in fermentation (27 %). Demo 8 and demo 6 impacts are mainly created during the production of the three main chemicals (adipic acid, 1,4-butanediol, and purified terephthalic acid) used for PBAT production (96% and 75 % respectively).

When the normalized and weighted results are analyzed on a demo level, the impact is caused as follows: 27 % from demo 5, 27 % from demo 8, 20 % from demo 6, 11 % from demo 3, 8 % from demo 2c, and 7% from demo 4.

5.2.1.2 Environmental burden of waste used as raw material

In LCA and circular ecosystems, most of the value chains produce several outputs in the form of products, by-products and waste. Typically, the environmental burdens are allocated between products and by-products in some way. The point when waste turns into a valuable by-product is difficult to define, but if there is an increasing demand or market for a waste material, it can be considered a by-product at some point and from that moment on, it should carry an environmental burden from the upstream value chain as well.

According to ISO standards 14040-44 (2006), the effects of choices regarding methodological decisions need to be tested with sensitivity analysis. The choice of allocating or not allocating emissions to the input raw material in A2C systems (though currently considered as waste from previous life cycles) is such a decision. To see what the maximum

burden for the waste used as a raw material could be, lemon peel and pulp waste is used as a test case. Lemon cultivation is considered with mass-based allocation, i.e. using the lemon production dataset from ecoinvent directly as the burden for the lemon waste. The burdens are shown in the results transparently with code “lemon production”. The impacts from lemon production in each impact category were shown already in Figure 5.7 and the share of lemon production in the normalized and weighted results can be seen in Figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10. Normalised and weighted results of agrifood system with market electricity, reported with life cycle stages, and lemon production shown as separate code.

The results for the total agrifood system don't change significantly even if the upstream burden for lemon waste is included or not, because the total share of lemon production is only 4 %, when the upstream burden is included in demo 3. The main difference is that the impact of Demo 3 almost entirely disappears from the water use category when lemon production is excluded from the calculations since it is caused mainly from the burden of lemon irrigation.

5.2.1.3 Waste treatment function

When lemon and artichoke waste are used as raw material for new production, the normal waste treatment is avoided. In the case of biowaste, the normal treatment could be for example composting. In this sensitivity assessment, the avoided waste treatment is included as processing in the benchmark system. The model is based on an ecoinvent process of “treatment of biowaste, industrial composting” for the amount of agrowaste used in the system, which is 2314 kg of lemon and 100 kg of artichoke waste. The comparison of benchmark with composting processing is illustrated in Figure 5.11.

Figure 5.11. Agrifood system results compared to benchmark system, and to benchmark system combined with composting treatment for the biowaste.

Impact of composting is calculated together with the benchmark product scenario, which is in the second pillar of Figure 5.11. Composting has a minimal impact on the overall result of

the benchmark scenario and does not change the conclusions, since it emits mainly biogenic CO₂ emissions that are considered climate neutral in EF3.1. The treatment of biowaste with industrial composting is advanced technology, and merely using waste material with no burden as raw material cannot gain environmental advantages. Even with circular solutions, energy and material efficiency has to be improved.

5.2.1.4 Water scarcity factors

Environmental impacts of water use depend strongly on the location and the water availability in that area. To test the impact of water scarcity factors, the global average factor used in the calculations was changed into the Murcia area water scarcity factor. This change reflects the use of water as input, e.g. as tap water, and to the water evaporating to air from the processes. The water impact from chemicals is not taken into account, since location for the production of chemicals is unknown, and thus they are still modeled with global water scarcity factors. The results for water use with Murcia factor can be seen in Figure 5.12.

Figure 5.12. Agrifood system results with market electricity and two water scarcity factors, global and Murcia area.

The change is visible only in the category of water use, where the impact is almost doubled.

5.2.2 Carbon handprint

As can be seen in the climate change part in Figure 5.5 , the climate impact (also called carbon footprint) of the A2C agrifood system is higher than the linear benchmark systems. Thus, carbon handprint, as explained in Chapter 3.2, is not generated.

5.3 Discussion

The A2C agrifood system had higher environmental impacts than benchmark products even when the A2C processes were modeled with renewable energy (wind power). The results of the agrifood system highlight the importance of energy and material efficiency in the processes. The production of process chemicals and electricity contribute to all impact categories remarkably. Especially the different chemicals used in demo 5, demo 8, and demo 6 generally have significant impacts across most categories. The other life cycle stages related to the use of water, waste treatment, use of fuels, and direct emissions have only minor impacts to the results.

When the results are studied at a demo-level, demo 5 has the single greatest impact to most impact categories. The biggest share of the normalized and weighted results is caused by demo 5 both with market electricity (34 %) and with wind electricity (27 %). This impact is mainly caused by the production stage of the chemicals, especially sodium chloride, and electricity used in the processes. Chemical recirculation could be increased for the fermentation process to gain significant impact deductions, because now the fermentation broth is calculated to be produced for each batch separately. Impacts caused by electricity consumption decrease when the source is changed from market electricity mix to renewable wind electricity. The impact caused by demo 5 has therefore great potential to decrease with recirculation of chemicals. The impact of demo 5 could be divided to demos 6 and 8, since the demo 5 does not currently have any own output products but it only processes the sugary fraction to be used in bioplastic production. If carotenoids production would have had data available for LCA calculations and were included, demo 5 would also have output products. The use of fuels for heating in PHBV extraction in demo 5 does not have significant impact to the overall results, and hence the use of heat return would not create a considerable difference.

Also, demos 2c, 8 and 6 have a notable impact on normalized and weighted results with market electricity. With wind electricity, the role of demos changes slightly, and the most impact after demo 5 comes from demos 6, 8 and 3. The impacts of demos 6 and 8 are mostly caused by the production of chemicals (especially antimony, butanediols, and adipic acid) used in the traditional fossil-based PBAT production, since only a limited amount of A2C

food waste can be used for plastic production to keep the functionality of the plastics high enough.

Demo 2c impacts mostly relate to electricity needed for yeast fermentation and solvent evaporation. The high electricity demand is explained by the data being laboratory scale, and there is great potential to be decreased with the scale up.

Demo 4 has minor impacts on the results, possibly caused by the smaller amount of agrifood treated, 100 kg of artichoke in demo 4 versus 2314 kg of lemon waste in demo 3. However, in the photochemical oxidant formation category, demo 4 has the most impact (49 %) which is caused mostly from the direct emissions from ethanol used in MAE. Currently 80 % of ethanol is circulating, but if all 100 % would be reused, the impact of the whole agrifood system to the photochemical oxidant formation could be halved.

The role of demo 3 relates mostly to the heating used for enzymatic extraction and the production of lemons as the origin of the waste material used. The role of lemon production is mostly visible in the impact categories water use, ecotoxicity: freshwater, terrestrial eutrophication and land use. Lemon waste could also be included burden free as discussed in the sensitivity analysis in chapter 5.2.1.2, since it is considered as waste, and this would decrease the total impact by 4% with market electricity and by 7% when wind electricity is used. However, this would not be enough to change the conclusion about the current superiority of benchmarks compared to the A2C system.

When results are normalized and weighted, the categories with highest impact are energy resources: non-renewable, climate change, and material resources: metals/minerals. In the categories of energy resources: non-renewable and climate change, the impacts are mainly from electricity use in demos 5 and from the fermentation in 2c when market electricity is used. With wind electricity, the impact to these categories is from demo 5 steam production for PHBV and sodium chloride for fermentation, and from demo 6 and 8 use of three PBAT chemicals. In impact category material resources: metals/minerals, with both market and wind electricity, the most impact is caused by the use of antimony for PBAT in demo 6 and 8, and sodium chloride used in demo 5 fermentation.

There are several possibilities to improve the environmental performance of the A2C agrifood system further. Impacts from chemicals' production could be reduced by optimization and circulation of the fermentation broth, improving the process yields, and minimizing the losses of chemicals. The fossil fuels used for heating purposes, e.g. natural gas, are visible in the results, and some renewable alternatives could be searched for to decrease the environmental impacts from the incineration of these fuels. Some heat compensation could be gained from the organic residues the PHBV processing produces, but these are excluded from the calculations, from being outside the scope of the model. The drying of extracts (fibre extract, phenolic extracts) could also be excluded in some cases, if the material would go directly without preservation demands to the next partner, to be used in final formulations.

6 Plastic waste system

6.1 System description

The plastic waste system on a higher level is illustrated in Section 4.1.3 and shown in blue boxes and text in Figure 4.2. In this chapter the plastic waste system is described in more detail. Figure 6.1 demonstrates the plastic waste system’s life cycle stages and related demos.

Figure 6.1. A2C plastic waste system and the principal material flows. The green boxes are part of the demo 1. The underlined and bolded items are the A2C demo outputs.

The first part of the plastic system is the demo 1 in which the plastic package waste enters the system at the pre-treatment stage. The plastic waste consists of the following plastic multilayers: LDPE/Al/PET, LDPE/metAl/PET, PE/metAl/PET/PE and LDPE multilayer (including PA). In the pre-treatment the plastic waste is shredded, washed, centrifuged and dried. The water treatment after the pre-treatment is excluded due to lack of data. Therefore, the small fraction which goes from demo 1 pre-treatment to demo 5 is also excluded from the LCA due to lack of data on how the water is used in demo 5.

After the pre-treatment, the plastic is optically sorted to separate the LDPE from the other plastic waste types. The LDPE is directed to demo 7 and other multilayers continue to delamination and sorting where the multilayers are separated from each other. The PET and PE layers continue to pre-treatment of enzymatic attack. Then, in the PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET, the PET is transformed to MHET and the PE passes through the system and is finally directed to demo 9. Then, the MHET is converted to EG and TPA which are inputs for demo 2 a and b biotechnology processing life cycle stages. In the demo 2a, the EG is converted to GA with processing steps biomass and GA production and deepwell plate centrifugation. In the demo 2b, the TPA is transformed to PCA with the process step fermentation, deepwell plate centrifugation, extraction, solvent evaporation and lyophilization. More detailed inputs and outputs of the demo 1 and demo 2ab are available in Table 6-1, Table 6-2 and Table 6-3.

In demo 7, non-biodegradable pellets are manufactured from the LDPE from demo 1 optical sorting and recycled filter chunk.

In demo 9, the agriculture film waste is pre-treated and non-biodegradable pellets are manufactured using also PE from demo 1 and recycled aluminum. These processes include shredding, washing, centrifuge, fan spindling and shaking. The decontamination process which would take in the end is not included in the LCA due to lack of data.

6.1.1 Demo 1

6.1.1.1 Assumptions

Pre-treatment (GWC)

- The gas oil is modelled as unleaded petrol which has a heat value of 43,2 GJ/t.

- This process has no material loss.
- The organic residue output of the demo (6kg) is considered burden-free because it can be recycled to the demo 5.

Delamination and sorting

- The input chemical mix and water are make-up values which need to be added per each batch based on expert opinion.
- For the separation fluid used in the process, a generic inorganic chemical was used as a proxy. Saperatec has its own chemical mix, but due to confidentiality reasons it could not be modelled, and proxy is used instead. The selected proxy isecoinvent 3.10 dataset “market for chemical, inorganic, GLO”.
- The output PE flakes can be recycled. Thus, the same amount, 115 kg, is added to the benchmark model as part of the benchmark system.
- The output aluminum is part of the filter waste.

Pre-treatment to enhance enzymatic attack (CETEC)

- Input water is reused; thus, it does not have emissions.
- The input ice is disposed of. The melted water is directed to wastewater treatment. However, this water can also be reused.
- No PE or PET loss takes place in the process.
- PE exits the system at this stage, although in the demo 1 the PE removal takes place in the enzymatic degradation process. This is due to applying data which was updated after the modeling took place.

PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET

- PET with high crystallinity is treated as waste although it could be re-used in other products or recirculated in the pre-treatment to enhance enzymatic attack.
- The outputs which are not directed to demos 2 a and b are treated as hazardous waste.

6.1.1.2 Life cycle inventory

The LCA data used to model the demo 1 is shown in Table 6-1. The data shown in this table is aggregated from all the demo 1 life cycle stages.

Table 6-1. Demo 1 aggregated life cycle inventory. The table includes all the life cycle stages of demo 1.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
plastic package waste	1200		kg	-
electricity	7053,69		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
heat	95,04		MJ	market for petrol, unleaded, burned in machinery, GLO
chemicals	62,84		kg	market for chemical, inorganic, GLO - market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state, RER - market for enzymes, GLO - market for sodium phosphate, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , RER - market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state, RER - market for potassium hydroxide, GLO
water	6081		l	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland
material to demos 2 a and b		59,66	kg	-
material to demos 7 and 9		976	kg	-
recyclable material		95,13	kg	-
wastewater		5833	l	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment, Europe without Switzerland
lost water		248	l	-
waste to be treated		69,21	kg	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration, GLO - treatment of waste polyethylene terephthalate, municipal incineration, GLO - treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, Europe without Switzerland

6.1.2 Demo 2a EG to GA and 2b TPA to PCA

6.1.2.1 Assumptions

Demo 2a) EG to GA

Biomass and GA production

- Tryptone is modelled as soybean meal.
- No emissions are assigned to the cooling water because it can be recirculated.

DWP centrifugation

- The vacuum pump electricity consumption is considered negligible and so are emission caused by it.
- The biomass is assumed to be water and is treated as wastewater. However, it has potential to be used in other industries. However, in this LCA it is directed to wastewater treatment due to the laboratory scale of this study.
- The output GA is in an aqueous solution. In the LCA it is assumed to be separated from the water without any additional emissions.

Demo 2b) TPA to PCA

Fermentation

- Sodium phosphate is used as a proxy for monosodium phosphate.
- Zinc sulfide is used as a proxy for zinc sulfate.
- Generic inorganic chemicals are used in the LCA due to lack of chemical specific data for the following chemicals: dipotassium phosphate, magnesium dichloride, kanamycin, sodium molybdate, cobalt chloride, manganese chloride.
- The input water amount is an estimation calculated based on the mass balance due to uncertainties in measuring the water consumption.
- The input cooling water can be recirculated. Thus, it is considered not to have emissions.
- The electricity consumption for compressing air is not included because it could not be estimated.

DWP centrifugation

- Electricity consumption is negligible due to the device properties and use time.

Extraction

- The input octanol can be re-used and the value used in this LCA is the make-up amount which is needed to be added. The value is based on expert opinion.
- The input octanol is modelled as a generic solvent due to lack of octanol-specific data in the ecoinvent database.

Lyophilization

- The input ammonium hydroxide is modelled as ammonia due to lack of ammonium hydroxide data in the ecoinvent database.
- The output PCA is mixed with ammonium chloride in a powder. The PCA is the demo 2 b output. However, in this LCA no emissions are assigned to the separation process and the PCA is treated as a main output and all emissions are allocated to it.
- The output emissions to air are estimations compiled by the data provider.

6.1.2.2 Life cycle inventory

The used LCA data for the demo 2a is shown in Table 6-2. The table combines the processes of biomass and GA production and deepwell plate centrifugation.

Table 6-2. Life cycle inventory of demo 2a. The data is aggregated from all the processing steps.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
EG from demo 1	16,22		kg	-
electricity	5799,08		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
chemicals	95,39129		kg	market for glucose, GLO - market for fodder yeast, GLO - market for soybean meal, RoW - market for propylene glycol, liquid, RoW - market for potassium hydroxide, GLO - market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state, RER.
water	871,9		l	market for water, deionised, Europe without Switzerland
glycolic acid in the final solution		15,69	kg	-
water in the final solution		856,2	kg	-
biomass		54,49	l	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater, Europe without Switzerland
carbon dioxide, fossil to air		27,25	kg	-
water vapour to air		363,1	l	-

Table 6-3 shows the LCA data for the demo 2 b.

Table 6-3. LCI data of the demo 2b. The data is aggregated from all the demo 2b processing steps.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
TPA from demo 1	43,44		kg	
electricity	4,36E+05		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
chemicals	6,05E+02		kg	See Annex A
water in the chemical solutions	82,8		kg	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland

water	4679		kg	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland
PCA		22,94		-
carbon dioxide, fossil to air		260,90	kg	-
treated waste		1317	kg	treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration, Europe without Switzerland
treated water		3776	l	treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment, Europe without Switzerland
octanol to air		54,97	kg	-
ammonium to air		70,53	kg	-
ammonium chloride		168,10	kg	-

6.1.3 Demo 7

6.1.3.1 Assumptions

- The compatibilizer is selected to be maleic anhydride based on the information from the data provider.
- The output filter chunk is recycled. Thus, no emissions are assigned to it.

6.1.3.2 Life cycle inventory

The used inventory data used in the LCA model of demo 7 is shown in Table 6-4.

Table 6-4. Life cycle inventory of demo 7.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
LDPE from demo 1	836		kg	-
compatibilizer	16,7		kg	market for maleic anhydride, GLO
electricity, non-solar	573,3		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
solar electricity	36,93		kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted, ES
plastic pellet		802,9	kg	
filter chunk		49,78	kg	

6.1.4 Demo 9

6.1.4.1 Assumptions

- The input water treatment chemicals are modelled as polyacrylamide.
- The emissions of manufacturing the input recycled aluminium are excluded due to its small weight.

- The output filter chunk, soil and plastic sawdust can be recycled. Thus, no emissions are assigned to them.

6.1.4.2 Life cycle inventory

The used LCA data for the demo 9 is shown in Table 6-5.

Table 6-5. Life cycle inventory of demo 9.

Data	Input amount	Output amount	Unit	ecoinvent v3.10 process and geography
agriculture film waste	1735		kg	-
PE from demo 1	140			-
Aluminium	10		kg	-
electricity, non-solar	1091		kWh	market for electricity, high voltage, ES
electricity, solar	101		kWh	electricity production, photovoltaic, 3kWp slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted, ES
heat from gas oil	83,28		MJ	heat production, light fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW, Europe without Switzerland
Water	362,5		kg	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland
calcium carbonate	30		kg	market for calcium carbonate, precipitated, RER
calcium oxide	6,7		kg	market for quicklime, milled, packed, RER
water treatment chemicals	0,536		kg	market for polyacrylamide, GLO
produced agriculture film pellet		1000	kg	-
filter chunk		3,59	kg	-
plastic sawdust		240	kg	-
Soil		671	kg	-

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Whole system

The results for the whole A2C plastic waste system by life cycle stage are shown in Figure 6.2.

Figure 6.2. Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages (processing steps) to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.

The results in the Figure 6.2 are dominated by the life cycle stage demo 2b TPA to PCA which comprise 93-98 % of the total environmental impact in all the impact categories. This is due to the high electricity consumption in the lyophilisation stage, which is the main contributor to all impact categories, except terrestrial eutrophication in which the direct ammonium emissions contribute the most (51 % of all the lyophilisation emissions). If the impact of the demo 2 b is deduced from the results, the demo 2 a covers 30-74 % of the total impact in different impact categories.

Figure 6.3 demonstrates the environmental impact of the plastic waste system (all demos included) compared to the linear benchmark system. Figure 6.3 shows the relationship

between the environmental impacts of the A2C plastic waste system and those of the corresponding linear system. In Figure 6.3, the value of the A2C plastic waste system's environmental impact is divided by the value of the linear system.

Figure 6.3. Comparison of the A2C plastic system with all demos to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the A2C plastic waste system is divided with the value of the linear system. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.

From Figure 6.3 it can be observed that the A2C environmental impact is 7-190 times bigger than the impact of the linear system in all the impact categories. This is due to the A2C life cycle stage production of TPA to PCA. As discussed below in Figure 6.2, the high electricity consumption is the main reason for the significant difference in the environmental impact of the A2C and benchmark system. Namely, only the electricity consumption of the lyophilisation stage is 169 times bigger than the whole electricity consumption of the benchmark production together.

Figure 6.4 presents the single-score environmental footprint of the A2C plastic waste system and linear benchmark system using normalised and weighted results. Figure 6.4 demonstrates that when all the demos are included in the plastic waste system LCA, the

environmental impact of the A2C system is 23 times bigger than the linear system’s impact. Also, from Figure 6.4 it can be noted that the most relevant impact categories of the A2C plastic waste system are climate change and non-renewable energy resources. Based on the results shown earlier in Figure 6.2, the TPA to PCA production life cycle stage dominates these impact categories contributing to 96 % and 97 % of the related impacts, respectively. This is due to the high electricity consumption of the lyophilisation process.

Figure 6.4. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system and of the linear benchmark system.

6.2.2 Without demo 2 a and b

This section demonstrates the plastic waste system results without the impact of the laboratory-scale life cycle stages demo 2a and 2 which dominated the results in Figure . These two life cycle stages are excluded from the results in this subsection to be able to evaluate better in detail the overall impact of the A2C plastic chain as a system taking into account also the other life cycle stages.

However, it should be noted that all the demo 1 processes prior to these two life cycle stages are included in the results of this subchapter. Hence, the life cycle stages of PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET and MHET conversion are included in the results although they are specifically producing materials for the demos 2 a and b. These two life cycle stages are included in the results to ensure that in the future a more comprehensive assessment of the entire plastic system's environmental sustainability is possible by collecting as much information as possible at this pilot stage of system development.

First, Figure 6.5 shows the share of different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages of the total environmental impact (based on characterized results). From Figure 6.5 it can be observed that the impact of the different A2C life cycle stages is more distributed than in the earlier shown Figure 6.2. In this case, the life cycle stages pre-treatment at GWC, PET enzymatic degradation to MHET and delamination and sorting dominate the results in various impact categories.

Figure 6.5. Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages (processing steps) without the demos 2 a and b to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.

Figure 6.6 shows the contribution of each process type to the total environmental impact in each impact category. From Figure 6.6 it can be concluded that electricity consumption is the main process type contributor in all impact categories, except metal and material resources. In this impact category, the production of chemicals used in the A2C is the main contributor.

Figure 6.6. Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system process types without the demos 2 a and b with market electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.

Figure 6.7 below shows the result when the characterised A2C results without the demo 2a and b are compared to the linear system.

Figure 6.7. Comparison of the A2C plastic system without the demos 2 a and b to the linear benchmark system using characterised results. The value of the A2C plastic waste system is divided by the value of the linear system. The value of the linear system is manually set to be 1.

From Figure 6.7 it can be observed that the A2C system without the demo 2 a and b is more environmentally sustainable in all impact categories except for ionising radiation. In this impact category, the higher electricity consumption and other background data of the A2C plastic waste system explains the difference to benchmark. The reason why the difference between the A2C system and the linear system is more significant in the ionising radiation than in the non-material resources category, which is also impacted widely by electricity consumption, is the share of radon used in nuclear energy in the Spanish market electricity dataset. In the linear benchmark system, the production of ethylene is the main contributor in all the impact categories except for ionising radiation and water use ranging from 80-92 % of the total impact categories' result excluding ionising radiation and water use.

The Figure 6.8 shows the single score results of the A2C plastic system without the demo 2 a and b and of the linear system.

Figure 6.8. Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2 a and b and of the linear benchmark system.

From Figure 6.8 it can be noted that the environmental impact of the A2C plastic waste system is 49 % smaller than the linear system's, and that the most relevant impact categories are climate change and non-renewable energy resources. These two impact categories can be analysed by observing Figure 6.5. In the climate change impact category, the life cycle stages pre-treatment at GWC and PET enzymatic degradation to MHET contribute the most to this life cycle covering 27 % and 24 %, respectively, of the total carbon footprint of the A2C plastic waste system excluding the demo 2a and b. From Figure 6.6 it can be noted that in both these life cycle stages the high electricity consumption is the main contributor to the carbon footprints of the two life cycle stages. Similarly based on Figure 6.5 in the impact category non-renewable energy resources, the life cycle stages pre-treatment at GWC and PET enzymatic degradation to MHET contribute the most to the impact category result contributing 31 % and 21% to the total impact, respectively. Also in this

impact category, in both these life cycle stages the high electricity consumption is the main contributor to the total impact as seen in Figure 6.6.

6.2.3 Sensitivity analysis

6.2.3.1 Renewable electricity without demo 2a and b

As shown earlier in Figure 6.6, the emission derived from electricity consumption impacts the results significantly. Therefore, it is worth evaluating the A2C plastic waste system when the electricity is generated from wind to present a possible future scenario for the system.

Figure 6.9 shows the contribution of plastic system life cycle stages' impact category results. From this Figure it can be noted that PET enzymatic degradation to MHET and delamination and sorting show the highest contribution in various impact categories.

Figure 6.9. Sensitivity analysis: Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system life cycle stages without the demos 2 a and b with wind electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.

Figure 6.10 shows the contribution of each process type in the studied impact categories when wind electricity is applied. From this figure, it can be noted that electricity and chemical consumption contribute the most. The relative impact of the chemicals increases compared to Figure 6.6 where market electricity was applied.

Figure 6.10. Sensitivity analysis: Contribution analysis by different A2C plastic waste system process types without the demos 2 and b with wind electricity to the different environmental impact in EF impact categories.

Figure 6.11 compares the results for the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2 and by using Spanish market electricity to using renewable Spanish wind electricity.

Figure 6.11. Sensitivity analysis: Comparison of A2C plastic system with renewable electricity to the system with market electricity. The value of the A2C plastic waste system with wind electricity is divided with the value of the same system with market electricity. The value of the system with market electricity is manually set to be 1.

From Figure 6.11 it can be noted that in all but two impact categories the system's environmental impact is smaller using renewable energy than market electricity. Namely, in carcinogenic human toxicity and metal/mineral resources the impact of the system with renewable electricity is slightly higher. As seen in Figure 6.9, in carcinogenic human toxicity, the upstream wind electricity emissions are responsible for 79 % of the impact generated in this category. Specifically, anthracene used for example in the ecoinvent dataset of the Spanish wind energy contributes the most in this impact category covering 77 % of the total emissions of the carcinogenic human toxicity category. In metal/mineral resources, based on Figure 6.9, the production of the chemical comprises 52 % of the total impact in this category and electricity upstream emissions 45 %. In chemicals, the manufacturing of sodium phosphate modelled to be used in production steps PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET and MHET conversion comprise 57 % of the chemicals' impact and the generic inorganic chemical used as proxy for the chemical mix in the delamination and sorting cover

32 % of the chemical emissions. In the upstream electricity emissions, the tellurium used in theecoinvent wind energy contains 47 % of the upstream electricity’s impact in this category.

Figure 6.12 demonstrates the single score environmental footprint results for the A2C plastic waste system without the demo 2 a and b and when using market and wind electricity. From Figure 6.12 it can be noted that the environmental impact of the studied system can be reduced by 73 % if wind electricity is applied. This is due to the decreased environmental impacts in the impact categories of non-renewable energy resources and climate change as fossil sources are switched to cleaner electricity production technologies.

Figure 6.12. Sensitivity analysis: Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2a and b with market and wind electricity.

Figure 6.12 also shows that if the plastic waste system uses renewable electricity, the impact category climate change contributes the most to the environmental footprint followed by metal/mineral material resources. As seen in Figure 6.9, in impact categories climate change

and metal/mineral resources the life cycle stages PET enzymatic degradation to MHET and delamination and sorting impact most in this category.

Regarding climate change, the PET enzymatic degradation to MHET life cycle stage contributes the most to this impact category, accounting for 35% of the total climate change impact. Within this stage, the treatment of hazardous waste has the highest contribution, amounting to 32% of the impact. The second highest contribution to climate change comes from the delamination and sorting life cycle stage, which covers 28% of the total climate change impact. In this life cycle stage, manufacturing of the chemical mix, modelled using a proxy, contributes 47% of the total climate change impact of this life cycle stage.

In metal/mineral material resources, the modelled sodium phosphate used in the PET enzymatic degradation to MHET life cycle stage, covers 57 % of the impact in this life cycle stage. For the delamination and sorting life cycle stage, the used proxy for the chemical mix is in charge of 85 % of the life cycle stage's emissions in this impact category.

6.2.3.2 Water scarcity factors

As detailed in section 4.2.2, a sensitivity analysis was conducted applying the watershed factor for Murcia water use. This analysis specifically focused on the A2C plastic waste system with market electricity, excluding demos 2a and 2b, to identify potential changes with greater precision.

Figure 6.13 shows the results for the A2C plastic waste system without the demos 2a and 2b when Murcia watershed and global water use factors are used.

Figure 6.13. Sensitivity analysis: Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2a and b with Murcia watershed and global water use impact factors.

The differences between the water use factors will only affect the water use impact category. However, when observing the water use in the Figure 6.13, it can be noted that applying the Murcia watershed factor has negligible impact to the results. Specifically, it increases the environmental impact of the A2C plastic waste system by 0,9 %. The minor impact is explained by the low contribution of water process type to the total results shown in Figure 6.6.

6.2.3.3 Waste treatment function

The sensitivity analysis for the waste treatment function was conducted for the entire plastic waste system with market electricity. This approach was chosen to assess the environmental performance differences between the plastic waste system and the linear benchmark system when the waste treatment function is included in the benchmark model.

Figure 6.14 shows the results for the plastic waste system waste treatment function sensitivity analysis.

Figure 6.14. Sensitivity analysis: Normalised and weighted single score environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic waste system with market electricity and benchmark system added with incineration and landfill waste treatment function.

From Figure 6.14 it can be noted that although the benchmark model includes the waste treatment burden, the A2C plastic waste system’s environmental impact is still significantly

higher than the linear benchmark system's environmental impact. Specifically, 16 times greater than the environmental impact of the benchmark system added with incineration and 22 times greater than added with landfill.

6.2.4 Only demo 2a and 2b – carbon footprint

In this section the carbon footprint of manufacturing glycolic acid and protocatechuic acid is presented in Figure 6.15 and Figure 6.16 together with their linear benchmarks. The aim is to demonstrate with the benchmarks the required level of carbon footprint which the A2C demo 2a and 2b should be reaching when being scaled up from laboratory-scale in the future.

Figure 6.15. Carbon footprint of the A2C laboratory-scale glycolic acid and linear benchmark product lactic acid. The results are modelled using Spanish market electricity.

Figure 6.16. Carbon footprint of the A2C laboratory-scale PCA and linear benchmark product benzoic acid. The results are modelled using Spanish market electricity.

In these figures no burden is given to the input material, ethylene glycol in case of the glycolic acid and TPA for the PCA, because the plastic waste system is studied as one unit. Assigning burden to the ethylene glycol and TPA is not possible without performing allocation procedures. As the plastic system is studied as a system, allocation is not conducted. However, the LCA results shown in the Figure 6.2 show that the impact of the life cycle stages of demo 1, which feed material to demos 2a, 2b, 7 and 9, comprise only 1,8 % of the total carbon footprint of the A2C plastic waste system (including demos 2a and 2b). If this burden is divided between demos 2a and 2b, 7 and 9, the share of the input materials for demos 2a and 2b are negligible compared to the carbon footprints of the demos 2a and 2b.

Also, if burden were allocated for the ethylene glycol and TPA, the carbon footprint of the A2C glycolic acid and PCA would increase.

Other impact categories than climate change (carbon footprint) are not included in the environmental sustainability assessment of the glycolic acid and PCA due to the early-stage laboratory-scale experiments. Typically, the carbon footprint results can indicate the results of the other impact categories with few exceptions.

From Figure 6.15 and Figure 6.16 it can be noticed that the carbon footprint of the A2C laboratory-scale glycolic acid and PCA is significantly higher than the linear benchmarks' carbon footprint. This is mainly explained by the inefficient electricity consumption of laboratory-scale devices. In the glycolic acid, electricity consumption comprises 80 % and chemicals 17 % of the total carbon footprint. In PCA, electricity consumption is responsible for 94 % of the total carbon footprint, while chemicals account for 2 %.

6.2.5 Carbon handprint

Currently, the carbon handprint is not generated when the whole plastic waste system is considered. Also, LCA studies of the final products where the A2C demo outputs are applied are required to determine if the plastic waste system creates a carbon handprint. And these studies need to take into account the substitution ratio of the A2C demo output compared to the linear benchmark product. However, with a cradle-to-gate system boundary, the plastic waste system creates a carbon handprint if only the pilot and industrial level demos are included.

The carbon handprint is calculated for the plastic waste system without the demos 2 a and b using Spanish market electricity. This setup was selected to represent the A2C solution taking into account the most upscaled processes. It should be noted that it is currently uncertain whether a carbon handprint will be generated in future LCA studies when demos 2a and 2b are included in the results. Also, considering the substitution ratios of A2C demo outputs compared to the linear products in final products will determine if a carbon handprint is generated.

The results are presented in Figure 6.17.

Figure 6.17. Carbon handprint of the A2C plastic waste system without demos 2 a and b and using Spanish market electricity. In this calculation the substitution ratio of the A2C demo output compared to the linear benchmark is not taken into account. This aspect should be considered in a wider LCA calculation where the final product where the A2C demo output is applied is studied.

From Figure 6.17 it can be noted that the A2C plastic waste system without the demos 2 a and b generates a carbon handprint of 2191 kgCO₂eq if it is applied instead of a linear system. The carbon handprint is generated because in the A2C plastic waste system virgin plastic is not required. On the contrary, in the benchmark system, 87 % of the carbon footprint is derived from the ethylene raw material. Electricity consumption covers 8 % of the total carbon footprint of the baseline system.

6.3 Discussion

Overall, the environmental impact of the plastic system is a preliminary estimation due to the different level of A2C data (laboratory, pilot and industrial) used in this LCA. The impact can be estimated with less uncertainties when more industrial scale data will be available for the whole plastic waste system. Especially, comparing the environmental impact of the plastic waste system to the linear conventional benchmark system is more robust when also the A2C system is modelled with more scaled-up data.

The plastic waste system is evidently less environmentally sustainable than the linear system when all the demos are included in the results. This highlights the need to use consistent upscaled data across all A2C processes. For a fair comparison with the linear system, the A2C system should also be modelled using industrial-scale data, similarly as the benchmark system.

If the demos 2 a and b are subtracted from the results, the A2C plastic waste system's environmental impact is estimated to be 49 % lower than the linear system's as shown in the Figure 6.4 when Spanish market electricity is applied. This is an indicative estimation because there are factors which need to be considered when interpreting this result.

A factor that decreases the environmental sustainability of the A2C plastic system in this LCA is the inclusion of the life cycle stages PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET and MHET conversion in the results, even though they provide materials only for demos 2a and 2b, which are excluded. The PET/PE enzymatic degradation to MHET life cycle stage is responsible for 21-43 % of the total environmental impact in different categories when demos 2a and 2b are excluded. The life cycle stage MHET conversion accounts for 0,56-0,89 % of the total environmental impact in different categories when demos 2a and 2b are excluded. However, in the benchmark model, all the processes related to manufacturing the linear benchmarks of demos 2a and 2b are excluded. This indicates that the two studied systems, the A2C plastic waste system and the benchmark system, are not equivalent. For a fair comparison, the benchmark model should include the manufacturing of the main raw materials for the demo 2a and 2b benchmark products in the results. In the benchmark model, the main raw material chemical for lactic acid is acetaldehyde. The contribution of acetaldehyde manufacturing to the total environmental impact of the benchmark system, excluding all other demo 2a and 2b related processes, ranges from 0.18% to 0.91% across different impact categories. Similarly, for toluene, which is the main raw material chemical for benzoic acid, the contribution ranges from 0.18% to 1.05%. To summarise, although the benchmark system's corresponding chemicals for demo 2a and 2b ethylene glycol and PCA are not included in the benchmark model, it has a minor impact on the interpretation of the plastic waste system results.

Also, the environmental footprint results would increase if an environmental burden were allocated to the used recycled plastics as recommended by the PEF method (European Commission, 2021). In the benchmark model, the raw material, ethylene, is the main contributor to the environmental impact of the linear system. If the burden were given the input plastic package or agricultural film waste, the difference in the environmental sustainability of the two systems would decrease as the A2C would receive the burden and it would decrease in the benchmark system.

On the other hand, the environmental footprint results of the A2C plastic system could possibly decrease if the A2C processes currently on pilot or demonstrator scale were modelled using industrial scale data. This scenario however requires that the energy and materials consumptions are more improved at the industrial level compared to pilot or demonstrator data.

In the scope of this LCA, the substitution ratio of the A2C demo output compared to the linear benchmark is not taken into account. However, based on the data collected in this project, currently the plastic pellet made from recycled plastic can only substitute 25-33 % of the virgin plastic pellet. The share depends for example on the type of final product, its application and properties. If the A2C plastic system's outputs in a final product would require to be used more in terms of mass than the linear benchmark to achieve the same functionality, the environmental footprint of the A2C plastic waste system would increase compared to linear benchmark.

As explained in chapter 3, the robustness level of different EF impact categories varies. This also affects the uncertainty of the results of the plastic waste system LCA. Highlighting specific hotspots from the less robust impact categories, such as non-renewable energy resources, carcinogenic human toxicity and metal/mineral resources should be interpreted with caution.

Another topic which causes uncertainty of the results is using proxies for chemicals used in the A2C demonstrator. Namely, in the case of the impact category metal/mineral resources the use of a generic inorganic chemical as a proxy for a specific chemical mix used at life cycle stage delamination and sorting causes uncertainty. Saperatec provided LCA results

of the specific chemical mix from a previous LCA study, but it was not possible to use the results in this LCA because a different impact assessment method was used in the previous LCA study.

To enhance the quality of the study, it is crucial to obtain industrial-scale data for a more accurate assessment of the environmental impact of the A2C plastic waste system compared to linear systems. Ensuring consistency in upscaled data across all A2C processes would provide a fairer comparison. Allocation of environmental burdens to recycled input materials should be considered, alongside the efficiency in electricity and chemical usage. Additionally, substituting the A2C plastic system outputs for linear benchmarks must reflect the real substitution ratios. Addressing these aspects would significantly improve the robustness and reliability of the study's results, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the environmental sustainability of the A2C plastic waste system.

7 LCA conclusions

This LCA study aims to evaluate the environmental impact of the A2C agrifood, plastic package waste and agriculture film upcycling system through a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) study. The LCA has two primary goals: identifying the most relevant process improvements for future technology development through hotspot analysis, and to benchmark the environmental performance of the A2C circular solution to a functionally equivalent linear solution. The purpose of combining benchmarking and hotspot analysis is to identify what are the aspects of the novel A2C system which need to be possibly improved to reach the level of sustainability as the more developed benchmark products, and give guidance on how to decrease the environmental impact of the whole value chain. The LCA contributes to the A2C project objectives by providing a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental impacts which can be applied in the operations of the technological partners and in building the A2C multidimensional model that enables the solution's territorial deployment, replication, and scalability for a wider audience.

The study has limitations that caused uncertainty in the results. The level of the used LCA data varies between the A2C solution and the benchmarks, which results in direct comparisons against industrial-scale production being unfair. Hence, the benchmark system serves for future sustainability goal setting purposes rather than for comparing the current level of environmental sustainability. The A2C solution is currently at a lower Technology Readiness Level (TRL), as laboratory or pilot, compared to the benchmarks. Additionally, primary data was not available for all processes and some processes were excluded from the LCA due to the lack of data.

The main contributors to the results in the agrifood and plastic waste system are largely impacted by their inefficiencies in electricity and chemical consumption. These inefficiencies are due to the less developed technology of the A2C solution compared to the industrially optimized processes found in the linear benchmark system. For the agrifood system, the environmental impact was found to be three times higher than the linear benchmark system. This difference is primarily due to the less developed nature of the A2C solution compared to the industrially optimized benchmark processes. Even if the A2C results were higher than of the compared benchmarks, they are in quite the same scale, and with improvements the

same level can be reached. The processes with room for improvement are for example recirculation of water and chemicals. For example, recirculation of saltwater brine in demo 5 is tested to be possible, and in further studies with better data, reuse of sodium chloride could be included in the calculations to change the results in many impact categories. Better reuse of ethanol in demo 4 could have potential to halve the impact of photochemical oxidant formation, if 100 % of ethanol would be reused instead of 80 %. Also, if demo 2c data would be scaled up instead of laboratory scale, impacts could be decreased significantly. The traditional PBAT production in demos 6 and 8 has remarkable impact to the overall results, for chemical use and with electricity, and if the share of fossils in the manufacturing of bioplastic could be decreased, impacts of the whole A2C agrifood system would be reduced. For the plastic waste system, the environmental impact was 23 times higher than the linear benchmark system. However, when excluding the life cycle stages modelled using laboratory-scale data, the environmental impact was 49% smaller than the linear benchmark system.

The results of this LCA contribute partially to the A2C project objective of decoupling of economic and human activities from the consumption of finite resources and greenhouse gas emissions. Particularly, avoiding the use of primary raw materials is evident in the results of the plastic pellets, reducing the pellets' environmental impact compared to manufacturing them from virgin materials. However, upcycling the agrifood and plastic waste instead of treating them as waste does not create a reduction in environmental impact with the applied data in this LCA. To reach the same level of sustainability as the linear benchmarks, the A2C solution needs to improve its electricity and chemical consumption. Despite the higher environmental impact presented in this LCA, the A2C solution shows significant potential to improve its environmental performance. Various promising side-streams generated by the A2C systems can be used in other applications which supports avoiding the production of virgin materials. Additionally, A2C solution promotes collaboration among circular economy actors, resulting in more efficient use of materials.

Overall, when evaluating the sustainability of circular economy solutions, it is not sufficient to only use waste as input material. Simultaneously, the production must be energy and material efficient. When conducting a complex LCA with various technology partners, cooperation among partners is essential. Understanding the overall concept and material

flows before data collection starts is vital which also requires strong collaboration. Low TRL level solution LCA, such as A2C solution, should also aim to use more industrial-level data in the LCA through for example TEA (techno-economic analysis). Also, communicating LCA results is complex for a wide-reaching system like A2C. Therefore, it is not always possible to offer straightforward and concise statements regarding the sustainability of a circular economy system.

To further assess the sustainability of the A2C system, future LCA studies should prioritize several important areas. Firstly, it is essential to examine the recirculation and valorisation of by-products, as these processes have the potential to reduce waste, improve material efficiency and substitute virgin materials. Secondly, estimating and applying industrial-scale data in the LCA of the A2C solution will offer valuable insights into its true impact by taking into account improvements in energy and material efficiencies. Thirdly, studying the final products that use the A2C demo outputs will help to evaluate sustainability more comprehensively. This includes understanding the substitution ratio, which measures how much of the circular product can replace the linear one and identifying any changes in the final product composition or production process that may arise from using A2C demo outputs.

8 Circularity monitoring

In this section, the framework for circularity monitoring is introduced, followed by description of the framework application process and suggested monitoring indicators. The systems examined in the circularity monitoring are consistent with the systems described in earlier sections 4, 5, and 6 with a few exceptions that will be explained in this section.

8.1 Framework

8.1.1 Objective

The objective of this study was to establish a monitoring framework for evaluating circular economy (CE) practices. This research concentrated on identifying the elements that should be considered in the monitoring of CE, rather than the methodological approaches for measuring CE. This distinction is essential, as CE monitoring aims to offer a comprehensive overview of the progress and impact achieved through CE practices. Methods, methodologies, frameworks, and tools serve as means for monitoring and assessment.

8.1.2 Methodology

First, a literature review was conducted with the search of relevant literature consisting of the following word combination (“circular econom*” AND monitor* AND framework AND (measur* OR assessment* OR indicator* OR metric*), where the goal of research was on identification of metrics for monitoring and assessing circular economy. The search yielded 180 journal papers. The search was limited to Article; Review Article; Early Access; Book in the Web of Science. The grey literature was left outside the scope of this study. The search focused primarily on identifying quantifiable metrics, including indicators and assessment methods/methodologies.

The first step entailed going through article titles and abstracts and identifying relevant papers. Scale of 1-3 was used for scoring the papers. Those marked with 3 were selected for further analysis based on the abstract. Those marked with 2 required a review of the full paper to ensure its relevance. Those marked 1 were excluded from the analysis. The selected studies were then reviewed. From the 180 papers, 136 were selected for further analysis.

This literature review yielded the identification of 437 metrics. From these groups of metrics, 26 were categorised into assessment methods such as life cycle assessment (LCA), material flow analysis (MFA), etc. From the remaining metrics, 85 were categorized as indicators that were suitable for the monitoring of agriculture and food systems. This list of indicators was used as the primary list of metrics in the application of the developed CE monitoring framework in Step 3 for the case study analysis. A CE indicator is a variable or function of variables that offers insights into circularity, such as technological cycles, or its impacts through cause-and-effect modeling. Furthermore, an indicator can be derived from a combination of quantitative and qualitative data (Alivojvodic 2024).

The assessment methodologies/methods were collected into a table consisting of information about the method/ology, such as the description of the metric, the research question or the question of interest the metric can answer, the scope that the metric is fit to apply, if the metric is a method or methodology, and information on whether the metric provides direct or indirect quantification. For a closer look at the direct and indirect quantifications of CE assessment metrics, see Elia et al. 2017. As a contribution to the existing literature listing metrics for measuring the CE, and to bring clarity to existing metrics, metric types were differentiated between method and methodology, which are based on the definitions obtained from Fassio and Chirilli (2023). They describe method as a collection of tools, models, and indicators (both quantitative and qualitative) that facilitate the calculation of values associated with a particular category of impact. Methodology is defined as a set of individual characterization methods that collectively address various environmental, ecological, and social issues, considering the associated effects and impacts through a systemic thinking approach (Fassio and Chirilli 2023).

The 95 identified agriculture and food sector-related indicators were divided into two types, intrinsic and impact, based on definitions adapted from Luthin et al. 2023 and Gursel et al. 2022. Intrinsic indicators measure the inherent circularity or success of implementing circular economic principles. Impact indicators measure the consequences of circularity on various sustainability dimensions, including environmental protection, economic viability, and social equity, as well as the accumulation of hazardous substances. The CE monitoring framework developed is described in the following section.

8.1.3 CE Monitoring Framework

The framework incorporates impact as a fundamental component of monitoring by providing guidance on selecting an appropriate impact assessment method, thereby establishing a foundation for its application. The process begins with the identification and description of the monitored circular economy (CE) practice, followed by the selection of the assessment method. Subsequently, based on the chosen assessment method, the necessary metrics for monitoring are identified.

A significant contribution of the developed framework to existing models is its approach, which emphasizes a clear distinction between intrinsic and impact metrics in monitoring. The framework elucidates, through its outlined steps, how the selection of intrinsic and impact metrics can be integrated into the monitoring of CE practices. This distinction underscores the complexity of measuring circularity, as some metrics directly quantify the degree of circularity, while others evaluate the broader impacts and contributions of circular strategies towards a more sustainable system (Luthin et al. 2023, Gursel et al. 2022, Corona et al. 2019).

The approach presented in this deliverable involved a literature review and the application of existing metrics, culminating in the proposal of a novel step-by-step framework for CE monitoring. This framework is applicable across various industries and for any product or service. In this project, the focus was concentrated on monitoring the environmental pillar of CE activities. However, the rationale underlying the framework's steps allows for its application to other pillars by utilizing metrics pertinent to each pillar, thereby laying the groundwork for expanding the framework to encompass social, governance, and economic pillars.

The CE Monitoring Framework consist of three steps described below.

Step 1. Defining the CE practice to be monitored.

Step 1 involves defining the practice to be monitored. This step requires a comprehensive description of the Circular Economy (CE) practice or activity as delineated by the responsible entity, such as a company, organization, or municipality, overseeing the practice. The list of CE practices, comprising 36 practices identified by Masi et al. (2018) (25 CE practices) and

Garza-Reyes et al. (2018) (11 additional CE practices), can be utilized to ascertain the type of CE practice subject to monitoring and assessment.

The objective of Step 1 is to delineate the scope and focus of the practice to be monitored and assessed. The CE practice description table (Table 8-1) is designed to aid in refining and establishing the boundaries of the monitoring and assessment focus. Correctly identifying the type of CE practice is crucial for clarifying the study case focus and defining assessment boundaries, which is essential information for selecting the impact assessment method (Step 2). However, it is important to acknowledge that CE is a dynamic concept, and the provided list may not encompass all existing CE practices. The critical aspect is the ability to define and describe the practice comprehensively to understand the goals for monitoring and measuring the necessary performance aspects.

As previously mentioned, the list of CE practices (Table 8-1) is derived from Masi et al. (2018) and Garza-Reyes et al. (2018). However, these publications do not offer direct descriptions of these practices. As the developed framework begins with the identification and selection of relevant CE practices for assessment, the aim has been to provide descriptions for these practices. The definitions of practices have been generated using two large language models (LLMs) and validated by an expert. Additionally, comparisons were made between the generated definitions for the CE practices, and suitable descriptions were selected by the expert based on the best available knowledge from the original sources.

Table 8-1. Circular economy practice list with definitions.

CE Practice	Definition
1. Designing products for reduced consumption of resources	A key principle of the circular economy that emphasizes resource efficiency beginning at the product design phase. This approach involves minimizing the amount of materials used, prioritizing renewable and recycled materials, and designing for durability to reduce the need for replacements. The goal is to create products that have a lower environmental impact throughout their life cycle, from material extraction to end-of-life disposal.
2. Design of products for reuse and or recovery of materials and or component parts	Designing products for reuse or recovery of materials and/or component parts involves considering and applying design for reuse, disassembly, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and recycling. This approach aims to ensure that products are designed in a way that facilitates the recovery and reuse of their materials and components at the end of their life cycle, contributing to reducing material consumption and promoting circularity.

CE Practice	Definition
3. Design of processes for minimisation of waste	Designing processes for waste minimisation is a circular practice that is a component of eco-design and is related to internal practices for resource utility and efficiency. Manufacturing SMEs can implement this practice by considering and applying designs that minimise waste. Implementation may include design for durability and strategies that utilise easily recyclable materials. This approach can provide short-term returns for a company.
4. Reducing material consumption	Reducing material consumption is achieved through the design of products for reduced resource consumption, reuse or recovery of materials and component parts, and the design of processes that minimise waste. It also involves using renewable materials and energy in the production process and reducing energy consumption.
5. Using renewable materials and energy in the production process.	Using renewable materials and energy in the production process refers to a company's efforts to track and reduce the consumption of non-renewable resources by identifying and implementing substitutes that are derived from renewable sources. This involves maintaining records of non-renewable material consumption, analyzing ways to decrease reliance on such materials, and taking concrete actions to replace them with renewable alternatives. Similarly, the process includes keeping track of non-renewable energy usage, assessing the feasibility of integrating renewable energy into production, and actively working towards transitioning from fossil fuel-based energy sources to renewable ones.
6. Reducing energy consumption	Reducing energy consumption involves systematically tracking and assessing the use of electricity, coal, gas, and other energy sources within a company's operations. This requires maintaining a record of energy consumption, analyzing opportunities to lower energy usage, and implementing actions aimed at achieving energy efficiency. Additionally, companies may explore whether any of their processes can generate energy and assess the feasibility of utilizing self-produced or renewable energy sources.
7. Reducing pollutants emissions	Reducing pollutant emissions involves keeping records of pollution levels and monitoring greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within a company's operations. This practice includes assessing and identifying opportunities to minimize emissions and implementing actions aimed at reducing their environmental impact. Additionally, companies may track the use of petrol, diesel, and other fossil fuels, analyze ways to decrease their consumption, and take steps to reduce reliance on these sources. In cases where fertilizers and pesticides are used, efforts may also be made to evaluate and mitigate their environmental effects.
8. Reducing wastes	Reducing waste involves maintaining records of waste generation, ensuring efficient waste separation, and actively supporting landfill prevention. Companies implementing waste reduction strategies assess and optimize waste circulation by treating waste as an input for other processes. Additionally, if waste disposal is necessary, they ensure that it is conducted in an environmentally responsible manner.
9. Green packaging	Green packaging refers to the use of packaging materials that are both environmentally friendly and efficient. This involves selecting materials that minimize environmental impact while ensuring that the packaging remains functional and effective in protecting and distributing products.
10. Special training for workers on environmental issues and circular economies	Special training for workers on environmental issues and circular economies involves initiatives aimed at increasing environmental awareness among all members of an organization. This includes providing formal and periodic training to both new and existing employees, ensuring the sharing of information and achievements related to circular economy practices. The goal is to integrate environmental considerations into the workforce's daily activities and decision-making processes.
11. Including environmental factors in the internal performance evaluation systems	Including environmental factors in the internal performance evaluation system involves setting specific targets for reducing the consumption of water, energy, waste, and raw materials within a company. This approach integrates environmental considerations into performance assessments, ensuring that sustainability metrics are actively monitored and managed. Additionally, companies may use an indicators dashboard to visualize and track progress toward their environmental goals, facilitating continuous improvement in circularity practices.

CE Practice	Definition
12. Environmental auditing programmes	Environmental auditing programs involve identifying environmental risks and systematically measuring and monitoring environmental impacts through tools such as ISO 14000, life cycle analysis, or material flow analysis. These programs help companies track their sustainability performance and ensure compliance with environmental regulations. Additionally, organizations may adopt sustainability frameworks such as the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), or Dow Jones Sustainability Index (DJSI) to enhance their environmental governance. The implementation of an environmental policy and actions to minimize the environmental impact of activities related to energy, water, and ecosystem conservation are also integral to such auditing initiatives.
13. Eco-labelling of products	Eco-labelling of products involves sharing environmental benefits with customers to encourage the purchase of products with lower environmental impacts. This practice aims to raise awareness and motivate consumers to choose more sustainable options by providing clear and transparent environmental information about the product.
14. Selecting suppliers using environmental criteria	Selecting suppliers using environmental criteria involves incorporating sustainable and circular procurement practices to enhance material efficiency and secure future sustainable resources. This includes sourcing recycled or second-hand materials whenever possible and ensuring that the supply chain is actively engaged in circular economy principles. Companies may require suppliers to provide environmental information on their activities and products and use these insights to assess and develop suppliers based on circularity standards. Additionally, purchasing decisions are made based on a total cost assessment that considers transportation, use, and waste management costs. Clear communication of environmental purchasing criteria with all stakeholders further strengthens this approach.
15. Cooperating with other firms to establish eco-industrial chains	Cooperating with other firms to establish eco-industrial chains involves forming partnerships with companies from both the same and different sectors, as well as with suppliers and educational institutions, to support circular economy initiatives. This collaboration aims to optimize resource efficiency and promote industrial symbiosis by facilitating the exchange and reuse of materials, energy, and water among businesses. Additionally, companies engaged in these partnerships may assess the employment impact of such collaborations, including both direct and indirect job creation.
16. Reusing energy and/or water across the value chain	Reusing energy and/or water across the value chain refers to sharing resources like energy and water with other companies within the value chain. This practice may include sharing energy generated by one company for future use in another company's processes or utilizing water produced by another company for their operations. It represents an effort to increase efficiency and minimize the waste of valuable resources by reintroducing them into the production processes of different stakeholders.
17. Taking back products from consumers after the end of their functional life	Taking back products from consumers after the end of their functional life involves the implementation of recovery programs where companies retrieve used products that can no longer perform their intended function due to wear, damage, or obsolescence. These products have reached the end of their lifecycle and are collected to ensure proper disposal, refurbishment, or recycling. This practice aims to prevent waste mismanagement, promote material circularity, and mitigate environmental impacts. Additionally, companies may work to address misconceptions or misunderstandings related to product recovery at the end of its functional life and implement strategies to ensure consistency in waste recovery processes, reducing uncertainties in collection, sorting, and material reuse.
18. Taking back products from customers at the end of their usage	Taking back products from customers at the end of their usage involves the implementation of recovery programs where companies retrieve products that are no longer wanted or needed by customers, even if they are still functional. These products may be returned due to customer upgrades, changes in preferences, or shifts in business needs, rather than functional failure. Companies collect these items to refurbish, resell, repurpose, or reintroduce them into the market through circular business models such as leasing or second-hand sales. Additionally, companies may work to address misconceptions or misunderstandings related to product recovery at the end of their usage and implement strategies to make waste recovery more predictable and efficient by standardizing collection methods and improving sorting and processing consistency.
19. Refurbishing products	Refurbishing products involves restoring used items to full working condition by repairing or replacing major faulty components. As a key strategy within circular economy models, refurbishing prevents premature disposal by extending product lifespans, enabling resale or reuse. Companies adopting this approach can significantly reduce waste and conserve resources. However, they must address common misconceptions, such as concerns about the quality and reliability of refurbished products compared to new ones. Maintaining a stable supply of spare parts is also crucial to ensuring the long-term viability and efficiency of refurbishing operations.

CE Practice	Definition
20. Remanufacturing products	Remanufacturing products involves restoring used or worn-out products to a like-new condition through an industrial process that includes disassembly, cleaning, repairing, replacing components, and reassembling. Unlike refurbishing, which typically focuses on repairing or replacing faulty components to make a product functional again, remanufacturing ensures that the final product meets original performance specifications, often with the same or improved quality and reliability. Companies implementing remanufacturing as a business model must address misconceptions, such as the belief that remanufactured products are inferior to new ones, and ensure a consistent supply of spare parts to maintain operational feasibility.
21. Use of recycled materials	The use of recycled materials involves incorporating materials that have been recovered and reprocessed into new production cycles instead of relying solely on virgin raw materials. Companies implementing this practice must ensure that the quality and performance of the recycled materials meet production standards while also addressing potential misconceptions about the reliability of recycled materials. By integrating recycled inputs, businesses can reduce resource depletion, lower environmental impacts, and enhance circular economy initiatives.
22. Adopting a leasing or service based marketing strategy	<p>Adopting a leasing or service-based marketing strategy shifts from traditional product ownership to a model where customers access products through leasing, rental, or service agreements. This approach allows companies to retain control over the product lifecycle, ensuring better maintenance, extended usability, and easier recovery for refurbishment, remanufacturing, or recycling.</p> <p>By implementing leasing, businesses can reduce resource consumption and waste while fostering long-term customer relationships. However, they must address concerns about ownership loss, contract limitations, and the perceived value of leased products. Ensuring a seamless customer experience, transparent terms, and strong after-service support is crucial to making this strategy viable and appealing.</p>
23. Cascading use of components and materials	The cascading use of components and materials refers to the practice of maximizing the utility of materials by repurposing them for multiple applications once they are no longer suitable for their original function. When a material or component loses its original properties and cannot be effectively recycled, it is redirected into alternative uses to extend its lifespan and delay disposal. This approach helps to reduce waste and resource depletion by ensuring that materials are used to their fullest potential before being discarded.
24. Targeting Green segments of the market	Targeting green segments of the market involves identifying and addressing the needs of environmentally conscious consumers. Companies implementing this approach take strategic actions to fully meet the expectations of green customers, ensuring their products align with sustainability values. This may include having a clear expansion plan for the green market and integrating environmental aspects into marketing strategies to highlight the ecological benefits of their products. By doing so, businesses can enhance their appeal to sustainability-driven consumers and strengthen their position in the circular economy.
25. Cross-functional cooperation for environmental improvements	Cross-functional cooperation for environmental improvements involves collaboration among various departments within an organization—such as purchasing, research and development, marketing, and sustainability—to enhance the company's environmental performance. This integrated approach ensures that environmental considerations are embedded across all functions, leading to more effective and cohesive sustainability initiatives. By fostering inter-departmental collaboration, companies can better align their strategies, share knowledge, and implement practices that collectively contribute to environmental goals.
26. Design for durability	Design for durability focuses on extending a product's lifespan by incorporating robust materials, modular components, and timeless aesthetics to ensure continued functionality and appeal. It involves strategies that minimize the risk of obsolescence, enabling multiple life cycles through repairability, refurbishment, or technological upgrades. Products designed with durability in mind contribute to circular economy principles by reducing waste generation and resource depletion. Additionally, consumer acceptance plays a crucial role, as durable products must retain their perceived value and usability over extended periods, mitigating concerns related to aging technology or aesthetic wear.

CE Practice	Definition
27. Circular management, culture and continuous monitoring	Circular management, culture, and continuous monitoring involve the integration of circular economy principles into an organization's core strategy, culture, and daily operations. This includes establishing a clear circular economy strategy, assigning dedicated personnel responsible for circular initiatives, and embedding circularity into corporate values. It also requires continuous tracking of environmental performance through data systems, regular reporting, and performance assessments that align with sustainability goals. Organizations adopting circular management practices ensure that circularity is not only a one-time transition but a continuously evolving process supported by management commitment, employee engagement, and structured monitoring mechanisms.
28. Awareness within customers	<p>Customer awareness in circular economy models involves educating consumers on sustainable practices like refurbishment, remanufacturing, and leasing. This includes transparent communication about product sustainability, warranties, and quality certifications to build trust and reduce perceived risks. Companies can use marketing campaigns, partnerships, and incentives to shift consumer preferences from ownership to service-based models or products with extended lifecycles.</p> <p>A critical aspect is encouraging consumers to prioritize product functionality and longevity over the desire for newness. Public campaigns, educational programs, and industry collaborations are essential in fostering this behavioral shift. Engaging customers through shared sustainability values can turn them into advocates for circular consumption, enhancing loyalty based on environmental responsibility.</p>
29. Awareness within the supply chain	Awareness within the supply chain involves educating and engaging all stakeholders—including suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors—in circular economy principles. This collective understanding ensures that each participant recognizes the value of sustainable practices, such as refurbishment and remanufacturing, leading to cohesive efforts toward resource efficiency and waste reduction. By fostering this shared awareness, companies can align their supply chain operations with environmental objectives, promoting a seamless transition to circular business models.
30. Reusing products	Reusing products refers to the practice of extending a product's lifespan by using it again for its original purpose, rather than discarding it. This aligns with circular economy principles by preserving the embedded energy and materials in a product, reducing waste, and minimizing the environmental impact compared to recycling or disposal. Consumer perception plays a significant role in the adoption of reused products, as factors like trust in quality, warranty availability, and pricing influence their willingness to engage in reuse.
31. Recycling of scrap or waste	The Recycling of scrap or waste refers to "any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes." This process includes the reprocessing of organic material but explicitly excludes energy recovery and the reprocessing of materials intended for use as fuels or for backfilling operations. Recycling plays a crucial role in utilizing still-usable resources, reducing the amount of waste requiring treatment or disposal, and minimizing environmental impacts. However, high recycling rates may sometimes discourage efforts to reduce overall waste generation.
32. Recycling of end-of-life products	Recycling of end-of-life products refers to the process of recovering materials from products that have reached the end of their functional life. This involves reprocessing waste materials into products, materials, or substances for either their original use or other applications. However, it excludes energy recovery, and the reprocessing of materials intended as fuels or for backfilling operations. End-of-life recycling plays a crucial role in reducing waste disposal impacts, recovering valuable materials, and minimizing reliance on virgin resources, though challenges exist in recycling complex, mixed-material goods such as plastics with contaminants and rare earth metals.
33. Recycling of products after usage	Recycling of products after usage involves recovering and reprocessing materials from products that have been used but may not have necessarily reached the end of their functional life. This process is often associated with reintroducing materials into production systems sooner than end-of-life recycling, potentially reducing material degradation and extending the usability of components. This excludes energy recovery and reprocessing for fuel or backfilling operations. It aligns with strategies that prioritize maintaining material value for as long as possible, integrating principles such as refurbishment, remanufacturing, and cascading use of components.

CE Practice	Definition
34. Adopting an updating market strategy	<p>Adopting an updating market strategy involves integrating continuous improvements into products and services to enhance their longevity, functionality, and customer appeal. This strategy is particularly relevant in circular economy models, where extending product life cycles reduces waste and resource consumption.</p> <p>Companies implementing this strategy focus on regular updates rather than full product replacements, ensuring that components, software, or designs remain relevant. Additionally, addressing misconceptions about updating, such as concerns over obsolescence, helps build consumer trust.</p> <p>By embracing an updating market strategy, businesses can increase customer retention, reduce environmental impact, and contribute to a more sustainable economy.</p>
35. Incentives	<p>Incentives are essential for promoting circular economy practices by encouraging recycling, reuse, and sustainable consumption. These include price incentives, warranty services, and trial periods to boost consumer confidence in reused and remanufactured products. Businesses also offer internal incentives for employees and suppliers to engage in circular activities.</p> <p>Governments support the transition through tax incentives, financial aid, and legally binding targets, ensuring regulatory compliance and rewarding sustainable practices. These strategies can help accelerate circular economy adoption while enhancing resource efficiency and environmental sustainability.</p>
36. Legislation and policies	<p>Legislation and policies are regulatory frameworks designed to promote sustainability and circular economy practices. These laws establish standards, incentives, and enforcement mechanisms that guide businesses and consumers toward resource-efficient production, waste reduction, and responsible consumption.</p> <p>Governments implement tax incentives, subsidies, and eco-schemes to support sustainable practices while enforcing legally binding targets and penalties to ensure compliance with circular economy goals. These policies drive systemic change by aligning economic activities with environmental sustainability, fostering innovation, and ensuring long-term resource efficiency.</p>

Step 2. Selection of impact assessment method.

Step 2 involves selecting an appropriate impact assessment method, guided by the scope and research question of the practice under study, as adapted from Walzberg et al. (2021) and Elia et al. (2017). A comprehensive list of assessment methods and methodologies is provided to facilitate the selection of the most suitable assessment method. This list includes detailed descriptions of each metric, the specific research questions or areas of interest they address, the applicable scope, whether the metric constitutes a method or methodology, and whether it offers direct or indirect quantification (Table 8-2).

Environmental assessment methods and methodologies are designed to address various questions of interest. In the context of monitoring and assessing impacts, selecting the most appropriate method or methodology is critical, as this choice determines the questions that can be effectively addressed. Key considerations include the scope of the method or methodology, the level of data granularity required for the assessment, and whether the selected method provides direct or indirect quantification. These factors must be carefully

evaluated to ensure the selection of the most suitable method or methodology for assessing the CE practice.

The compiled list of methodologies identified from the scientific literature, along with the supplementary information provided for each methodology, is intended to facilitate the selection of the most appropriate methodology. The selection process should commence with the research question of interest, specifically, what the assessment aims to address. The descriptions offer concise information about the metrics. The questions generated for each methodology in the table should be regarded as exemplary, aiming to elucidate the type of question the methodology primarily addresses (these questions can be formulated and posed in various ways). Once this aspect is clarified, the subsequent crucial step is to examine the scope of the methodology—whether it is capable of addressing the level of the question of interest and the scope of the practice. This step will aid in eliminating unsuitable methodologies. For example, if the focus is on understanding product-level impacts, a life cycle assessment (LCA) is a more suitable methodology than input-output (I-O) models, which are designed to assess large systems (i.e., macro-level assessments).

The final critical step is to determine whether the metric provides direct or indirect quantification. This is essential in planning the overall monitoring content and identifying the key metrics it should include. The selection of the impact assessment method will come with potential metrics, which can then be supplemented with additional necessary ones based on what the impact method already encompasses. For instance, when the PEF (product environmental footprint) method is employed in the LCA, the results include a set of 16 different environmental impact categories, which are impact metrics. This implies that for the remaining relevant metrics selection for the assessed CE practice, the practitioner can focus more on intrinsic metrics, as the majority of the environmental impact metrics are covered by the selection of LCA as an environmental assessment method. The study by Elia et al. (2017) provides more detailed information about which metrics yield direct and indirect quantification. They categorize the CE requirements into five groups (Reducing input and use of natural resources; Increasing the share of renewable and recyclable resources; Reducing emissions; Reducing valuable material losses; and Increasing the value durability of products) and through this categorization demonstrate how each analysed methodology is capable of producing direct and/or indirect quantification based on the CE requirement,

which can be beneficial in choosing the appropriate metric for the assessment (if this level of granularity is necessary for the assessment method selection). The authors also use the CE requirements to define which methodologies are capable of addressing the aforementioned CE requirements, further assisting in the selection of a suitable assessment methodology.

For further information on appropriate methods for CE assessment, refer to Sassanelli et al. (2019), Walzberg et al. (2021), Elia et al. (2017), and Helander et al. (2019). These studies offer various approaches for a more comprehensive selection of assessment methods. Notably, the works of Elia et al. (2017) and Walzberg et al. (2021) are particularly insightful, while Sassanelli et al. (2019) provides a systematic literature review of existing CE assessment methods.

As explained, Table 8-3 provides an overview of methods available for environmental impact assessment with summarized key information. It is worth noting that in this specific study, LCA was a predetermined choice of environmental impact assessment method. However, presentation of the list in this deliverable aims to demonstrate the reasoned and purposeful selection of a suitable method in Step 2 according to the framework.

Table 8-2. Performance assessment metrics applied for measuring circular economy.

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Analytical modelling (Uses analytical modelling methods for assessment)	Analytical modeling involves using mathematical models to simulate and predict the behavior of complex systems. This method is applied to assess the performance and environmental impacts of circular economy strategies under various scenarios. It can include optimization, scenario analysis, or system dynamics models to evaluate resource use, waste generation, and emissions.	How can different circular economy strategies be modeled to predict their environmental and economic impacts, and how can these models be used to optimize resource use and minimize waste?	Analytical modeling can be applied at the micro, meso, or macro level, depending on the complexity and scale of the system being modeled. It is especially useful for simulating systems and assessing strategies where direct measurement is difficult.	Indirect
Carbon Footprint (CF)	The Carbon Footprint (CF) quantifies the total greenhouse gas emissions, expressed in CO ₂ equivalents, associated with a product, service, or organization. This metric helps assess the contribution to global warming potential across the entire life cycle of a product or service. CF is an index-based method commonly used to measure climate change impacts related to carbon emissions.	What is the total amount of greenhouse gas emissions (in CO ₂ equivalents) associated with the life cycle of a product, service, or organization, (and how can these emissions be reduced)?	The CF metric typically spans the full life cycle of a product, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal, and can be applied at the micro, meso, or macro levels.	Direct
Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) is a lifecycle-based method used to quantify the total amount of energy required to produce a product or service. It aggregates all forms of energy use, including fossil and renewable sources, across the entire product life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal. CED is an index-based method that provides a single indicator for energy consumption, which helps assess the sustainability of products or services in terms of their total energy footprint.	How much total energy is required across the life cycle of a product or service, and how can energy efficiency be improved in the production and disposal phases?	The CED method typically operates at the micro level, focusing on individual products or services, but can be applied at the macro level for large-scale systems or regions.	Direct
Dissipation area index (DAI)	The Dissipation Area Index (DAI) is derived from the Sustainable Process Index (SPI) and focuses on measuring the total area required to absorb the output flows of a specific process. Unlike other indices, the DAI includes the absorption of substances that are not part of closed natural cycles, which are considered unsustainable. The DAI provides a means to quantify human pressure on the biosphere by focusing on the spatial requirements needed for absorption and sustainability.	How much area is required to absorb the environmental outputs of a process, and how does this reflect the sustainability of the system in terms of resource absorption?	The DAI operates at the micro, meso, or macro levels depending on the specific application, from individual processes or products to broader systems.	Indirect

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Ecological Footprint (EF)	The Ecological Footprint (EF) is an index-based method that estimates the biological capacity of the planet consumed by human activities or populations. Specifically, it measures the total amount of productive land required, including land for food, crops, timber, energy, infrastructure, and the area needed to absorb carbon emissions generated. The EF is expressed in global hectares (gha), allowing for comparisons across different types of land use and geographical locations. The EF indirectly integrates various environmental impacts, such as land-use change, CO ₂ emissions, and resource consumption.	How much land area is required to support the consumption and waste generation of a product, service, or population, and how does this contribute to the sustainability of the system?	The EF can be applied at the micro, meso, or macro level, depending on the system being assessed, such as an individual product, a company, or a nation.	Indirect
Ecological Rucksack (ER)	The Ecological Rucksack (ER) is an index-based method that quantifies the total material input required for the production, use, and disposal of a product or service, excluding the final product's mass. It measures the hidden environmental costs embedded in the product's life cycle. ER is closely related to the Material Inputs Per unit of Service (MIPS) method but focuses specifically on the material intensity, i.e., the mass of materials that are required for each product or service. The ER method includes all material flows, not just those consumed directly by the product, providing a broader environmental footprint measurement.	What is the total amount of material required to produce a product, excluding the product itself, and how can material efficiency be improved in the production process?	The ER method operates primarily at the micro level, applied to individual products or services, but can also be used for broader assessments of processes or regions.	Direct
Economy-Wide Material Flow Analysis (EW-MFA)	Economy-Wide Material Flow Analysis (EW-MFA) is a method used to assess the material flows within an economy by tracking the movement of materials through production, consumption, and disposal. It provides a comprehensive view of material extraction, processing, consumption, and recycling within a defined system, often focusing on macro-scale systems like national or regional economies. EW-MFA allows for the quantification of the total material flows, offering insights into resource use efficiency and the effectiveness of recycling or waste management strategies.	What are the total material flows within an economy or region, and how can material use be optimized to improve resource efficiency and minimize waste?	EW-MFA is applied primarily at the macro level, often focusing on national or global material flows. However, it can also be used at the meso level, such as within industries or regions.	Indirect
Ecosystem Damage Potential (EDP)	Ecosystem Damage Potential (EDP) is a method used to assess the environmental impacts of land use and transformation on ecosystems, particularly focusing on species diversity. The EDP uses various damage functions and characterization factors based on land use types to calculate the potential harm to ecosystems. Unlike other metrics such as the Carbon Footprint (CF), the EDP focuses specifically on the damage caused by land use changes, which can impact biodiversity and ecosystem health.	How does land use and transformation impact biodiversity and ecosystem health, and what is the potential long-term damage to ecosystems from human activities?	The EDP method operates at the micro level, as it typically focuses on specific land use changes and their direct impacts on ecosystems, but it can also be used at the meso or macro level when assessing broader land use practices or policies across regions or countries.	Indirect

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Embodied Energy (EE)	Embodied Energy (EE) is a method that quantifies the total energy required to produce a product or service, including all direct and indirect energy flows throughout its life cycle. This includes energy for raw material extraction, manufacturing, transportation, and disposal. It is often expressed in MJ/kg and can account for both renewable and non-renewable energy sources. EE is an index-based method widely used in assessing resource efficiency and identifying areas where energy use can be minimized.	How much total energy is embedded in the production and life cycle of a product or service, and how can this energy consumption be reduced to improve resource efficiency?	The EE method is primarily applied at the micro level, focusing on individual products or processes, though it can also be applied at the macro level in certain large-scale assessments.	Direct
EMergy Analysis (EMA)	EMergy Analysis (EMA) is an energy-based method that evaluates the total energy input, both direct and indirect, required to produce a product or service, using solar energy joules (seJ) as the unit of measurement. Unlike traditional energy assessments, EMA incorporates both the quantity and the quality of energy involved in production processes. This metric helps assess the sustainability of a product or system by considering the relative values of different types of energy and their efficiency in the context of natural ecosystems. It is particularly useful for evaluating the role of renewable and non-renewable energy sources within circular economy systems.	How much energy is required to produce a product or service, and how does the quality of energy used influence the sustainability of production processes?	EMA is typically applied at the micro level to evaluate the energy flows in specific systems or processes, but it can also be applied at the meso and macro levels when evaluating broader systems like industrial parks or entire economies.	Direct
Energy/exergy based analysis	Energy/Exergy-Based Analysis (EMA) is an assessment method that combines energy and exergy principles to evaluate the efficiency and sustainability of systems. Exergy refers to the maximum usable energy of a material or system, and its application helps in evaluating the efficiency with which energy is utilized. EMA provides insights into the thermodynamic performance of processes by considering the quantity and quality of energy consumed, especially focusing on the transformation processes. The use of exergy also highlights potential inefficiencies, making it useful for improving energy performance.	How efficiently is energy used within a system, and how can the quality of energy be optimized to improve sustainability and reduce inefficiencies?	EMA can be applied at the micro, meso, or macro levels, depending on the system being analyzed. It can be used for evaluating individual processes or broader systems, such as industrial parks or entire economies, providing a detailed view of energy flows and their quality across different scales.	Direct

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Environmental Performance Strategy Map (EPSM)	The Environmental Performance Strategy Map (EPSM) is a graphical representation tool used to integrate multiple environmental impact categories, including water, carbon, energy, emissions, and work environment (e.g., number of lost workdays per product unit). The EPSM defines a target for each footprint and maps the results on a spider diagram. The cost dimension is incorporated as the second axis, and the volume of a pyramid represents the overall environmental impact, termed as the Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI). EPSM provides a comprehensive view of a product or service's environmental performance by integrating different impact categories into a single indicator, making it easier to communicate results, though it may face limitations in data availability and standardization.	How can the environmental impacts across multiple categories (carbon, water, energy, etc.) be integrated and communicated effectively to support strategic decision-making and improve sustainability?	EPSM is used primarily at the meso and macro levels, often applied to broader systems like industries or entire supply chains. It provides a high-level view of environmental performance across various categories, making it suitable for strategic decision-making.	Indirect
Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EE-MRIO)	Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EE-MRIO) is an extension of traditional input-output analysis that integrates environmental data, offering a comprehensive approach to quantifying the environmental impacts across global supply chains. Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) analysis is an economic assessment method used to study the interdependencies between industries and regions in a global economy. It focuses on understanding how the production and consumption in one region influence the economies of other regions through trade and supply chain interactions. EE-MRIO links national and regional economic systems, providing a way to model the interdependencies between industries, countries, and environmental impacts (e.g., CO ₂ emissions, resource use). It enables the assessment of indirect environmental impacts, such as those from imported goods and services, and is often used to analyze material flows, waste, and recycling at a global scale.	How do global economic activities and trade affect environmental impacts, and how can material and energy flows be quantified across international supply chains?	EE-MRIO operates primarily at the macro level, assessing global or regional economic and environmental flows. It is particularly useful for tracking the environmental consequences of international trade and global material cycles, and it can incorporate time series data to explore changes over time.	Indirect

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Framework for measuring circularity in cities	The Framework for Measuring Circularity in Cities provides a structured approach to assessing the progress and performance of urban areas transitioning to a circular economy. This framework integrates indicators across environmental, economic, and social dimensions, enabling cities to measure key aspects such as material flows, waste management, renewable resource use, and environmental impact. It focuses on fostering circularity through systemic changes, such as the adoption of smart urban metabolism and the promotion of sustainable resource use and energy systems at the city level. This framework is essential for cities aiming to achieve a circular economy by offering a set of indicators for monitoring, evaluating, and improving circular practices.	How can cities track their progress towards circularity, and what indicators can be used to monitor the effectiveness of circular economy strategies in urban environments?	This framework is applied at the macro level, focusing on cities as whole systems, measuring various facets of urban life and the effectiveness of circular economy strategies implemented across the urban environment.	Indirect
Indicator analysis (Sustainable Process Index, Dissipation Area Index, Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator)	Indicator Analysis combines multiple index-based methods to assess environmental impacts in circular economy strategies. The Sustainable Process Index (SPI) evaluates the total area necessary to embed a product or process into the biosphere in a sustainable manner, considering material and energy flows. The Dissipation Area Index (DAI), derived from SPI, focuses on the area needed to absorb the output flows of a specific process, highlighting unsustainable flows. The Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI) is part of the Environmental Performance Strategy Map (EPSM), which combines several environmental footprints (carbon, water, energy, emissions) and integrates them into a single indicator to assess overall environmental performance. These indices help quantify the sustainability of processes and products in a comprehensive manner, while allowing for comparisons across different strategies.	How can multiple environmental impacts (e.g., carbon, water, energy) be integrated into a single indicator to assess the sustainability and environmental performance of circular economy strategies?	These indicators are applicable at the micro, meso, or macro levels, depending on the system being assessed. They can be used to evaluate individual products, regional systems, or larger-scale industrial processes.	Indirect
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a standardized methodology used to quantify and evaluate the environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product's life, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. It encompasses a detailed accounting of material and energy flows through the entire product life cycle, allowing for the identification of environmental hotspots and trade-offs between different impact categories, such as carbon footprint, water usage, and resource consumption. LCA is one of the most widely used methods in sustainability and circular economy assessments due to its ability to provide a comprehensive view of environmental impacts.	What are the environmental impacts associated with the full life cycle of a product or service, and how can these impacts be minimized through design, production, and end-of-life management?	LCA can be applied at the micro, meso, or macro level. At the micro level, LCA is used to assess individual products or processes. At the macro level, it is applied to assess systems or sectors, such as industries or regions, providing insights into larger-scale sustainability challenges.	Direct

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Material Flow Analysis (MFA)	Material Flow Analysis (MFA) is a systematic assessment method that tracks and analyzes the flows and stocks of materials within a defined system (e.g., a city, region, or country). It focuses on understanding the material processes in space and time, such as transformation, transportation, and storage activities. MFA helps to assess resource consumption, waste management, material availability, and material disposition, thereby informing strategies for more efficient material use and circularity. It is particularly useful for identifying material inefficiencies and waste in systems, although it does not typically focus on the environmental impacts associated with material flows.	How can material flows be tracked and analyzed to assess resource efficiency and sustainability in a system, and how can circular economy strategies improve material management?	MFA operates at the micro, meso, or macro level, depending on the system being analyzed. It can be applied to small-scale studies (e.g., individual products) or large-scale systems (e.g., global material flows), providing flexibility across various scales.	Indirect
Material Inputs Per unit of Service (MIPS)	Material Inputs Per unit of Service (MIPS) is an index-based method used to measure the material intensity of a product or service. It calculates the total material inputs required for the full life cycle of a product or service, from production through use and disposal, normalized by the service provided (e.g., material per unit of product or service delivered). This method follows a cradle-to-cradle approach, considering all material inputs across the entire lifecycle of a product or service. MIPS is particularly useful for evaluating the material efficiency and identifying areas where resource use can be reduced.	How much material is required to provide a given service or product, and how can material efficiency be improved throughout the product lifecycle?	MIPS is typically applied at the micro level, focusing on individual products or services. It can also be applied at more strategic levels to assess the material intensity of business practices or supply chains.	Direct
Material/substance/chemical based analysis	Material/Substance/Chemical-Based Analysis is an assessment approach that focuses on understanding the flow, usage, and impacts of specific materials, substances, or chemicals within a system. This method examines the life cycle of materials from extraction, production, and use to disposal or recycling. It is particularly concerned with tracking hazardous substances, the toxicity of materials, and the potential risks they pose to human health and the environment. Chemical-based analysis provides insights into how the chemical properties of materials affect their behavior during various stages of the life cycle, such as biodegradation or persistence in ecosystems. This analysis is integral in evaluating the sustainability of circular economy strategies, especially in preventing harmful substances from re-entering the supply chain.	How can the use and flow of specific materials, substances, or chemicals be tracked and managed to minimize environmental and health risks, and how can circular economy strategies address the reuse or recycling of hazardous substances to prevent adverse impacts?	This analysis operates at the micro or meso level, often applied to individual products or material categories. It can be used in specific sectors such as construction, electronics, or textiles, and may focus on a single substance or a group of chemicals used in products. The scope can be expanded to larger-scale assessments when considering systemic impacts, such as regional or national regulations on chemical use and waste management.	Direct

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
MRIO, A multi-regional input output	Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) analysis is an economic assessment method used to study the interdependencies between industries and regions in a global economy. It focuses on understanding how the production and consumption in one region influence the economies of other regions through trade and supply chain interactions. MRIO tracks the flow of goods and services between countries or regions and analyzes how these flows impact economic output, resource use, and environmental emissions across multiple regions. This method is particularly useful for studying global supply chains, carbon footprints, and material flows, as it allows for the assessment of indirect environmental impacts such as greenhouse gas emissions or resource consumption that result from cross-border trade.	How do interregional trade and supply chains contribute to global environmental impacts, and how can circular economy strategies help minimize these impacts by redesigning global production and consumption systems for more sustainable outcomes?	MRIO operates at the macro level, typically involving national or global systems. It is applied to large-scale assessments that examine the environmental, economic, and social impacts of cross-border trade and the global movement of materials. MRIO can provide insights into the environmental performance of entire supply chains and trade networks, and it is often used to study the effects of economic policies or changes in global production systems.	Indirect
Substance flow analysis (SFA)	Substance Flow Analysis (SFA) is a method used to track and quantify the flows and stocks of specific substances within a defined system, focusing particularly on substances that may pose environmental or health risks. SFA aims to identify hazardous flows and stocks of substances, providing insights into how these substances move through various processes and their potential to cause harm. Unlike Material Flow Analysis (MFA), which deals with general material flows, SFA focuses on individual substances such as chemicals or pollutants, helping to design strategies for risk reduction and more sustainable management of hazardous substances. It plays a critical role in resource conservation, waste management, and recycling, especially for substances that are toxic or pose significant environmental threats.	How can the flows and stocks of hazardous substances be effectively tracked and managed to reduce environmental and health risks, and how can circular economy strategies help in minimizing the harmful impact of these substances through improved resource management and recycling practices?	SFA operates at the micro, meso, or macro levels, depending on the system and the specific substances being studied. It can be applied at the micro level for single products or at larger scales like regions or countries. The scope is typically focused on substances that are either harmful or have the potential to cause environmental or health issues if not properly managed.	Direct

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI)	The Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI) is a composite index that integrates various environmental footprints into a single indicator to assess the overall environmental performance of a product, service, or process. It combines five different environmental footprints—such as water, carbon, energy, emissions, and work environment—into a single measure of sustainability. These footprints are represented on a spider diagram, and the overall impact is visualized as a pyramid, with the height representing the impact. The SEPI provides a way to compare the environmental performance of different strategies, offering a comprehensive yet simplified understanding of their sustainability, but it requires standardization of data and methodology, which is a challenge in its application.	What is the overall environmental performance of a product, service, or process across multiple sustainability dimensions, such as carbon, water, energy, and emissions? / How can the integration of multiple environmental footprints into a single indicator like SEPI help evaluate the overall sustainability of circular economy strategies, and what are the challenges in ensuring data reliability and standardization for its application?	SEPI is applied at the meso or macro level, often used to assess the environmental performance of products, processes, or business strategies at a larger scale, such as industries, regions, or entire value chains. It is particularly useful for comparing different environmental strategies across various sectors and providing a holistic view of environmental impacts.	Indirect
Sustainable Process Index (SPI)	The Sustainable Process Index (SPI) is an environmental assessment tool designed to evaluate processes based on their sustainability, specifically by considering material and energy flows. The SPI aims to assess how much area is needed to embed a product or service sustainably into the biosphere, considering the entire lifecycle of the process or product. This index aggregates the mass and energy flows into a single metric, which provides a spatial representation of sustainability. It is useful for evaluating the environmental compatibility of industrial processes and comparing various processes or products in terms of their environmental impact and resource efficiency.	What is the environmental sustainability of an industrial process in terms of its material and energy flows throughout its lifecycle?	The SPI is applied primarily at the meso level, focusing on processes, activities, or regions. It measures the environmental pressure exerted by these systems, making it applicable to industries, production facilities, and eco-industrial parks. This method can also be used at the macro level for regional or national assessments, but it requires high availability of regional data, which can be uncertain and time-consuming to gather.	Indirect
Water Footprint (WF)	The Water Footprint (WF) is an environmental indicator that quantifies the total volume of freshwater consumed or polluted over the lifecycle of a product, service, or process. It considers the entire supply chain, from raw material extraction through production, use, and disposal, and includes direct and indirect water usage. WF is a life cycle-based approach that identifies water consumption in different stages and highlights the impact of water use on specific hydrological basins. The WF also accounts for water pollution, providing a holistic measure of water use efficiency. It is particularly useful in identifying critical areas of high water use and pollution within processes and can guide decision-making towards more sustainable water management practices.	What is the total volume of freshwater consumed or polluted throughout the lifecycle of a product or service, and how does this influence the sustainability of water use in the circular economy?	The WF operates at the micro, meso, or macro level depending on the product, service, or system being analyzed. It is applied at the product level to evaluate the water use associated with individual goods and services but can also be extended to sectors, regions, or entire nations to assess large-scale water consumption patterns and guide policy decisions.	Direct

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) and Fuzzy Logic	Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) is a set of methods used to evaluate and prioritize different alternatives based on multiple conflicting criteria. In the context of circular economy (CE), MCDM helps assess the trade-offs between various performance metrics such as environmental impact, cost, and resource efficiency, enabling decision-makers to select the most sustainable options. Fuzzy logic, often used in conjunction with MCDM, is a mathematical approach that deals with uncertainty and imprecision in decision-making by allowing for partial truths rather than just binary decisions. This is particularly useful in CE assessments, where multiple uncertain variables (e.g., resource availability or environmental impact predictions) must be considered simultaneously.	How can the trade-offs between multiple sustainability criteria (e.g., environmental impact, cost, resource efficiency) be assessed and prioritized when making decisions in circular economy systems?	MCDM and fuzzy logic approaches are applied primarily at the micro and meso levels, where detailed decision-making is required for evaluating individual products, processes, or business models within the circular economy. These methods are particularly relevant for assessing performance across various lifecycle stages (e.g., production, use, end-of-life) and considering environmental, economic, and social factors in decision-making.	Indirect

Metric	Description	Research question/Question of interest	Scope	Direct/Indirect quantification of impacts
I-O models	Input-Output (IO) models are economic assessment tools used to understand the relationships between different sectors within an economy. They represent the interdependencies of industries, showing how the output of one industry serves as an input to another. This method provides insight into the flow of goods and services between sectors, helping to assess the economic impact of changes in production, consumption, or policy. Input-Output models can be extended to include environmental data (e.g., carbon emissions, resource use) to provide a more comprehensive view of the environmental impacts of economic activities. These models are particularly useful for analyzing the indirect effects of economic activities, such as the environmental impacts of imported goods and services.	How do changes in production and consumption patterns in one sector influence the economic and environmental impacts across other sectors in the economy, and how can Input-Output models be used to assess these interdependencies?	Input-Output models operate primarily at the macro level, assessing the interconnections between entire industries or economies. They are used to evaluate large-scale systems, such as national or global economies, and can be applied to study the economic and environmental effects of changes in policy, production patterns, or consumption behavior across sectors.	Indirect
Discrete Event Simulation (DES)	Discrete Event Simulation (DES) is a method used to model and analyze complex systems where events occur at discrete points in time. It simulates the operation of a system by representing it as a series of events (e.g., arrivals, departures, or processing stages) that happen at specific times. DES is often used in supply chain management, manufacturing, logistics, and circular economy scenarios to simulate and optimize the flow of materials, resources, and products. It allows for the analysis of system performance, identification of bottlenecks, and evaluation of various strategies under different scenarios, making it particularly useful for assessing the impact of changes in process design, production rates, and inventory management.	How can the behavior and performance of systems with discrete events (such as manufacturing lines or supply chains) be modeled to identify bottlenecks, optimize resource allocation, and predict the impact of different operational strategies over time?	DES is applicable at the micro or meso level, focusing on individual processes, systems, or facilities. It is particularly useful for modeling systems with a high degree of variability, such as production lines, waste management systems, or recycling facilities. The model can represent specific products, services, or entire processes, offering insights into how changes in one part of the system affect the overall system performance.	Indirect

Step 3. Selection of intrinsic and impact metrics for monitoring.

The identification of pertinent intrinsic and impact metrics is essential for the assessment and monitoring of circular economy (CE) cases. A wide array of CE metrics exists, among which some are intrinsic, designed to measure the circular nature of an activity, while others are impact metrics, intended to reveal the activity's impact. The literature review indicates that although existing indicators provide valuable insights into specific aspects of circularity, none comprehensively capture the necessary scope for measuring the environmental sustainability of a circular economy (Helander et al. 2019). Integrating intrinsic metrics with impact metrics, and vice versa, offers a more comprehensive approach, directly linking circular economy activities to their ultimate environmental impact.

Intrinsic vs. Impact Indicators: The framework distinguishes between two types of performance indicators for the CE, which is crucial for overall performance monitoring and assessment. Differentiating between these two types of indicators is vital, as the type of metric used determines what is observed and measured. As previously described, intrinsic metrics can only indicate the realization of circularity but serve as a vital source of information for impact assessment. Impact indicators directly display the achieved impact. Intrinsic indicators serve as tools to evaluate the inherent circularity and the effectiveness of circular economy principles within a product, process, or system. These indicators focus on assessing elements such as the percentage of recycled materials, the number of times a product can be reused, and the efficiency of material flow within a closed-loop system. Often referred to as "technical circularity" indicators, they provide a measure of how well circular economy practices are being implemented.

Impact indicators are essential for assessing the sustainability impacts of CE activities, including metrics such as greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, and social effects. These indicators often correspond closely with the impact categories utilized in life cycle assessment (LCA). They offer a thorough evaluation of how circularity influences various sustainability dimensions, such as environmental stewardship, economic resilience, social equity, and the management of hazardous substances.

To prevent double counting and misinterpretation of the CE practice assessment results, it is advisable to first select an impact assessment methodology, as recommended in Step 2. This selection aids in the exclusion of environmental impact metrics that may already be incorporated within the chosen environmental impact assessment methodology. Ideally, Steps 2 and 3 should be employed iteratively to screen for suitable environmental assessment methods and the relevant indicators in Step 3. In essence, these two steps function bilaterally, assisting in the determination of appropriate metric selection prior to finalizing (meaning locking down) the environmental impact method and the selection of additional necessary impact metrics. In this iterative process, the table of CE performance metrics serves as a starting point, as it provides insight into what type of indicators (such as those in the case of LCA described above) are already included in the methodology. Consequently, the focus for the remaining metric selection should be on identifying the missing metrics necessary for a comprehensive monitoring and assessment of the CE practice in question.

In the implementation of this step, practitioners will observe that the categorization of metrics into intrinsic and impact types is not a widely established practice. The majority of scientific literature does not classify or differentiate metrics into intrinsic or impact categories (Luthin et al. 2023; Gursel et al. 2022). While Luthin et al. and Gursel et al. address this distinction, they do not provide a comprehensive list of metrics categorized by type (intrinsic/impact). In this deliverable, categorization for agricultural and food-related indicators was performed, which was subsequently applied in the case (demos) applications of the developed Circular Economy (CE) monitoring framework. This is exemplified in the monitoring of agricultural side stream use cases within the EU Agro2Circular project. However, the list of metrics provided is not exhaustive and is intended solely for the demonstration of the framework's application. A more comprehensive list of indicators (cross sectoral) with metric type categorization (intrinsic/impact) is currently being developed as part of extensive PhD research and is scheduled for future publication.

8.2 Application of the framework to demos

Circularity monitoring in the Agro2Circular project aimed to establish the initial foundations for the most appropriate CE evaluations of the developed agricultural product systems through applying a novel framework. The monitoring is intended to enable the recurrent assessment of key strengths and challenges in the systems' progress towards circularity and environmental sustainability.

The objective of the application of the CE monitoring framework to A2C demos was to conduct an initial analysis of the systems to test the functionality of the framework to real case studies and learn from how well the framework assists in CE monitoring and assessment. In this study, application of the framework resulted in a curated set of circularity metrics and additional recommendations for relevant metric selection, which aim to guide the practitioners managing the A2C processes. The key target of the monitoring is to analyse the processes, which include various technologies that refine by-product streams to multiple products, to ensure their holistic circularity performance in the defined context. The circularity monitoring was applied to A2C demos 3, 4, 5, 2c, 6, and 8. These demos were selected for analysis to have a variety of novel products which reflect diverse types of systems characterized by distinct features.

The chosen metrics are divided into three categories:

- 1) Recommended metrics for use – This category refers to metrics that are essential for monitoring and assessment of the analysed processes (CE practices)
- 2) Potential relevant metrics to consider – is a list of metrics that were identified to be necessary for the monitoring and assessment but could be not be traced from the reviewed literature
- 3) Additional metrics to consider – Refers to metrics that consider the important aspects related to analysed systems that were out of the scope/system boundaries of the study but could prove beneficial for creating and understanding on systemic level in which by-products for the A2C demos operate (such as estimation of availability of supply of by-products)

8.2.1 Scope of the application

The scope of circularity monitoring in this study was confined to environmental considerations, intentionally excluding economic and social dimensions. Nevertheless, certain selected indicators may incorporate economic parameters, such as market availability, or integrate both environmental and economic aspects to evaluate circularity strategies.

The system boundaries applied in the LCA part of this deliverable were followed in the circularity monitoring. Similarly to LCA, primary agricultural feedstock production was excluded from the analysis. In this study, the term “waste” was applied to by-product material derived from the primary agricultural production, and by-product streams generated within the process, but not the intermediate materials between the A2C demos. The analysis was primarily focused on the current systems in place defined for each demo in the previous chapters as scenario building was beyond the scope of this study. However, in some cases, aspects identified relevant to monitor were grounded on a more hypothetical reasoning to allow a future perspective on what should be monitored. For example, waste generation was uncertain in a specific point of the monitored system with the currently available information; nevertheless, or perhaps for that very reason, it was found crucial to monitor waste disposal for the proper management of potential waste streams.

8.2.2 Criteria applied in the choice of indicators

A list of 95 circularity indicators from the CE monitoring framework was employed to select appropriate indicators. These indicators were primarily identified from the reviewed literature and were updated based on the demo needs with additional sources. The initial list of indicators, derived from the reviewed literature, was revised due to the absence of known and essential metrics that were not present in the examined literature but were deemed crucial for monitoring the demo cases. The additional sources of CE indicators included indicators lists such as the ISO 59020 standard for circularity measurement and assessment, ISO 20200:2023 (Plastics — Determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials under composting conditions), harmonised standards for bioplastics by European Bioplastics, BS EN 13432:2000 (European standard for Requirements for

packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation), GRI Standard for environmental reporting. In accordance with the system boundaries, primarily production process-related indicators were chosen. Furthermore, indicators applicable to the agri-food sector were prioritized. Intrinsic indicators were chosen first, and then those impact indicators which remained unaddressed by LCA impact categories. Holistic indicators that provide broader context were excluded from the selection as the focus of the analysis was on specific production processes (demos). However, examples of potential holistic indicators are provided in the “Additional metrics to consider” category. Holistic metrics may offer a valuable systemic view to the sector, field, or market in which the specific demo production systems operate, which can be important in organizational decision-making. For example, these metrics could help in adjusting and optimizing the process by understanding the material stocks and flows in the surrounding system, including availability of raw materials, and even identifying potential alternative feedstocks. These aspects could be beneficial to monitor even before the TRL of the demos is progressed to analyse the risks related to availability of the raw materials.

As the aim was not to specify a circularity method or composite indicator, i.e., multiple indicators aggregated into a single index or score, for monitoring, these types of metrics were excluded from the selection. Instead, individual relevant indicators were compiled to create a curated set of metrics for each demo. However, in the “additional metrics to consider” category, examples were also suggested for composite indicators that could be particularly useful for these demo systems.

The selection of suitable indicators was informed by multiple factors. Firstly, the suitability of an indicator measurement scope and the applicability of an indicator to the specific production context were assessed. Secondly, the relevance of an indicator for each demo was estimated based on the available information regarding the A2C processes, findings from the LCA (sections 5 and 6), and the authors’ expertise in circularity assessment. Practical feasibility of measuring an indicator was not considered in the selection process. Instead, the metrics were chosen based on relevance and necessity to each demo.

While the proposed metric lists predominantly comprise Circular Economy (CE) metrics, additional metrics have been identified as essential for evaluating the circularity and environmental impacts of processes. As previously mentioned, beyond selecting pertinent metrics for the demonstrations from the set of 95 indicators list, we have suggested additional metrics for consideration that were not encompassed within the scope of the metric search for this study. These metrics include those adapted from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standards or entirely newly proposed as potentially relevant metrics for the analyzed systems, given the absence of exact metrics in the reviewed literature. Given that grey literature was initially excluded from the scope of the literature review, the newly proposed metrics should be considered as a prompt for future research. Upon verification of their existence (rather they potentially exist in some form or not), these metrics could potentially be developed into valuable circular economy (CE) metrics.

The compiled lists of metrics for each demo are non-exhaustive, and with further development of the processes and technologies, new critical aspects to monitor may arise. Moreover, the scope of monitoring could be extended to cover raw materials and end products. The intended use for the list is to provide a starting point for circularity monitoring for the producers of A2C demos. Practitioners of the responsible CE practices and the processes are recommended to complement the suggested list of metrics in this study based on necessity.

8.2.3 Analysis of the A2C demo cases

The framework has been applied to six demos: demo 2c, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 8. As the demos have been described in the LCA section of this report, descriptions of the demos will not be included in this chapter. Relying on the provided information about the demos and by applying the developed CE framework, the focus is on defining what is advisable to be considered in the assessment and monitoring of the developed technologies in this project.

All A2C demos, i.e., stages of the processes, were analysed as individuals, and therefore, some indicators appear in the list for multiple demos of the same process. Complementary

collaboration and information exchange between demos could reduce the potential overlap in their monitoring efforts. The next sections introduce the results of the application of the CE framework to each selected demo.

By following the instructions of the framework, in Step 1, the CE practices have been identified by applying the provided list of CE practices (Table 8-1) for each demo. Since LCA was the predetermined environmental assessment method in this study, we have omitted Step 2 and focused on identification of the relevant intrinsic and impact metrics by applying Step 3 of the framework. In this study, LCA is a well fit environmental impact assessment method as it provides a direct and comprehensive analysis of multiple environmental impact categories across the entire life cycle of a product or process. It assesses impacts related to global warming potential, human health, eutrophication, acidification, and resource depletion, among others offering a detailed understanding of the environmental consequences of specific activities. As the LCA covers a wide range of environmental impact indicators, in Step 3, the focus was on identification of other relevant intrinsic and impact metrics for each demo.

The metrics identified in Step 3 are presented in a table format for each demo. Due to the readability of the report, the detailed list of all relevant metrics has been added into Annex B, which can be found at the end of this document.

8.2.3.1 Demo 3

Demo 3 focuses on the use of agricultural by product/waste in the production of sugar fraction for PHBV to be used further in the production of biodegradable food packaging and agricultural film.

The main activity of demo 3 falls into Recycling of scrap or waste, where the goal is to make use of the waste/byproduct by applying any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes. Table 8-3 shows the list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 3.

Table 8-3. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 3. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)
Waste diverted from disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Industrial waste reused as a source of raw materials in relation to total waste %	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Nutrient extraction from discharged water, %		Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Recycled input materials used in the production	Percentage or Metric tonnes/Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Share of food waste from the sector to total food waste	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Share of reused water in total water use	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic

Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Share of waste after processing of primary product/material	Percentage or Ratio (e.g., kilograms of waste per tonne of product processed)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all process of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Total solid waste output from the process	Percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Global Resource Indicator (GRI)	Typically expressed as a dimensionless index or normalized score (often using energy-equivalent units as part of the calculation)	Additional metric to consider	Impact
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (products)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Value-based Resource Efficiency indicator (VRE)	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic

8.2.3.2 Demo 4

The focus of demo 4 is in use of agricultural by product/waste in the production of dietary fibre and antioxidant extract to be used in new food formulations. The main activity of demo 4 falls into CE practice of Recycling of scrap or waste, where the goal is to make use of the waste/byproduct by applying any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes. Table 8-4 shows the list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 4.

Table 8-4. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 4. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)
Waste diverted from disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Industrial waste reused as a source of raw materials in relation to total waste %	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Nutrient extraction from discharged water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Per cent energy recovered from residual, non-renewable and non-recoverable resource outflows, %	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic

Recycled input materials used in the production	Percentage or Metric tonnes/Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Share of food waste from the sector to total food waste	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Biogenic Carbon Content (%)	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Biodegradable Product Production vs. Local Biodegradation Capacity	Metric tonnes	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Designed biodegradability of a product	Percentage, degradation rate or comparative index	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Share of waste after processing of primary product/material	Percentage or Ratio (e.g., kilograms of waste per tonne of product processed)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all processes of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Total solid waste output from the process	Percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Ecocosts/Value Ratio (EVR)	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless)	Additional metric to consider	Impact

Global Resource Indicator (GRI)	Typically expressed as a dimensionless index or normalized score (often using energy-equivalent units as part of the calculation)	Additional metric to consider	Impact
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (agricultural systems)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Value-based Resource Efficiency indicator (VRE)	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic

8.2.3.3 Demo 5

The focus of this demo is on the use of agricultural by product/waste to produce PHBV to be used in the production of biodegradable food packaging and agricultural film.

Since the production of sugar fraction in demo 5 requires demo 3 processes, this demo falls under Recycling of scrap or waste, where the goal is to make use of the waste/byproduct by applying any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes. Table 8-5 shows the list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 5.

Table 8-5. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 5. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic

Nutrient extraction from discharged water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Biogenic Carbon Content (%)	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Monitoring recirculation of beneficial substances in internal processes	Metric tonnes or percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Reutilisation of excess heat from own or external sources in the production	Kilowatt-hours (kWh) or megajoules (MJ).	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all processes of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (agricultural systems)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic

8.2.3.4 Demo 6

The focus of this demo is on the use of agricultural by product/waste to produce biodegradable pellets for food packaging.

Since the production of biodegradable pellets in demo 6 requires demo 3 processes, this demo falls under Recycling of scrap or waste, where the goal is to make use of the waste/byproduct by applying any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes. Table 8-6 shows the list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 6.

Table 8-6. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 6. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Nutrient extraction from discharged water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic

Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Biogenic Carbon Content (%)	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Biodegradation Rate	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Time to 90% Biodegradation (days)	Time (days)	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all processes of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Total solid waste output from the process	Percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Global Resource Indicator (GRI)	Typically expressed as a dimensionless index or normalized score (often using energy-equivalent units as part of the calculation)	Additional metric to consider	Impact
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (products)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Recycling rate of plastic packaging (percentage)	Percentage	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Disintegration Rate	Percentage	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Heavy Metal Content	Concentration (mg/kg)	Additional metric to consider	Impact

Residual Mass After Biodegradation	Mass fraction (%)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Compost Quality Post-Degradation	Composite parameters (e.g., pH; nutrients in mg/kg; moisture %)	Additional metric to consider	Impact

8.2.3.5 Demo 8

The focus of this demo is on the use of agricultural by product/waste to produce biodegradable pellets for agriculture film.

Since the production of biodegradable pellets in demo 8 requires demo 3 processes, this demo falls under Recycling of scrap or waste, where the goal is to make use of the waste/byproduct by applying any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes. Table 8-7 shows the list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 8.

Table 8-7. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 8. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)
Biodegradation Rate	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Biogenic Carbon Content (%)	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Nutrient extraction from discharged water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic

Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Time to 90% Biodegradation (days)	Time (days)	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all processes of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Total solid waste output from the process	Percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Compost Quality Post-Degradation	Composite parameters (e.g., pH; nutrients in mg/kg; moisture %)	Additional metric to consider	Impact
Disintegration Rate	Percentage	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Global Resource Indicator (GRI)	Typically expressed as a dimensionless index or normalized score (often using energy-equivalent units as part of the calculation)	Additional metric to consider	Impact
Heavy Metal Content	Concentration (mg/kg)	Additional metric to consider	Impact

Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (products)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
Residual Mass After Biodegradation	Mass fraction (%)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic

8.2.3.6 Demo 2c

The focus of this demo is on the use of agricultural by-product/waste to produce sugary fraction that is used in the production of microbial oil.

Since the production of sugar fraction in demo 2c requires demo 3 processes, this demo falls under Recycling of scrap or waste, where the goal is to make use of the waste/by-product by applying any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials, or substances, whether for the original or other purposes. Table 8-8 shows the list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 2c.

Table 8-8. The list of relevant indicators to be monitored in demo 2c. A full table with the descriptions of the indicators and sources are presented in Annex B.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)
Biogenic Carbon Content (%)	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic

Nutrient extraction from discharged water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all processes of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	Intrinsic
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	Intrinsic
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	Intrinsic

8.3 Discussion and conclusions

The novel circularity monitoring framework presented in this deliverable offers a guided step-by-step path for practitioners on monitoring circular economy and provides demonstration with case studies for its application. The developed framework was applied to selected A2C demos with the objective to test the functionality of the framework to real case studies and to learn from how well the framework assists in CE monitoring and assessment. The

framework contributes to the project's objectives by incorporating circularity metrics to the environmental assessment, which can be applied in the A2C territorial multidimensional model enhancing materials reuse, recycling and waste minimisation. The overarching aim of the framework is to provide means for CE monitoring that reveals the progress that is achieved via deployment of chosen CE practices.

Based on the literature review, there is already a valuable pool of studies that aim to categorise, organise and rationalise the use of CE metrics. As demonstrated, the developed framework builds strongly on existing studies. While there are useful and applicable frameworks for measuring the CE, the results show evident lack of categorisation of the CE metrics based on their intrinsic and impact type. This lack can hinder the comprehensive progress assessment of the CE practices, including the realisation of the CE as such but most importantly the achieved impacts.

The application of the framework in the A2C case study demonstrates that by following these steps, crucial elements in case-specific CE monitoring can be identified in a more efficient manner, and the harmony of circularity metrics with impact-based methods, such as LCA, can be improved. In this A2C study, through the perspective provided by the presented framework, the focus was on identifying critical elements to consider in CE monitoring of the demo systems. The application of the framework yielded a list of suggested circularity monitoring metrics aimed to provide a tangible approach for the A2C demo practitioners to assess the development of their activities relevant to CE. Most of the suggested metrics fall into the category of intrinsic indicators, providing supporting value to the environmental impact indicators of LCA. The CE monitoring framework and LCA support each other by offering suitable indicators to broaden the environmental sustainability perspective. One key conclusion of the LCA was the necessity of not only using waste as raw material but also enhancing energy and material efficiency, which the CE monitoring framework facilitates by offering tools to monitor relevant indicators. It was also noted in the LCA that it is possible to utilize side streams and increase material recirculation, actions that the framework supports.

To further develop the framework, it is suggested to improve its usability and integration with environmental impact assessments, fostering a more comprehensive evaluation of circular practices and their impacts. Efforts will be concentrated on simplifying the indicator analysis process, ensuring that the framework continues to provide valuable insights and practical guidance for practitioners striving towards sustainability and circular economy goals.

Remarks on the deployment and labor required for CE monitoring

Implementing CE monitoring for any evaluated system, practice, or product for the first time necessitates significant labor, particularly in data acquisition. Depending on the methods applied in the assessment, data requirements can range from highly detailed to large-scale. Deploying an impact assessment method, such as LCA, demands data and knowledge at the production level, which is often the same data needed for monitoring many intrinsic metrics recommended in this work.

The intrinsic metrics, aligned with the realisation of the CE itself, like those assessed in this study, are frequently linked to production processes. While the information obtained from these intrinsic metrics describes the assessed case, it does not inherently indicate the impact being generated. However, they can be crucial for evaluating the impact.

Overall, the proposed indicators aim to inform the responsible owner of the CE practice about the progress being made. As stated, some of the recommended metrics will inform on the realisation of the CE while serving as valuable information for impact assessments. Chosen impact assessments, on the other hand, provide answers regarding the impact of the assessed CE practice. Together, these two types of monitoring metrics offer an understanding of the progress. As suggested, impact assessment methods should be selected based on the questions of interest to ensure the methodology can address the types of questions relevant to the monitoring body and the CE practice that is being assessed.

The indicators highlighted in this work within demos cover information from micro to macro levels. Most intrinsic metrics require a thorough understanding of the assessed

product/system but are relatively straightforward in acquisition and calculation, such as the share of recycled input or the amount of rainwater used in the production. Monitoring these metrics annually is sufficient.

Some intrinsic metrics, as seen in our case studies, are closely tied to production processes. Depending on the inputs used in production, some recommended metrics, like energy profile and water source, could be monitored based on production variability annually. For instance, the hotspot analysis obtained from the LCA can help determine which inputs to monitor more closely. This information can provide insight into the effect of a particular energy source or chemical during a specific production period.

Finally, a segment of the proposed metrics sheds light on the broader context concerning the sector or primary materials employed by the industry. Among the additional metrics suggested for consideration in this study is the Global Resource Indicator (GRI). This metric offers a comprehensive evaluation of the efficiency with which both renewable and non-renewable resources are utilized and conserved throughout the lifecycle of a product or system. Implementing these metrics is significantly more labor-intensive than the acquisition and monitoring of most intrinsic metrics discussed in this study. Nevertheless, they can provide crucial insights for decision-making. For example, the GRI metric can indicate the status of strategic materials used in production. Ideally, monitoring this type of metric is an ongoing process, but the information is gathered through assessments conducted at specific intervals, which can be updated in defined cycles based on the nature and condition of the particular input. Factors such as regional availability, global market fluctuations, and increasing physical and transitional risks due to climate change can all influence the state of the inputs used.

In conclusion, it is the practitioner's duty to establish the necessary cycle for updating the list of monitored metrics. In today's rapidly changing world, no system operates in isolation from the broader economic environment, making it advisable to include metrics that consider the larger context beyond individual operations. As a general rule, any change related to the assessed product or system should be reflected in the monitoring, even if it occurs outside

the established update cycles. Naturally, the seriousness and implications of each metric should be evaluated in relation to the operation and assets in use.

The set of metrics chosen for each demonstration is specifically tailored to that demo and is firmly grounded in the information generated in this project. The list of metrics provided in this study is intended to serve as a starting point for responsible monitoring bodies. Assuming that these processes will continue to evolve, we recommend that responsible actors reassess the adequacy of the proposed list and make necessary additions and modifications as the processes develop further. For instance, the operating region, varying inputs, and any changes made to these analyzed production processes can influence the proposed list of metrics.

9 Bibliography

Adibi, N., Lafhaj, Z., Yehya, M., & Payet, J. (2017). Global Resource Indicator for life cycle impact assessment: Applied in wind turbine case study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 165, 1517-1528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.07.226>

Alivojvodic, V., & Kokalj, F. (2024). Drivers and Barriers for the Adoption of Circular Economy Principles towards Efficient Resource Utilisation. *Sustainability*, 16(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16031317>

AWARE. <https://wulca-waterlca.org/aware/download-aware-factors/> [Accessed 21.3.2025].

ASTM International. (2022). *Standard test methods for determining the biobased content of solid, liquid, and gaseous samples using radiocarbon analysis (ASTM D6866-22)*. ASTM International. <https://store.astm.org/d6866-22.html>

British Standards Institution. (2000). *BS EN 13432:2000 Packaging. Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation. Test scheme and evaluation criteria for the final acceptance of packaging*. <https://www.en-standard.eu/bs-en-13432-2000-packaging.-requirements-for-packaging-recoverable-through-composting-and-biodegradation.-test-scheme-and-evaluation-criteria-for-the-final-acceptance-of-packaging/>

Cader, J., Koneczna, R., & Marciniak, A. (2024). Indicators for a circular economy in a regional context: an approach based on Wielkopolska region, Poland. *Environ Manage*, 73(2), 293-310. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-023-01887-w>

Corona, B., Shen, L., Reike, D., Rosales Carreón, J., & Worrell, E. (2019). Towards sustainable development through the circular economy—A review and critical assessment on current circularity metrics. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 151, 104498. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104498>

Di Maio, F., Rem, P. C., Baldé, K., & Polder, M. (2017). Measuring resource efficiency and circular economy: A market value approach. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 122, 163-171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.02.009>

Elia, V., Gnoni, M. G., & Tornese, F. (2017). Measuring circular economy strategies through index methods: A critical analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, 2741-2751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.196>

European Bioplastics. (n.d.). Harmonised standards for bioplastics. <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics/standards/>

Eurostat. (2020). Contribution of recycled materials to raw materials demand - end-of-life recycling input rates (EOL-RIR) (cei_srm010). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/cei_srm010_esmsip2.htm

Eurostat. (2023). Monitoring framework - Circular economy. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/circular-economy/monitoring-framework>

Fagone, C., Santamicone, M., & Villa, V. (2023). Architecture Engineering and Construction Industrial Framework for Circular Economy: Development of a Circular Construction Site Methodology. *Sustainability*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15031813>

Fassio, F., & Chirilli, C. (2023). The Circular Economy and the Food System: A Review of Principal Measuring Tools. *Sustainability*, 15(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151310179>

Garza-Reyes, J. A., Salomé Valls, A., Peter Nadeem, S., Anosike, A., & Kumar, V. (2018). A circularity measurement toolkit for manufacturing SMEs. *International Journal of Production Research*, 57(23), 7319-7343. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2018.1559961>

Global Reporting Initiative. (n.d.). GRI Standards English Language. <https://www.globalreporting.org/how-to-use-the-gri-standards/gri-standards-english-language/>

Gursel, I., Elbersen, B., Meesters, K. P. H., & van Leeuwen, M. (2022). Defining Circular Economy Principles for Biobased Products. *Sustainability*, 14(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912780>

Helander, H., Petit-Boix, A., Leipold, S., & Bringezu, S. (2019). How to monitor environmental pressures of a circular economy: An assessment of indicators. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 23(5), 1278-1291. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12924>

Hingsamer, M. et al. (2022) Environmental and socio-economic impacts of new plant breeding technologies: A case study of root chicory for inulin production. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fgeed.2022.919392/full>

International Organization for Standardization. (2006a). Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework (ISO Standard No. ISO 14040:2006)

International Organization for Standardization. (2006b). Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines (ISO Standard No. ISO 14044:2006).

International Organization for Standardization. (2012). Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions — Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide (ISO Standard No. ISO 14855-1:2012). <https://www.iso.org/standard/57902.html>

International Organization for Standardization. (2021). Plastics — Organic recycling — Specifications for compostable plastics (ISO Standard No. 17088:2021). <https://www.iso.org/standard/74994.html>

International Organization for Standardization. (2022). *ISO/IEC 27002:2022 – Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Information security controls*. <https://www.iso.org/standard/75652.html>

International Organization for Standardization. (2023). *Plastics — Determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials under composting conditions in a laboratory-scale test (ISO 20200:2023)*. ISO. <https://www.iso.org/standard/81932.html>

International Organization for Standardization. (2024). Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity performance (ISO Standard No. 59020:2024). <https://www.iso.org/standard/80650.html>

Lokesh, K., Matharu, A. S., Kookos, I. K., Ladakis, D., Koutinas, A., Morone, P., & Clark, J. (2020). Hybridised sustainability metrics for use in life cycle assessment of bio-based products: resource efficiency and circularity. *Green Chemistry*, 22(3), 803-813. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9gc02992c>

Luthin, A., Traverso, M., & Crawford, R. H. (2023). Circular life cycle sustainability assessment: An integrated framework. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 28(1), 41-58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13446>

Masi, D., Kumar, V., Garza-Reyes, J. A., & Godsell, J. (2018). Towards a more circular economy: exploring the awareness, practices, and barriers from a focal firm perspective. *Production Planning & Control*, 29(6), 539-550. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2018.1449246>

Nessi, S., Sinkko, T., Bulgheroni, C., Garbarino, E., Garcia-Gutierrez, P., Giuntoli, J., Konti, A., Orveillon, G., Sanye Mengual, E., Tonini, D., Pant, R., Marelli, L. and Ardente, F. (2022). Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of alternative feedstocks for plastics production, EUR 31085 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-52959-0, doi:10.2760/234548, JRC127175.

Pajula, T., Vatanen, S., Behm, K., Grönman, K., Lakanen, L., Kasurinen, H., & Soukka, R. (2021). Carbon handprint guide: V. 2.0 Applicable for environmental handprint. VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland. https://publications.vtt.fi/julkaisut/muut/2021/Carbon_handprint_guide_2021.pdf

Razza, F., Briani, C., Breton, T., & Marazza, D. (2020). Metrics for quantifying the circularity of bioplastics: The case of bio-based and biodegradable mulch films. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 159, 104753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104753>

Rocchi, L., Paolotti, L., Cortina, C., Fagioli, F. F., & Boggia, A. (2021). Measuring circularity: An application of modified Material Circularity Indicator to agricultural systems. *Agricultural and Food Economics*, 9(9). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40100-021-00182-8>

Sassanelli, C., Rosa, P., Rocca, R., & Terzi, S. (2019). Circular Economy performance assessment methods: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 440-453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.019>

Vogtländer, J. G., Bijma, A., & Brezet, H. C. (2002). Communicating the eco-efficiency of products and services by means of the eco-costs/value model. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 10(1), 57-67. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-6526\(01\)00013-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-6526(01)00013-0)

Walzberg, J., Lonca, G., Hanes, R. J., Eberle, A. L., Carpenter, A., & Heath, G. A. (2021). Do we need a new sustainability assessment method for the circular economy? A critical literature review. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 1, 620047. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2020.620047>

Zaman, A. U., & Lehmann, S. (2013). The zero waste index: A performance measurement tool for waste management systems in a 'zero waste city'. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 31, 1-14. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Atiq-Zaman/publication/261925208_The_zero_waste_index/links/0f317535f5bf0e8130000000/The-zero-waste-index.pdf

10 Annex

ANNEX A: Used ecoinvent 3.10 chemicals in the demo 2 b LCI Table 6-3.

Data	ecoinvent 3.10 process	Geography
hydrochloric acid	market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state	RER
ammonium sulfate	market for ammonium sulfate	RER
calcium chloride	market for calcium chloride	RER
EDTA	market for EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid	GLO
glucose	market for glucose	GLO
ammonium hydroxide	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
cobalt(II) chloride	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
copper(II) sulfate	market for copper sulfate	GLO
dipotassium phosphate	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
iron(II) sulfate	market for iron sulfate	RER
kanamycin	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
magnesium dichloride	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
manganese(II) chloride	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
monosodium phosphate	market for sodium phosphate	RER
sodium molybdate	market for chemical, inorganic	GLO
yeast extract	market for fodder yeast	GLO
zinc sulfate	zinc sulfide production	RER

Annex B: Full list of indicators with detailed information applied in demo cases.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Waste diverted from disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	This metric captures the total weight of waste diverted from disposal, measured in metric tonnes. It includes a breakdown by waste composition, hazardous versus non-hazardous status, recovery operation (e.g., preparation for reuse, recycling), and whether disposal was onsite or offsite. All relevant contextual factors, such as methodologies and assumptions, are also provided.	Intrinsic	GRI Standard.
Biodegradation Rate	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This indicator measures the percentage of material's organic carbon that is converted into CO ₂ (aerobic) or CH ₄ (anaerobic) by microbial activity under controlled composting conditions.	Intrinsic	International Organization for Standardization. (2012). ISO 14855-1:2012 – Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions
Biogenic Carbon Content (%)	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This indicator measures the fraction of carbon in a plastic that originates from renewable (biobased) sources using radiocarbon analysis.	Intrinsic	ASTM International. (2022). ASTM D6866-22 – Standard Test Methods for Determining the Biobased Content of Solid, Liquid, and Gaseous Samples Using Radiocarbon Analysis
Industrial waste reused as a source of raw materials in relation to total waste %	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the percentage of industrial waste that is reused as a source of raw materials relative to the total industrial waste generated, expressed as a percentage (%). It helps assess the circularity of industrial processes and the extent to which waste is repurposed into valuable raw materials instead of being discarded.	Intrinsic	Cader et al. (2024)
Energy consumption within the production process	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	This metric quantifies the total energy consumed during a specific production process, expressed in joules, watt hours or appropriate multiples. It includes detailed measurements of all energy inputs—covering fuel consumption from both non-renewable and renewable sources (with fuel types specified) and the use of electricity, heating, cooling, and steam. Additionally, it accounts for any energy outputs sold (e.g., surplus electricity or steam) that are directly associated with the production process.	Intrinsic	Adapted from GRI Standard.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Imp act)	Source
Per cent energy recovered from residual, non-renewable and non-recoverable resource outflows, %	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This metric quantifies the proportion of energy recovered from residual resource outflows—specifically, those derived from non-renewable and non-recoverable resources that, due to technological, economic, environmental, social, or regulatory constraints, cannot be reused as material inputs—relative to the total energy inflow into the system. In practice, this involves converting waste or low-value by-products (such as those processed via incineration with energy recovery, pyrolysis, gasification, or biogas production) into usable energy.	Intrinsic	International Organization for Standardization. (2024). ISO 59020:2024, Section B.4.2
Energy intensity	Joules, watt-hours or multiples	Recommended metric for use	This metric assesses the efficiency of a specific production process by comparing the total energy consumed (including fuel, electricity, heating, cooling, steam, etc.) against a measure that best reflects production activity—such as the number of units produced, production volume, or production hours. In this way, it shows how much energy is used per unit of output. The metric also specifies whether it includes energy used directly in production, energy used in supporting processes, or both, helping to target improvements in process efficiency.	Intrinsic	Adapted from GRI Standard.
Recycled input materials used in the production	Percentage or Metric tonnes/Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the proportion of input materials sourced from recycled streams that are used in the production process. It can be expressed as a percentage of total input materials or in terms of mass/volume (e.g., kilograms or liters) relative to the overall raw material usage. The indicator provides insight into the level of integration of secondary, recycled materials in the production process, reflecting progress in reducing reliance on virgin resources.	Intrinsic	Adapted from GRI Standard.
Share of food waste from the sector to total food waste	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the proportion of food waste generated by a specific sector (e.g., agri-food industry) relative to the total food waste generated across all sectors. It provides insight into the contribution of a given sector to overall food waste.	Intrinsic	Cader et al. (2024)
Materials used by weight or volume	Metric tonnes or Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	This metric captures the total weight or volume of materials employed in producing and packaging an organization’s primary products and services during a selected production period. It distinguishes between non-renewable and renewable materials, thereby providing insights into resource utilization and sustainability performance.	Intrinsic	Adapted from GRI Standard.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Nutrient extraction from discharged water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This metric expresses the effectiveness of nutrient removal from water that is discharged from the system in focus. It is calculated by comparing either the volume of water that has been treated (i.e., from which surplus nutrients have been extracted) to the total water discharged (Method A) or the mass of nutrients extracted relative to the mass originally present in the discharged water (Method B). In both cases, the result is expressed as a percentage, indicating the proportion of nutrients successfully removed before discharge. Typical measurement units include cubic meters (m ³) for water volumes and kilograms (kg) for nutrient masses, but the final output is dimensionless. This approach ensures that excess nutrients, which could otherwise contribute to environmental issues like eutrophication, are effectively extracted and potentially recovered for further use.	Intrinsic	International Organization for Standardization. (2024). ISO 59020:2024, Section B.5.2
Per cent water discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This metric assesses the extent to which water discharged from a system meets specified quality standards. It is calculated by dividing the volume of water that is discharged in compliance with the quality requirements (which could include specific limits for pollutants, pH levels, turbidity, etc.) by the total volume of water discharged, and then multiplying by 100. The result, expressed as a percentage, indicates the level of compliance with water quality criteria, thereby reflecting the system's performance in managing effluent quality.	Intrinsic	International Organization for Standardization. (2024). ISO 59020:2024, Section A.5.3
Ratio (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation, dimensionless	Ratio	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the circularity of water within a facility over a reporting period. It is calculated by comparing the total volume of water reused or recirculated on-site (after undergoing the necessary containment and treatment for reuse) to the total volume of water withdrawn from external sources. The ratio indicates the extent to which water is internally managed within the facility; values exceeding 1.0 imply that the facility's water requirements are being met not only by direct withdrawal but also by on-site recirculation and reuse. This metric is dimensionless, as it represents a pure ratio between two volumetric flows.	Intrinsic	International Organization for Standardization. (2024). ISO 59020:2024, Section A.5.4.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Reuse rate of industrial water	Percentage	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the percentage of industrial water that is reused within a specific process or sector relative to the total industrial water used, expressed as a percentage (%). It helps assess the efficiency of water management in industrial processes and tracks the extent to which water resources are reused rather than consumed.	Intrinsic	Cader et al. (2024)
The amount of rainwater used	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the proportion of water that is reused within a specific process or sector relative to the total water used, expressed as a percentage (%). It helps assess the efficiency of water use and the extent to which water resources are being reused rather than consumed.	Intrinsic	Cader et al. (2024)
Time to 90% Biodegradation (days)	Time (days)	Recommended metric for use	This indicator measures the time required for a plastic material to achieve 90% conversion of its carbon to CO ₂ (or CH ₄) under standardized composting conditions.	Intrinsic	International Organization for Standardization. (2012). ISO 14855-1:2012 – Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions
Waste directed to disposal	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the total weight of waste sent for disposal, expressed in metric tonnes. It includes detailed breakdowns by waste composition, disposal operation (e.g., incineration, landfilling), and whether the waste is hazardous or non-hazardous. The data also distinguish between onsite and offsite disposal, and any relevant contextual factors (such as methodologies or assumptions) are documented.	Intrinsic	GRI Standard.
Waste generated	Metric tonnes	Recommended metric for use	This metric captures the total weight of waste produced, measured in metric tonnes. It also provides a detailed breakdown of the waste by its composition.	Intrinsic	GRI Standard.
Water consumption	Cubic meters	Recommended metric for use	This metric measures the total volume of water consumed in a specific sector or process, expressed in cubic meters (m ³). It helps assess the intensity of water use within a system and provides insight into the sustainability of water consumption practices.	Intrinsic	Cader et al. (2024)

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Water withdrawal	Megaliters	Recommended metric for use	This metric quantifies the total volume of water withdrawn (in megaliters) across all areas. It includes a detailed breakdown by water source—surface water, groundwater, seawater, produced water, and third-party water—as well as data specific to regions under water stress. Additionally, it provides subdivisions based on water quality (freshwater with ≤1,000 mg/L TDS versus other water with >1,000 mg/L TDS) and includes contextual notes regarding the methodologies, standards, and assumptions used in the data compilation.	Intrinsic	GRI Standard.
Biodegradable Product Production vs. Local Biodegradation Capacity	Metric tonnes	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric compares the mass of produced biodegradable products—expressed in metric tonnes—to the available industrial biodegradation capacity in the market area, typically also expressed in metric tonnes per year. It is reported as a ratio or percentage, indicating how the production volume aligns with or exceeds the local infrastructure’s capacity to process biodegradable materials.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.
Designed biodegradability of a product	Percentage, degradation rate or comparative index	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric assesses the inherent biodegradability built into a product’s design. It reflects the extent to which the product is formulated to break down under defined environmental conditions (e.g., industrial composting or landfill scenarios) within a specified time frame. The evaluation can be based on standardized biodegradability tests or performance criteria, with results expressed as a percentage, degradation rate, or comparative index.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.
Share of waste after processing of primary product/material	Percentage or Ratio (e.g., kilograms of waste per tonne of product processed)	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric quantifies the proportion of waste generated during the processing of a primary agricultural products —after the product has been processed according to the desired or required specifications at the previous stage. This metric is for informing the following producer/processor about the share of waste that is left out of the primary product/material after it has already been processed, such as peels, pulp, seeds. It is typically expressed as a percentage of the input material or as a ratio based on a chosen unit of measure (e.g., kilograms of waste per tonne of product processed). This indicator is to assist the sector and the users of the waste/byproduct to be able to assess and estimate the quantities of the available substitute material through CE.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
The share of solid matter in discharged water from all processes of the production	Percentage or Concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter)	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric measures the proportion of solid matter in the water discharged from all production processes. It is typically expressed as a percentage or as a concentration (e.g., milligrams per liter). This indicator helps assess the effectiveness of water treatment and waste reduction practices in the production process.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.
Monitoring recirculation of beneficial substances in internal processes	Metric tonnes or percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric tracks the extent to which beneficial substances—such as nutrients or chemicals—that would normally be sourced externally are recirculated and reused within internal production processes. It aims to quantify how effectively the production system recovers and re-integrates these substances, thereby reducing the need for additional external inputs. The metric can be expressed in mass units (e.g., kilograms or tonnes) or as a percentage of total input usage.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.
Total solid waste output from the process	Percentage	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric expresses the percentage of solid waste generated by a production process relative to the total material input or processed output. It is calculated by dividing the mass (or volume, when applicable) of solid waste by the overall mass (or volume) of materials used, then multiplying by 100 to yield a percentage. This indicator helps evaluate process efficiency, identify opportunities for waste minimization, and support improvements toward sustainability goals by highlighting the effectiveness of waste reduction practices.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.
Reutilisation of excess heat from own or external sources in the production	Kilowatt-hours (kWh) or megajoules (MJ).	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric quantifies the amount of excess heat—sourced either internally during production or obtained from external supplies—that is recovered and reused within the production process. The recovered heat is measured in an energy unit such as kilowatt-hours (kWh) or megajoules (MJ). This indicator helps evaluate the effectiveness of thermal energy recovery initiatives in reducing overall energy consumption by integrating reutilised heat back into the production cycle.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Waste/by-product reusability potential in the next application (Energy or Product)	Percentage or Ratio	Potential relevant metric to consider	This metric assesses the extent to which waste or by-products generated in the production process are recognized to have an alternative use—either as an energy source or as a raw material for a new product—even though they are not currently utilized by the producer. It is typically expressed as a percentage or ratio (based on mass, volume, or energy content) relative to the total waste/by-product output. The metric includes contextual details on the feasibility of these potential applications, such as technical suitability, market demand, and infrastructure readiness, supporting decision-making aimed at improving resource efficiency and promoting circular economy practices.	Intrinsic	Proposing development of a novel metric—absent in reviewed literature.
Ecocosts/Value Ratio (EVR)	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless)	Additional metric to consider	This metric measures the eco-efficiency of a product or service by comparing the environmental costs incurred over its lifecycle (eco-costs) to its economic value. It reflects how much environmental burden is generated per unit of economic output.	Impact	Vogtländer et al. (2002)
Compost Quality Post-Degradation	Composite parameters (e.g., pH; nutrients in mg/kg; moisture %)	Additional metric to consider	This indicator measures key agronomic properties (pH, nutrient levels, moisture) of compost made after plastic degradation to ensure it meets agricultural standards.	Impact	International Organization for Standardization. (2021). ISO 17088:2021 – Plastics — Organic recycling — Specifications for compostable plastics.
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (agricultural systems)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	This metric adapts the original MCI to assess circularity specifically within agricultural systems. It measures the proportion of bio-based and biodegradable inputs that are recovered through biological processes—such as composting, anaerobic digestion, or natural biodegradation—taking into account agricultural-specific flows and residue management.	Intrinsic	Rocchi et al. (2021)

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Disintegration Rate	Percentage	Additional metric to consider	This indicator measures the fraction of a plastic sample that physically breaks down into fragments smaller than 2 mm during industrial composting.	Intrinsic	EN 13432:2000 – Packaging – Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation
Global Resource Indicator (GRI)	Typically expressed as a dimensionless index or normalized score (often using energy-equivalent units as part of the calculation)	Additional metric to consider	This metric quantifies resource depletion potential by integrating multiple resource-related factors—such as criticality, recyclability, and regeneration rates—within a life cycle assessment framework. It provides a holistic measure of how efficiently both renewable and non-renewable resources are used and preserved across a product or system’s lifecycle.	Impact	Adibi et al. (2017)

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Heavy Metal Content	Concentration (mg/kg)	Additional metric to consider	This indicator measures the concentration of regulated heavy metals in compost derived from biodegraded plastics to ensure soil safety.	Impact	EN 13432:2000 – Packaging – Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) adapted to biological cycles (products)	Dimensionless Index (expressed on a normalized scale, e.g., 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	This metric adapts the traditional MCI for bio-based and biodegradable products (e.g., mulch films) by measuring the proportion of bio-based feedstock that is recovered via biological processes—such as composting or biodegradation—thus treating biodegradation as an equivalent end-of-life recovery process.	Intrinsic	Razza et al. (2020)
Value-based Resource Efficiency indicator (VRE)	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless)	Additional metric to consider	This metric quantifies the efficiency with which a production process converts stressed resources—those scarce or with high market value—into added economic value. It is expressed as the ratio of the value added by a product or service to the market value of the stressed resources consumed during production.	Intrinsic	Di Maio et al. (2017)
Recycling rate of plastic packaging (percentage)	Percentage	Additional metric to consider	This metric represents the efficiency of plastic packaging waste recovery by calculating the percentage of total plastic packaging waste that is collected and recycled. It is determined by dividing the weight of recycled plastic packaging by the overall weight of plastic packaging waste generated, then expressing the result as a percentage. This indicator helps assess progress toward circular economy targets by providing insights into the effectiveness of waste management practices and recycling policies.	Intrinsic	Eurostat (2023)

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
Residual Mass After Biodegradation	Mass fraction (%)	Additional metric to consider	This indicator measures the remaining dry mass of a plastic sample after exposure to composting conditions for a defined period.	Intrinsic	ISO 20200:2023 – Plastics — Determination of the degree of disintegration of plastic materials under composting conditions
Hybridised sustainability metrics	Dimensionless composite index (typically normalized on a scale, e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	This suite of hybridised metrics integrates standardized LCA impact categories with green chemistry, resource efficiency, and circularity indicators to provide a comprehensive evaluation of a product's sustainability performance. It captures diverse dimensions— including hazardous chemical use, waste generation, energy efficiency, and resource recirculation—to offer a multi-faceted view of a product's environmental performance.	Impact	Lokesh et al. (2020)
Contribution of recycled materials to raw materials demand	Percentage or Ratio (dimensionless)	Additional metric to consider	This metric assesses the extent to which recycled materials satisfy the overall demand for raw materials. It is typically expressed as the percentage of total raw material consumption met by recycled content. In addition to measuring volume, it also considers the quality and suitability of recycled materials in fulfilling production requirements compared to virgin resources.	Intrinsic	Eurostat (2020), Fassio and Chirilli (2023).
Sustainable Circular Index (SCI)	Dimensionless Index (often scaled from 0 to 1 or 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	This composite index assesses the sustainability and circularity performance of manufacturing companies by integrating multiple indicators (e.g., resource efficiency, recycling, waste reduction, and sustainable practices). It provides a benchmarking tool to evaluate and compare companies' progress in transitioning toward circular economy principles.		Azevedo et al. (2017)

Indicator	Unit of Measure	Relevance for studied case	Description	Metric Type (Intrinsic/Impact)	Source
ZeroWaste index	Ratio or Percentage (dimensionless) – Often expressed as a normalized score on a scale (e.g., 0 to 100)	Additional metric to consider	This metric measures the performance of waste management systems by estimating the extent to which recovered resources substitute for virgin materials, energy, water, and greenhouse gas emissions. It reflects how effectively a system diverts waste from disposal and reintroduces materials into the economy, supporting a zero-waste approach.	Intrinsic	Zaman and Lehmann (2013)

